

Realistic Quantum Theory

Solving the Interpretation Problem

(English version)

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Abstract

In 2018, a new systematic approach to solving the interpretation problem of quantum theory was published (in German) under the title “Realistische Quantentheorie” (Realistic Quantum Theory) [2]. A postprint of this publication can be found in the Mathematical Physics Preprint Archive as well as the Zenodo repository.

The new approach comprises a canonical modeling of quantum reality, a precise formulation of the deterministic and probabilistic laws, proof of the logical consistency of these laws (thus solving the well-known no-go problems), unequivocal definition of the quantum state and clarification of its ontological status, solution to the problem of measurement and clarification of the role played by the reduction of quantum states.

Ambiguities of the Copenhagen interpretation are avoided, as are speculative concepts of many-worlds theories or attempts to adhere to outdated particle concepts (Bohmian mechanics). Also avoided are pseudo-philosophical speculations about subjectivism or phenomenalism as expressed in the assertion that the world is “nothing but information”.

In this text, the main results of this new approach are reported (part A). Necessary derivations and proofs are included (part B). A more detailed description of this solution to the interpretation problem can be found in the summary (p. 7).

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(English version)

Preface

Quantum theory is the most fundamental theory in physics. It thus also forms the basis of our entire scientific understanding of nature. However, its logical and epistemological foundations are not really understood to this day. Despite all practical success of the quantum theoretical formalism, the question of what quantum theory tells us about the real universe has still not clearly been answered.

Dissatisfied with this situation, the author has spent many years investigating the question of how this “interpretation problem” can be solved in a systematic way, apart from the existing rather speculative (and in part somewhat mystical) attempts that have been made up to now. This has finally led to an approach the author has published some years ago (in German) under the title “Realistische Quantentheorie” (Realistic Quantum Theory) [2].

The author starts from the assumption that there can be no solution to the interpretation problem without a logically sound basis. This applies in particular to the fundamentals of the concept of probability, which is ultimately required in every physical theory. Here, it becomes apparent that it is not sufficient for physics to be based on the usual Kolmogorov concept of probability. Although this concept is suitable for describing individual experiments, difficulties arise when formulating general physical laws, in particular in connection with Bell’s inequality. This fact has received little attention in the physical discussion so far.

Part A of the present text shares the essential results of the theory developed in [2]. The necessary mathematical derivations and proofs can be found in part B. Theorems and definitions given there are cited as T.x.x or D.x.x, respectively.

The theory discussed here includes:

- canonical modeling of the structure of the quantum world as objective reality,
- precise formulation of deterministic and probabilistic laws based on a general concept of probability,
- proof of the consistency of these laws and thus a solution to the well-known no-go problems (Bell’s inequality, Kochen-Specker theorem),
- clear definition of quantum systems, quantum states, physical objects, etc., with clarification of their respective ontological status,
- solving the problem of measurement and clarifying the role of state reduction.

Overall, this theory turns out to be a complete solution to the interpretation problem.

The ambiguities of the “Copenhagen interpretation” are avoided here, as are speculative concepts of many-worlds theories or attempts to adhere to the outdated idea of classical particles (as in Bohmian mechanics). Unfounded pseudo-philosophical speculations about subjectivism or phenomenalism, as expressed in the pointed statement that the world is “nothing but information”, are avoided as well.

In February 2026

Rudolf Lierenfeldt

Contents

<i>Preface</i>	3
<i>Summary</i>	7

PART A Realistic Quantum Theory

1. Role and relevance of the interpretation problem	10
2. How can the interpretation problem be solved?	11
3. Modeling reality in quantum theory	12
4. The model of quantum theory and the classical approximation	13
5. Deterministic laws of quantum theory	16
6. The algebra of possible facts in the model of quantum theory	18
7. The problem of Bell's inequality	20
8. Kolmogorov's concept of probability	21
9. The general concept of probability	22
10. The concept of probability in physics	24
11. The probabilistic law of quantum theory	25
12. Definition of quantum states	27
13. Deterministic and probabilistic states	29
14. The compatibility of determinism and probabilism	31
15. The initial condition	33
16. Macroscopic documents	33
17. Empirical accessibility	34
18. Macroscopic experiments and their probability measure	35
19. Quantum experiments and the Copenhagen formalism	36
20. Reduction of quantum states and the problem of measurement	38
21. Physical objects	41
22. The model of the microscopic and its intuitiveness	43
23. Weirdness and philosophical consequences of quantum theory	45

PART B Mathematical Appendix

Chapter B0. Basic Definitions	50
Chapter B1. Axioms of quantum theory and the Kochen-Specker theorem	57
1. The consistency of the axiom system	57
2. Observables and their values	58
3. The inconsistency of the physical “tertium non datur”	58
Chapter B2. Classical mechanics	62
1. Representation of classical mechanics by an axiom system	62
2. The empirical content of the strong and weak classical theories	68
3. Definition of probabilistic states in classical mechanics	71
Chapter B3. The Schrödinger equation	72
Chapter B4. Bell’s inequality	78
1. Logical inconsistency due to Bell’s inequality	78
2. Incompatibility of Kolmogorov’s probability theory with quantum realism .	81
Chapter B5. The law of probability in quantum theory	83
1. The Euclidean norm on the space of continuous operators	83
2. The subspace-metric δ on the set \mathcal{U} of linear subspaces of \mathcal{H}	86
3. Definition of the mapping ρ on the set \mathcal{A}^\wedge of all finite logical conjunctions of events, with its characterizing property	89
4. Definition of the outer measure μ on the algebra \mathcal{A} and its explicit representation	93
5. On the continuity of ρ and μ	95
6. The validity of common equations for μ and the logical consistency of the theory	97
Chapter B6. Document relationships	103

Chapter B7. Macroscopic experiments and their probability measure	106
1. Empirically accessible events	106
2. The nesting property	108
3. Formal representation of macroscopic experiments	117
4. Certain possible facts and their properties	119
5. Some statements about outcome constellations	122
6. From the outer measure μ to the probability measure for the experiment . .	126
Chapter B8. Measurements on quantum systems	130
1. Quantum experiments: prerequisites and definitions	130
2. Reduction and commutability of experimental results	133
3. The probability measure on the algebra of possible experimental results . .	136
4. Some more definitions	141
5. Calculation of outcome probabilities using quantum states	143
6. The quantum state after measurement	150
<i>References</i>	153

Summary

What is usually called “quantum theory” is, in fact, just a formalism by which the results of certain experiments can be predicted. It is not, however, a theory of physical reality, and that is why there is an “interpretation problem”. Many attempts have been made to solve this problem, but none of these has led to a precisely formulated theory from which the Copenhagen formalism could be derived in a rigorous sense.

In order to solve the interpretation problem, one has to define a physical theory of the universe and its properties such that the Copenhagen quantum formalism can be derived from it. Such a theory consists of a model, a set of axioms (i.e., deterministic laws), and a probability function defined on the algebra of all possible facts as given by the model. Essentially, the model must specify the set \mathcal{E} of all possible events. This can be achieved by defining the set of all real physical quantities and assuming a timeline $T \subset \mathbb{R}$. If L is one of these quantities, if ΔL is a subset of \mathbb{R} and $t \in T$ is a point of time, then the term

“(L \in ΔL) at time t ”

constitutes a possible event.

In the case of quantum theory, a numerical quantity L is represented by a self-adjoint operator on \mathcal{H} , the Hilbert space of the universe. The term “L \in ΔL ” then corresponds to a linear subspace of \mathcal{H} . So, if we define

$$\mathcal{U} := \{ A \mid A \text{ is a linear subspace of } \mathcal{H} \},$$

then each event is described by a pair (A,t) with $A \in \mathcal{U}$ and $t \in T$. Consequently, we have

$$\mathcal{E} = \mathcal{U} \times T \quad (\text{the Cartesian product of } \mathcal{U} \text{ and } T).$$

Now, in quantum theory, there are three deterministic laws or axioms:

- 1) The principle of monotonicity. It states that, for all $t \in T$ and $A, B \in \mathcal{U}$,
if $A \subset B$ and (A,t) is real, then (B,t) is real as well.
- 2) The principle of exclusion. It states that, for all $t \in T$ and $A_1, A_2, \dots \in \mathcal{U}$,
if the A_j are jointly orthogonal, then the (A_j,t) cannot all be real at the same time.
Here “jointly orthogonal” means that the A_j are pairwise commutable (i.e., their projection operators are) and that their intersection is the zero subspace.
- 3) The Schrödinger equation: For all $t \in T$ and $A \in \mathcal{U}$, the event $(A,0)$ is real if and only if $(U_t A,t)$ is real. Here U_t is defined in the usual way by $U_t := e^{-itH/\hbar}$ with the Hamiltonian H .

Since the *real* world ω_0 (i.e., the set of events that really occur) is a subset of \mathcal{E} , we can define the set of *possible* worlds as the power set of \mathcal{E} :

$$\Omega := \wp(\mathcal{E}).$$

For every $E \in \mathcal{E}$, the term

$$\langle E \rangle := \{ \omega \in \Omega \mid E \in \omega \}$$

denotes the possible fact that E is real. Now let \mathcal{A} be the smallest set algebra on Ω which contains all such possible facts $\langle E \rangle$. Then \mathcal{A} represents the algebra of all possible facts as given by the model. Essentially, such a possible fact is a logical combination of events. On \mathcal{A} , common logical operations such as \wedge , \vee , \neg , \forall , etc. can be defined.

Every axiom corresponds to a subset of \mathcal{A} , so their union, denoted by AX , is a subset of \mathcal{A} as well. By

$$\Omega_{AX} := \{ \omega \in \Omega \mid \forall F \in AX \omega \in F \}$$

we define Ω_{AX} to be the set of those possible worlds that obey to all deterministic laws. Furthermore, for all $F \in \mathcal{A}$, let

$$\diamond_{AX}(F) :\Leftrightarrow F \cap \Omega_{AX} \neq \emptyset.$$

The operator \diamond_{AX} , defined on \mathcal{A} , denotes “physical possibility”. On this basis, one can define a function μ on \mathcal{A} such that μ is a continuous extension of \diamond_{AX} . This function denotes “physical improbability” (“improbability” essentially means “gradual impossibility” here). μ is a subadditive and monotonic function on \mathcal{A} , i.e., a so-called “outer measure” in the sense of mathematical measure theory.

From the absolute improbability function μ , we can derive conditional improbabilities by

$$\mu(F \mid G) := \mu(F \wedge G) / \mu(G) \quad (\text{for } F, G \in \mathcal{A})$$

as well as probabilities

$$\nu(F \mid G) := 1 - \mu(\neg F \mid G) \quad (\text{for } F, G \in \mathcal{A}).$$

Furthermore, “expected frequencies” $P(F \mid G)$ can be defined by the so-called “law of large numbers”. If $P(\cdot \mid G)$ is defined on a sub-algebra \mathcal{A}' of \mathcal{A} , then it is a probability measure on \mathcal{A}' in the usual sense. What has been introduced here is a concept of probability which is slightly more general than that of Kolmogorov. This is done for good reason: It allows us to avoid any problems with Bell’s inequality.

The theory is now complete: It consists of a model of reality, deterministic laws, and a law of probability. It is ontologically realistic since every event has a unique truth value, regardless of whether anything has been observed or measured. Moreover, the theory’s logical consistency can be formally proven, so there is no problem with any no-go theorems. As mentioned before, problems with Bell’s inequality are avoided by using a more general concept of probability. The problem of Kochen-Specker’s theorem does not arise, because we do not assume numerical properties to be “value definite”. Such properties are allowed to have, at every point in time, either exactly one value or no value at all. This is not “weird” since numerical properties in everyday life, such as the length of a table, are not value definite either: They have a value only as long as the object in question exists.

Finally, the Copenhagen formalism can be derived from the theory. First, we have to note that a subsystem Q of the universe corresponds to a tensor factor of the Hilbert space \mathcal{H} :

$$\mathcal{H} = \mathcal{H}_Q \otimes \mathcal{H}_{Q^-}.$$

Here Q^- denotes the “rest of the world”. Now the conditional quantum state $W_{Q;t|\mathcal{B}}$ can be defined in a quite plausible way for every subsystem Q , each $t \in T$, and every finite sequence of events \mathcal{B} as a condition. This quantum state is always a statistical operator on \mathcal{H}_Q . If its rank is equal to one, it is called a *pure* state and can be represented by a single wave function $\varphi \in \mathcal{H}_Q$. The quantum state thus defined will never be “ontic”. However, if \mathcal{B} corresponds to the empirical knowledge of a subject, the state can be called “epistemic”, since in this case it describes what the subject knows about the subsystem.

Remark: If $(A,t) \in \mathcal{E}$ is an event, then A is a complete description of its form and thus can be called “ontic”. If the dimension of A is equal to one, A can *also* be represented by a single wave function.

The quantum state defined here behaves just as the Copenhagen formalism describes: The state is prepared by the condition \mathcal{B} , it moves according to the Schrödinger equation as long as the system is undisturbed (in practice this will happen only approximately), and, in the case of an experiment, probabilities of possible results can be calculated by the usual formula. When a measurement is completed and its result is incorporated into \mathcal{B} as an additional condition, the new conditional state is given by the formula described in the Copenhagen formalism.

Conclusions: The theory considered here is precisely defined, starting with the canonical model of quantum theory. Moreover, it is logically consistent and the Copenhagen formalism can be derived from it. Since every concept used in this theory is given a precise definition, there is no interpretation problem regarding quantum systems, quantum states, or measurements. Questions that arise in the interpretation debate, such as: “Are wave functions ontic or epistemic?”, can be clearly answered. Speculative concepts like “many worlds”, “many minds”, “pilot waves”, etc. are avoided, and there are no ambiguities as occur in the so-called “Copenhagen interpretation”. Thus this theory represents a reasonable solution to the interpretation problem of quantum theory.

Note: For better readability, we write Ω , A , $\langle \dots \rangle$, etc. in this summary instead of Ω_0 , A_0 , $\langle \dots \rangle_0$, etc. as defined in the main text.

PART A Realistic Quantum Theory

1. Role and relevance of the interpretation problem

The classical model of the microscopic has failed: the ultraviolet catastrophe has shown that classical field theory cannot apply at the microscopic level. Double-slit experiments show that the concept of classical elementary particles (and thus classical atomism) does not correctly describe reality.

Since a better model could not be formulated, physicists focused on talking only about what could be “measured” in the context of an experiment. This, however, does not lead to a theory of microscopic reality.

Little has changed about that to this day. Even current textbooks do not formulate a model of reality, but deal with the preparation of systems and with measurements or observations that can be made on them. We have a theory “with subjects” and without a model, rather than an objective theory of reality, a theory of the real properties of (quantum) objects, i.e., a theory *with* a model and “without subjects”.

Quantum theory, as it is commonly taught, is in fact just a formalism that allows making predictions in certain situations. It should be called the “Copenhagen quantum formalism”.

This formalism essentially states that quantum systems with a specific state can be prepared by some experimental apparatus. If the system is not disturbed, this state develops according to Schrödinger’s equation. In the case of a measurement, it can be used to calculate the probabilities of possible measurement results. After the measurement, the system is described by a new state, depending on the result obtained.

Just as the ancient Greeks were able to predict a solar eclipse even though they did not have an accurate theory of celestial mechanics, so too with the quantum formalism: it allows predictions to be made, but it does not constitute a physical theory in the true sense. In fact, when it comes to formulating a truly physical theory of the microscopic, the Copenhagen quantum formalism is nothing more than a provisional approach.

In the past, some physicists have rightfully claimed that “physics should be about nature, not human action”. As a theory, the Copenhagen quantum formalism must therefore be regarded as *unphysical*.

A reasonable physical theory has to begin with a model of reality. In particular, that model must include a description of the macroscopic. Within the framework of this model, deterministic laws (such as the classical deterministic law of motion) and probabilistic laws – as far as they exist – must be specified. Such a theory must be formulated in an ontologically realistic way, i.e., without referring to subjective terms such as “observable” (instead of property), “observation”, or “measurement”. Moreover, it has to be logically sound; in particular, it must

not entail any contradictions, such as those that arise from the well-known no-go theorems. There is no “measurement problem” in such a theory from the outset. If the theory is formulated in a precise way, there will be no ambiguity about the role of quantum states or wave functions either.

The lack of a reasonable physical theory of the microscopic has consequences not only for physics. Physics is the basis of all natural sciences, and within physics, the theory of the microscopic again forms the basis. Therefore, as long as we do not succeed in formulating a real quantum *theory*, we cannot have a consistent scientific worldview as well. Instead, absurd pseudo-philosophical speculations are running wild.

No one can (or could) be satisfied with this situation. That is why a debate on the interpretation of quantum theory has developed, aiming to solve the problem. This has led to a multitude of attempts to find a reasonable interpretation of the quantum formalism. However, none of these attempts has been truly successful in the sense that it has led to an ontologically realistic, logically consistent, and precisely formulated physical theory. The interpretation variant known as “shut up and calculate” is, of course, not a solution, but merely a capitulation to the problem.

2. How can the interpretation problem be solved?

A solution to the interpretation problem is found when an ontologically realistic, logically sound, and precisely defined theory has been formulated from which the Copenhagen quantum formalism can be derived. This raises the question of what exactly such a physical theory is. Such a theory begins with the specification of a model of reality. But what actually is a model?

First, the objects of everyday life and their properties have to be modeled. Since each such object is part of the universe, every property of the object is, in a canonical way, a property of the universe as well. It is therefore sufficient to consider only properties that relate to the universe as a whole. The model of reality can thus be given by specifying the properties of the universe. By this, all properties of microscopic objects are modeled at the same time.

But what do we mean by a property? There are basically two types of properties: numerical and factual properties. While numerical properties have a real value, factual properties have a truth value. Factual properties can also be referred to as “binary” or “logical” properties or as “predicates”. While “length” or “location” are numerical properties, “red”, for example, is a factual property.

Now, there is a peculiarity about numerical properties: such a property can be either “value-definite” (i.e., it always has a value) or not. An example of a non-value-definite numerical property is the length of a table. This property only has a value as long as the table actually exists. This distinction is important for quantum theory, as apparently there is a problem with the assumption of general value definiteness in this theory (uncertainty principle, Kochen-Specker no-go theorem).

In order to deal with this problem, it is necessary to understand how numerical properties, whether value-definite or not, can be reduced to factual properties. If L is a numerical property and ΔL is an interval of real numbers (or any other subset of \mathbb{R}), then “ $L \in \Delta L$ ” denotes a factual property that is either given or not. If *none* of these factual properties are given, then the numerical property L simply has no value at all.

Reality is therefore modeled by specifying the factual properties of the universe. A numerical property L is then considered to be a parameterized set of factual properties. The parameter range could be, for example, the set of all real intervals ΔL . However, it makes more sense to use the set of all measurable subsets $M \subset \mathbb{R}$ instead.

So, in general, a numerical property L is nothing more than the set of all factual properties of the form “ $L \in M$ ”, where M is any measurable subset of \mathbb{R} . Such a numerical property has a specific value λ if and only if the associated factual property “ $L \in \{\lambda\}$ ” has the truth value “true”. If none of these particular factual properties has the truth value “true”, then the quantity L has no value at all.

3. Modeling reality in quantum theory

According to what has been said, we now have to model the set of factual properties of the universe. In the Hilbert space model of quantum theory, each factual property is represented by a (closed) linear subspace of the Hilbert space of the universe. This is the only plausible possibility and can be justified in many ways.

As an example, let us consider a table standing in front of us at time t . This fact can be observed. Accordingly, there is an observable L that has exactly two possible values (e.g., 1 and 0), the first value corresponding to the presence of the table. Obviously, L is a projection operator. The image A of this operator (i.e., the eigenspace corresponding to the eigenvalue 1) then describes the presence of the table, or more precisely, the presence of a table with the shape specified by A .

Thus, the event that consists of a table with the shape described by A being present at time t is modeled by the pair (A, t) . In this manner, all macroscopic events can be modeled. However, microscopic events, such as the presence of an electron with a certain spin property in a given area in space, can also be modeled in this way.

Conversely, it is reasonable to assume that *every* subspace of the Hilbert space corresponds to a real property of the universe. For example, it does not make sense to select a specific spin direction and consider only the subspace corresponding to it as a real property. In principle (though not in practice), *each* subspace describes a property that can be measured. However, this does not mean that it must be possible to measure all or even very many different such properties *at the same time*.

To put it formally, let

- \mathcal{H} be the Hilbert space of the universe,
- \mathcal{U} the set of (closed) linear subspaces of \mathcal{H} ,
- T the time axis, as a subset of \mathbb{R} ,
- \mathcal{E} the Cartesian product of \mathcal{U} and T .

Reality in quantum theory is now modeled by identifying the set of factual properties of the universe with \mathcal{U} . By this, all numerical properties of the universe, as well as the properties of every subsystem, are specified at the same time.

Note: If A is an element of \mathcal{U} and the universe has the property modeled by A at time t , we can briefly say: The universe “has property A at time t ”.

The set \mathcal{E} (as the set of all pairs (A,t) with $A \in \mathcal{U}$ and $t \in T$) represents the set of *possible events* in the model given above. The assumption of ontological realism now states that each element of \mathcal{E} is objectively assigned exactly one truth value. It can be easily shown that the model of reality specified in this way does not lead to a contradiction with regard to the well-known no-go theorems, i.e., Bell’s inequality and the Kochen-Specker theorem (see T.5.6, p. 102).

The modeling of objective microscopic reality (i.e., the “quantum world”) is thus complete. Now, the deterministic and probabilistic laws of the theory must be formulated. These are laws about the possible events in the universe, i.e., lawful relationships between the elements of the set \mathcal{E} .

Note: In quantum theory, a numerical property is represented by a self-adjoint operator L . For every (Borel) measurable subset M of \mathbb{R} , we can form the indicator function 1_M . By applying this function to L , we obtain the operator $1_M(L)$. This is a projection operator that projects onto a subspace of the Hilbert space. The resulting subspace corresponds to the factual property “ $L \in M$ ”. In this way, a self-adjoint operator represents a parameterized set of subspaces, where the parameter range is the set of all measurable subsets of \mathbb{R} . The subspaces that occur in this context are pairwise commutable. Two subspaces are considered commutable here if the associated projection operators commute.

4. The model of quantum theory and the classical approximation

At this point, we want to show how macroscopic properties of the universe can be modeled. To do this, we consider wave functions. A univariate wave function is a mapping from \mathbb{R} to the complex plane. If we identify the domain \mathbb{R} with the x -axis and represent the complex plane by the y - z -plane, we can simply imagine a wave function as a thread in space.

Such a wave function φ has values that are different from zero in a certain region on the x -axis. This results in a localized distribution on the x -axis, similar to a mass distribution. Thus, φ describes a mean location $E_\varphi(X)$ on the one hand and a standard deviation $\Delta_\varphi(X)$ on the other. In addition, φ rotates with a certain velocity around the x -axis at each point x . This

results in a distribution on momentum space and, consequently, a mean momentum $E_\varphi(P)$ as well as a standard deviation of the momentum $\Delta_\varphi(P)$.

A one-dimensional classical particle is described by a pair (x,p) , where x indicates the position and p indicates the momentum. If we now consider a wave function φ for which the following applies:

$$E_\varphi(X) \approx x \quad \text{and} \quad \Delta_\varphi(X) \approx 0 \quad \text{as well as}$$

$$E_\varphi(P) \approx p \quad \text{and} \quad \Delta_\varphi(P) \approx 0$$

we can approximate the state of the classical particle by this wave function.

Here, due to the uncertainty principle, we always have:

$$\Delta_\varphi(X) \cdot \Delta_\varphi(P) \geq \hbar/2$$

Therefore, we cannot demand that

$$\Delta_\varphi(X) = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \Delta_\varphi(P) = 0$$

are true at the same time. However, for an optimal approximation of a classical particle state, the following should apply:

$$\Delta_\varphi(X) \cdot \Delta_\varphi(P) \approx \hbar/2$$

This means that φ comes as close as possible to the uncertainty relation.

In order to model macroscopic properties, we now consider wave functions which are restricted to a very small subinterval of the x -axis (and have a value of zero outside of it) and rotate with uniform velocity around the x -axis. Such wave functions have the shape of a spiral spring. In addition to a distribution in space, they specify a distribution of momentum that is centered at a certain value p . In this way, they approximate a classical particle state, even though they do not satisfy the condition $\Delta_\varphi(X) \cdot \Delta_\varphi(P) \approx \hbar/2$ for an *optimal* approximation.

Within the set of all such spiral-shaped wave functions, we can select an orthonormal basis. To do this, we divide the x -axis into small disjoint intervals of length Δx and consider only those functions that are concentrated on one of these subintervals and perform an integer number of rotations on this interval. These special functions form an orthonormal basis of the Hilbert space of all univariate wave functions on the x -axis. Each point (x,p) of the phase space of a one-dimensional classical particle can be approximated by an element of this orthonormal basis.

We now consider a three-dimensional classical particle, which is described by three position and three momentum coordinates. We can approximate the state of such a particle by a wave function as well. To do this, we select (from the orthonormal basis just described) three wave functions φ_x , φ_y , and φ_z which approximate the position and momentum in the x , y , and z directions, respectively. We then define the trivariate wave function φ by

$$\varphi(x,y,z) := \varphi_x(x) \cdot \varphi_y(y) \cdot \varphi_z(z)$$

This function approximates the classical state of the three-dimensional particle. The set of all functions defined in this way again forms an orthonormal basis, namely in the Hilbert space of all trivariate wave functions.

In a similar way, we can define (again by forming products) an orthonormal basis \mathcal{B} in the Hilbert space of all $3N$ -variate wave functions. Then, for each point z in the phase space Z of a classical N -particle system, there is an element ϕ of this orthonormal basis \mathcal{B} that approximates point z . This gives us a mapping α from Z to \mathcal{B} such that every $z \in Z$ is approximated by $\alpha(z) \in \mathcal{B}$.

We now assume (for simplicity) that the universe can be described classically as an N -particle system. The existence of a macroscopic object of a certain shape then corresponds to a subset A of the phase space Z of this universe. (We are not dealing with a *point* in phase space here because we describe the object only macroscopically and do not specify exactly where each particle is located and what momentum it has.) If we apply the mapping α to A , we obtain a subset

$$A' := \alpha(A)$$

of the orthonormal basis \mathcal{B} of the Hilbert space \mathcal{H} of the universe. The set A' (of basis vectors) constitutes an approximation to the set A (of classical states).

Now, let A'' be the linear closure of A' , i.e., the set of all linear combinations of elements of A' . Then A'' is a subspace of \mathcal{H} . In this way, the fact that an object of a certain shape exists in the universe at time t is represented by a pair (A'', t) , where A'' is a subspace of the Hilbert space of the universe and t is a point in time.

These considerations not only show that macroscopic properties of the universe can be modeled by subspaces of the Hilbert space, but also describe by *which* subspace this can be done in each particular case. Moreover, they show that macroscopic properties can be modeled by subspaces that are pairwise commutable. The latter results from the fact that the modeling takes place within one and the same orthonormal basis of the Hilbert space.

Note: Instead of the wave functions considered so far, we can also use functions that have the form of a spiral in momentum representation rather than position representation. Using these wave functions, an orthonormal basis \mathcal{B} can again be formed in the way described. For everyday macroscopic objects, this even provides a much better approximation, especially with regard to their macroscopic momentum properties.

Note: We started from modeling a certain property by points in classical phase space and then approximated these points by wave functions. However, this does not mean that classical particles really exist. Rather, one has to look at it the other way around: In fact, subspaces correspond to real properties of the universe, and the corresponding subsets of phase space constitute an approximation to this reality. Thus, by assuming classical particles, we obtain an approximation to the actual situation. This approximation may be helpful in many cases. However, it fails under conditions where we are dealing with typical “quantum effects”.

5. Deterministic laws of quantum theory

The deterministic laws of quantum theory are divided into two parts: The first part is about relationships between different properties the universe has at a certain point in time. The second part is about relationships over space and time.

The first part includes two laws, the monotonicity principle and the exclusion principle. The monotonicity principle states: If subspace A is contained in subspace B and the universe has property A at time t , then it also has property B at the same time. The exclusion principle states: If properties A_j are jointly orthogonal, then the universe cannot have all A_j at the same time.

Here, a finite or infinite sequence A_j of properties is called “jointly orthogonal” if the A_j are pairwise commutable and their intersection is the zero subspace. A sequence of exactly two elements A and B is “jointly orthogonal” if and only if A and B are orthogonal in the normal sense, i.e., if $A \perp B$. The exclusion principle thus is a generalization of the statement that the universe cannot have properties A and B at the same time if A and B are orthogonal to each other.

Note: The exclusion principle implies that every numerical quantity L can have at most one value (see T.1.2, p. 58). This means that L either has exactly one value or no value at all. The exclusion principle in its general form corresponds to the following statement: If M_j is a sequence of measurable subsets of \mathbb{R} and the intersection of the M_j is empty, then the universe cannot have all the factual properties “ $L \in M_j$ ” at the same time.

At this point, a third principle could be formulated: the negation principle. It states that at any given time and for any subspace A , the universe always has either property A or property A^\perp . Here, A^\perp denotes the orthogonal complement of A .

The negation principle can also be referred to as the “physical tertium non datur”. It must not be confused with the logical “tertium non datur”, which states that the universe always either has property A or does not have it. The latter refers to only one subspace A , while the physical “tertium non datur” relates the two subspaces A and A^\perp to each other.

However, the assumption of the physical “tertium non datur” is not possible in quantum theory. If this principle were accepted as an additional deterministic law, one could deduce from it that every discrete numerical quantity always has exactly one value. According to the Kochen-Specker no-go theorem, this leads to a logical contradiction. This contradiction can only be avoided by abandoning the assumption of the physical “tertium non datur” as a general law (see T.1.1, p. 57, and T.1.3, p. 60).

Note: The solution to the problems associated with the Kochen-Specker no-go theorem is achieved here in two steps: Firstly, as the real properties of the universe, we do not start from numerical quantities but from factual properties. Numerical realism, which is common in

classical physics, is thus replaced by the more general factual realism. Secondly, the assumption of the physical “tertium non datur” is abandoned. At the same time, the assumption of general value definiteness of numerical quantities is given up. It can be formally proven that the theory formulated in this way is logically consistent. For this reason, there can be no further no-go theorem as far as the deterministic laws of the theory are concerned (see T.1.1, p. 57).

One may wonder whether abandoning the physical “tertium non datur” does not result in a theory that is too weak. To show that this is not the case, it is ultimately sufficient to prove that the Copenhagen quantum formalism can be derived from this “weak” theory, and this will turn out to be true.

Another argument about this is as follows: All of the above considerations can also be applied, in an analogous way, to classical mechanics. To do this, one simply has to define the set \mathcal{U} differently, namely as the set of measurable subsets of classical phase space. Then projection operators must be replaced by indicator functions, the zero subspace by the empty set, and orthogonal complements by set complements.

In the case of classical mechanics, the physical “tertium non datur” can be accepted without contradiction as a deterministic law. By this we obtain general value definiteness of all numerical quantities and thus the completely normal classical theory. However, if we omit the physical “tertium non datur”, we end up with a (logically) weaker theory. It can be shown, though, that the empirical content of this “weak” theory is identical to that of the original “strong” theory (see T.2.3, p. 70). This shows that a theory without the physical “tertium non datur” can be sufficient as far as its empirical content is concerned (defined in the sense of Karl Popper as the set of all possible empirical materials by which the theory is disproved). So, if one wants to formulate a theory with sufficient empirical content, one does not necessarily have to assume the physical “tertium non datur”.

In order to solve the interpretation problem, it is necessary to formulate a theory that has (at least) the same empirical content as the Copenhagen quantum formalism. According to what has been said, this can be achieved even without assuming the physical “tertium non datur” and thus without the assumption of general value definiteness of numerical quantities.

With the two deterministic laws mentioned above, the monotonicity principle and the exclusion principle, all relationships between different properties the universe can have at a given time have already been specified. We will now discuss the relationships over space and time.

In quantum mechanics, there is only one such relationship: the law of motion, which takes the form of the Schrödinger equation. Starting from the Hamiltonian H on the Hilbert space of the universe, we define, for every point in time t , the unitary operator

$$U_t := e^{-itH/\hbar}$$

in the usual way. The law of motion now states: The universe has property A at time 0 if and only if it has property $U_t A$ at time t . For simplicity, we assume that 0 is an element of the time axis.

The law of motion specified here is deterministic and reversible, just like the law of motion in classical mechanics. In general, it only applies to the universe as a whole. One could claim that such a law should also apply to every closed system, but in the real universe, no proper subsystem will ever be entirely closed. However, the following can be derived from the law of motion of the universe: If conditions are given under which the retroactive effect of a subsystem on its environment is so small that the effect of the environment on the subsystem is not significantly changed, the motion of the subsystem can be approximately described by its own Schrödinger equation (see T.3.1, p. 77).

In quantum field theory, a field law (as a relationship over space and time) can be specified in an analogous manner. In this case, too, we obtain a deterministic and reversible law of motion over time in every space-time coordinate system.

Note: The Hilbert space of quantum field theory can be based on wave functions that are defined on space-time rather than on space alone. In this case, time is no longer a classical parameter. An event is then modeled by a subspace of the Hilbert space only, and the law of motion takes a somewhat different form.

With the monotonicity principle, the exclusion principle, and the deterministic law of motion (or field law), the definition of deterministic laws is complete. All that is missing now is the probabilistic law. In order to define this law in a precise way, we must first introduce the algebra of possible facts in the given physical model.

6. The algebra of possible facts in the model of quantum theory

The probabilistic law of a physical theory is specified by a function that assigns to each possible physical fact a certain value as its probability. The set of possible facts can be precisely defined on the basis of a given physical model of the universe. This formal definition is necessary in order to accurately specify the domain on which probability is defined. Without clarity on this, it is not possible, for example, to truly understand the role of Bell's inequality or to reasonably solve the problem associated with it.

First, let ω_0 be the set of all events that actually occur. Then ω_0 is a subset of \mathcal{E} and represents the “true world”. Now, every other possible world ω is a subset of \mathcal{E} as well. Consequently, the set Ω_0 of all possible worlds as given by the model is the power set of \mathcal{E} , and ω_0 is an element of it.

For every possible event $(A,t) \in \mathcal{E}$, we denote by $\langle A,t \rangle_0$ the set of those possible worlds in which (A,t) occurs:

$$\langle A,t \rangle_0 := \{ \omega \in \Omega_0 \mid (A,t) \in \omega \}$$

This expression stands for the possible fact that the possible event (A,t) actually occurs. It denotes a subset of Ω_0 .

We now form the set of all such expressions

$$\mathcal{R}_0 := \{ \langle A, t \rangle_0 \mid (A, t) \in \mathcal{E} \}$$

and define

$$\mathcal{A}_0 := \mathcal{A}(\mathcal{R}_0)$$

to be the σ -algebra generated by \mathcal{R}_0 on Ω_0 , i.e., the smallest σ -algebra on Ω_0 that contains all possible facts of the form $\langle A, t \rangle_0$.

\mathcal{A}_0 is the algebra of possible physical facts in the given model. Basically, a possible fact is just a logical combination of events. Logical operations can be performed on \mathcal{A}_0 . For example, we can define the following for any possible facts F, G , and $F_j \in \mathcal{A}_0$:

$$F \wedge G := F \cap G$$

$$F \vee G := F \cup G$$

$$\neg F := \Omega_0 \setminus F$$

$$\forall_j F_j := \bigcap_j F_j$$

etc.

Within the set Ω_0 , one can distinguish those elements that comply with the deterministic laws. For example, $\omega \in \Omega_0$ satisfies the monotonicity principle if the following applies to all subspaces A and B with $A < B$ and for all points in time t :

$$(A, t) \in \omega \Rightarrow (B, t) \in \omega$$

Now, let Ω be the set of all elements of Ω_0 that satisfy the monotonicity principle, the exclusion principle, and the law of motion. Then Ω is the set of all *physically* possible worlds. Also on this set, possible facts can be modeled. To do this, let

$$\langle A, t \rangle := \langle A, t \rangle_0 \cap \Omega \quad (\text{for every event } (A, t))$$

and let

$$\mathcal{A} := \{ F \cap \Omega \mid F \in \mathcal{A}_0 \}$$

be the induced algebra of \mathcal{A}_0 on Ω . It follows that \mathcal{A} is the smallest σ -algebra on Ω which contains all expressions of the form $\langle A, t \rangle$.

\mathcal{A} can also be interpreted as the algebra of possible physical facts. However, since \mathcal{A} is defined on the set Ω of those possible worlds that comply with the deterministic laws, possible facts are distinguished here from one another only if they are not equivalent with respect to these laws. Each element of \mathcal{A} thus corresponds to an equivalence class of elements of \mathcal{A}_0 , i.e., of possible facts in the given model. Logical operations such as $\wedge, \vee, \neg, \forall$, etc. can be defined on \mathcal{A} as well.

The reason for introducing the algebra \mathcal{A} is as follows: If a probability function is defined on \mathcal{A} , it specifies a probability for each element of \mathcal{A}_0 as well. At the same time, however, it is ensured that the probability function is compatible with the deterministic laws. In particular, possible facts always have the same probability if they are equivalent with respect to the

deterministic laws, and they have zero probability if they are physically impossible according to these laws.

In the following, we will start from \mathcal{A} as the algebra of possible facts and define the concept of probability on it.

7. The problem of Bell's inequality

In order to introduce the probabilistic law of quantum theory, one could try to define a suitable probability measure P on the algebra \mathcal{A} , i.e., a function from \mathcal{A} to the interval $[0,1]$ that is additive and normalized to one. We would expect this probability measure to satisfy certain equations, such as

$$P(\langle A,t \rangle | \langle B,t \rangle) = \text{tr } \pi_A \pi_B / \text{tr } \pi_B$$

where A and B are subspaces of \mathcal{H} , t is a point in time, tr denotes the trace operator, and π_A and π_B are the projection operators associated with A and B , respectively.

However, it turns out that this is impossible. In particular, the above equation contradicts Bell's inequality, which can be derived from the additivity of the probability measure P (see Chapter B4, Section 1, equation (**), on p. 78).

More generally, it can be shown that the following three statements are logically inconsistent:

- (1) Every subspace of the Hilbert space is assigned a truth value at every point in time, such that the monotonicity and exclusion principles apply (realism).
- (2) P is a Kolmogorov probability measure on the algebra \mathcal{A} of all possible facts in the model of quantum theory (Kolmogorov's probability theory).
- (3) At a given time t , the probability of the possible fact $\langle A,t \rangle$ can be calculated for each subspace A using the formula

$$P(\langle A,t \rangle) = |\pi_A \varphi|^2$$

where φ is an element of the Hilbert space.

This inconsistency is based on the fact that Bell's inequality can be derived for every Kolmogorov probability measure and that the formula given in statement (3) is not compatible with this inequality (see Chapter B4, Section 2, pp. 81-82).

Statement (3) is based on experimental results and has been repeatedly confirmed. Thus, there is a contradiction between the assumption of realism, Kolmogorov's probability theory, and empirical findings. This is sometimes seen as proof that objective reality (or at least local reality) does not exist.

However, we cannot give up ontological realism if we want to solve the interpretation problem. Rather, the only reasonable conclusion from the contradiction described is that Kolmogorov's concept of probability does not fit empirical realities. We must therefore address the question of whether the axioms of Kolmogorov's theory are valid for the concept of probability *in general* or whether they represent just a special case.

8. Kolmogorov's concept of probability

The basic requirement of Kolmogorov's probability theory is the additivity of the function P . But why should probability be additive? There is only one reason for this: the identification of probability with a limit of relative frequencies. Since absolute frequencies behave in an additive way, this also applies to relative frequencies and, consequently, to their limit when an experiment is repeated an infinite number of times.

However, there is no reason to identify probability with frequency from the outset. This is merely a traditional idea from the time when it was still believed that probability could be defined as a limit of relative frequencies. Such a definition (by the weak law of large numbers) is impossible, though, since the concept of probability is already needed in order to even *form* this limit of relative frequencies (relative frequencies only converge "with probability"). It was only the failure of such a definition that led to Kolmogorov's axiomatic introduction of the concept of probability.

When specifying the axioms of his probability theory, however, Kolmogorov did not base them on the properties of the concept of probability itself, but on the basic property of relative frequencies, namely additivity. Implicitly, this meant that the identification of probability and frequency was retained, and as a consequence of the axiomatically assumed additivity, this identity can then be proven as a theorem.

So it seems that additivity is a property that must apply to probability in any case. Since Kolmogorov's concept of probability has proven itself in practice within certain contexts, particularly when considering individual experiments, there seems to be no need to doubt the additivity of probability. Only the failure of this concept when applied to the algebra of possible facts in quantum theory shows that additivity cannot be simply assumed for probability in general. Rather, it must be accepted that the requirement of additivity and thus the general identification of probability with frequency has been empirically refuted by the results of quantum experiments.

Note: There is a problem with the application of Kolmogorov's concept of probability in classical mechanics too. It is reasonable to assume that all paths in classical phase space are equally probable. Since each path is determined by its starting point, this can be described by the Lebesgue measure on phase space. However, this measure is not a probability measure in Kolmogorov's sense because it cannot be normalized to one. Here, too, we find that Kolmogorov's concept of probability cannot be readily applied in physics.

The assumption of an additive and normalized measure on the algebra of possible facts is based on the usual, i.e., Kolmogorov's probability theory. However, this theory is normally applied only to the algebra of possible outcomes of individual experiments, and it is only in this context that it has proven itself in practice. Whether we can assume such a measure on the algebra of all possible facts in the model of quantum theory is quite a different matter. Therefore, we must first consider the question of what is to be understood by probability *in general*, and we shall see that Kolmogorov's theory is only a special case of a probability theory.

9. The general concept of probability

In general, probability and improbability are gradual modal operators on the algebra \mathcal{A} of all possible facts. They are close analogues to the two (non-gradual) operators of necessity and impossibility. While probability is to be understood as approximate necessity, improbability means approximate impossibility. For example, if a possible fact $A \in \mathcal{A}$ is extremely probable, we consider it to be almost necessary. If it is extremely improbable, it is almost impossible.

The operators of probability and improbability (as gradual modal operators) are represented by functions

$$v : \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \quad (\text{probability, in the sense of gradual necessity})$$

and

$$\mu : \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \quad (\text{improbability, in the sense of gradual (im-) possibility})$$

For all $A \in \mathcal{A}$, $\mu(A)$ should always be greater than or equal to zero, where $\mu(A) \approx 0$ means that A is highly unlikely. Similarly, $v(A)$ should always be less than or equal to one, where $v(A) \approx 1$ means that A is very likely.

As is well known, the following relationship exists between the necessity operator \square and the possibility operator \diamond :

$$\square(A) \Leftrightarrow \neg \diamond(\neg A) \quad (\text{for all } A \in \mathcal{A})$$

It states that A is necessary if and only if the negation $\neg A$ is impossible. By analogy, we obtain a simple relationship between μ and v :

$$v(A) = 1 - \mu(\neg A) \quad (\text{for all } A \in \mathcal{A})$$

It states that A is probable if its negation $\neg A$ is improbable. Since the operator v can be derived from the operator μ by this equation, we can limit ourselves in the following to the question of which properties the operator μ should have. In order to find these properties, we can start from the properties that characterize the concept of possibility.

Note: When applying the concept of probability, the focus will in general be on the concept of improbability, not probability. For example, in a statistical test procedure, it is important that the type I error be highly improbable. It therefore makes sense to introduce the operator μ of improbability with its characteristic properties as a basic concept and then to derive the concept of probability from it by means of a definition (and not the other way around). Besides that, the properties of the operator μ have a simpler and more easily understandable form than those of v .

For the possibility operator \diamond , the following relationships exist (for all $A, B \in \mathcal{A}$):

$$A \subset B \Rightarrow (\diamond(A) \Rightarrow \diamond(B))$$

$$\neg \diamond(A) \wedge \neg \diamond(B) \Rightarrow \neg \diamond(A \vee B)$$

From this, we obtain the characteristic properties of the operator μ :

$$A \subset B \Rightarrow \mu(A) \leq \mu(B) \quad (\text{monotonicity})$$

$$\mu(A \vee B) \leq \mu(A) + \mu(B) \quad (\text{subadditivity})$$

It is reasonable to require subadditivity not only for two, but for any finite or infinite sequence of possible facts. Besides this, we should always have $\mu(A) \geq 0$ as well as $\mu(\emptyset) = 0$. This lets μ be a so-called “outer measure” in the sense of measure theory, i.e., a monotonic and σ -sub-additive mapping from \mathcal{A} to $[0, \infty]$.

In the general case, the concept of (im-) probability can thus be described by an outer measure μ on the algebra \mathcal{A} of possible facts. This measure indicates, for each possible fact A , the degree of improbability by $\mu(A)$. Here, $\mu(A) \approx 0$ means that A is very improbable. Starting from μ , the concept of probability is defined by

$$v(A) := 1 - \mu(\neg A) \quad (\text{for all } A \in \mathcal{A})$$

If $v(A) \approx 1$, then A is very probable. In addition, for all $A, B \in \mathcal{A}$ with $0 < \mu(B) < \infty$, we can define:

$$\mu(A | B) := \mu(A \wedge B) / \mu(B) \quad (\text{conditional improbability})$$

$$v(A | B) := 1 - \mu(\neg A | B) \quad (\text{conditional probability})$$

While in general we do not need to require the function μ (i.e., the absolute improbability) to be normalized to one, conditional improbabilities will always be normalized and, like conditional probabilities, will always lie in the interval $[0, 1]$. As a rule, for practical applications only these conditional (im-) probabilities are relevant.

The concept of independence can also be defined on the basis of the outer measure μ . In this sense, the possible facts A and B are independent if the following applies:

$$\mu(A \wedge B) = \mu(A) \cdot \mu(B)$$

From the outer measure μ (the measure of improbability), we can derive another concept, that of the *degree of frequency*, which will be denoted by P . The degree of frequency is defined (based on μ) by the weak law of large numbers:

$$P(A) = p \iff \forall \delta > 0 \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mu(\#A_j/n \notin [p-\delta, p+\delta]) = 0 \quad (\text{for } A \in \mathcal{A})$$

Here, the expression $\#A_j/n$ denotes the relative frequency of occurrences of the possible fact A in n independent repetitions. Conditional degrees of frequency can be defined in an analogous manner.

In general, the degree of frequency P cannot be defined on the entire algebra \mathcal{A} . However, if P is defined on all elements of a subalgebra \mathcal{A}_e of \mathcal{A} , then P is additive and normalized on this subalgebra (as are the relative frequencies on which P is based) and thus forms a Kolmogorov probability measure on \mathcal{A}_e .

The function v can be referred to as a (generalized) “probability measure”, μ as an “improbability measure”, and P as a “frequency measure”. Such a frequency measure describes relative frequencies of possible experimental results to be expected when experiments are repeated. Thus, it can also be referred to as “expected frequency”.

The concept of probability described here is a generalization of Kolmogorov’s theory, since every Kolmogorov probability measure is a special case of an outer measure.

The difference between Kolmogorov's theory and the more general theory presented here is that Kolmogorov's concept does not distinguish between probability, improbability, and expected frequency. Instead, all these terms are represented by the same function P , i.e., the following equation is assumed to hold:

$$\mu = \nu = P$$

We will refer to this equation as *Kolmogorov's hypothesis*. Kolmogorov's theory thus represents the special case of probability theory in which it is assumed that probabilities and expected frequencies can be identified with each other. In so far, Kolmogorov's theory is actually a theory of frequencies.

Note: The empirical content of a deterministic theory lies in the fact that the theory can be refuted by empirical findings. For such a refutation, one must observe an empirical material that is impossible according to the theory. The same applies to a probabilistic theory. It is refuted when some empirical material is observed that is extremely unlikely according to this theory. The refutation of a probabilistic theory can only be realized to a certain degree. This applies regardless of whether we base our argument on the general concept of probability introduced here or on Kolmogorov's more special concept.

– Remark –

Within the framework of Kolmogorov's concept of probability, a value of $p \in [0,1]$ for the probability of a specific experimental result is understood to mean that on average $N \cdot p$ "hits" will be found in N independent repetitions of the experiment. This is regarded as the defining property of probability.

For probabilities in the order of magnitude of $p = 1/6$ or even $p = 10^{-6}$, there is at first glance nothing wrong with this view. In many physically relevant cases, however, we are dealing with much smaller probabilities. For example, the probability that a glass of lukewarm water will spontaneously divide into an upper layer of hot water and a lower layer of cold water is certainly much smaller than 10^{-100} .

With such a small probability, the experiment would have to be repeated more than 10^{100} times in order to find a number of hits that is not simply always zero. In the real (finite) universe, however, it is not possible to repeat an experiment 10^{100} times. Therefore, in such a case it makes no sense to base the value of a probability on a relative frequency.

The identification of probability and frequency, which underlies Kolmogorov's theory, proves to be of little use here, quite independently of the problem of Bell's inequality in quantum theory.

10. The concept of probability in physics

Kolmogorov's hypothesis, if related to the concept of probability on the algebra \mathcal{A} of all possible facts in the model of quantum theory, has to be regarded as empirically refuted. This

follows from the fact that it implies additivity of probability and, by this, Bell’s inequality, which we have seen to contradict empirical reality.

The situation is very much the same here as in the case of general relativity: although Euclidean geometry (as the geometry of real physical space, not as a purely mathematical theory) has been regarded as true for centuries, it nevertheless contradicts empirical facts. Real space turns out to be non-Euclidean, which means that the parallel axiom does not hold in it: there is not, for every “straight” (i.e., geodesic) line and for every point in space, a parallel through this point.

Similarly, the assumption of probability to be additive (which is based on the identification of probability with frequency) proves untenable in view of empirical reality. Just as Euclidean geometry had to be replaced by a more general geometry because it does not fit reality, so too Kolmogorov’s probability theory must be reasonably replaced by a more general theory of probability.

It is not reasonable, however, to adhere to Kolmogorov’s hypothesis, which is neither particularly plausible a priori nor fits reality, and to draw such bizarre conclusions from it as, for example, that there is no objective reality at all and that the universe is merely “information” (whatever that is supposed to mean).

It thus becomes apparent that the problem of Bell’s inequality has nothing to do with any “weirdness” of quantum theory. Rather, it is about probability theory, in particular about the fact that an inappropriate concept of probability is being used.

According to what has been said above, the probabilistic law of a physical theory can be defined by specifying an outer measure μ on the algebra \mathcal{A} of possible facts. In the case of classical physics, this law is specified by the Lebesgue measure on phase space. We will discuss the definition of a suitable outer measure for the case of quantum theory in the following section.

11. The probabilistic law of quantum theory

In order to define the outer measure on the algebra \mathcal{A} of possible facts in the model of quantum theory, we start from the following continuity principle: If $(A_1, t_1), \dots, (A_n, t_n)$ is a sequence of possible events, then the possible fact $\langle A_1, t_1 \rangle \wedge \dots \wedge \langle A_n, t_n \rangle$ will be very unlikely if there are properties B_1, \dots, B_n of the universe such that, on the one hand, $B_j \approx A_j$ (for all j) and, on the other hand, the possible fact $\langle B_1, t_1 \rangle \wedge \dots \wedge \langle B_n, t_n \rangle$ is physically impossible due to the deterministic laws of the theory.

An outer measure on \mathcal{A} that complies with this principle can be constructed as follows: For every operator L on the Hilbert space \mathcal{H} , by

$$|L| := (\text{tr } LL^*)^{1/2}$$

we define its (Euclidean) norm. Then, for any subspaces A and B of \mathcal{H} , let

$$\delta(A,B) := | \pi_{B^\perp} \pi_A |$$

Here, a small value of $\delta(A,B)$ means that A is approximately a subspace of B .

Now we define a function ρ that satisfies the following equation for every sequence A_1, \dots, A_n of properties (see D.5.9 and T.5.1, p. 93):

$$\rho(\forall_j \langle A_j, 0 \rangle) = \inf \{ \sum_j \delta(A_j, D_j) \mid D_1, \dots, D_n \subset \mathcal{H} \text{ and } \text{the } D_j \text{ are jointly orthogonal} \}$$

Here, the expression $\forall_j \langle A_j, 0 \rangle$ stands for the possible fact that all properties A_j are given at time 0. The measure of improbability μ is now defined as the maximum outer measure on \mathcal{A} for which the following applies (see D.5.12, p. 94):

$$\mu(\forall_j \langle A_j, 0 \rangle) \leq \rho(\forall_j \langle A_j, 0 \rangle)^2 \quad (\text{for any properties } A_1, \dots, A_n)$$

By this, the probabilistic law of quantum theory has been specified. For the outer measure μ , certain statements that would be expected to hold can now be derived. For example, the following applies for every time t and for all subspaces A and B of \mathcal{H} with $0 < \dim B < \infty$ (see T.5.5, p. 102):

$$\mu(\langle A, t \rangle \mid \langle B, t \rangle) = \text{tr } \pi_A \pi_B / \text{tr } \pi_B$$

The outer measure μ is introduced here without contradiction by a definition. Therefore, there is no problem with Bell's inequality at this point. Furthermore, the logical consistency of the entire theory formulated so far can be formally proven. Thus, there is no problem with any other possible no-go theorem as well (see T.5.6, p. 102).

Note: The fact that there is no problem with Bell's inequality here can be understood as follows: μ is defined on the entire algebra \mathcal{A} , i.e., for every possible fact in the model of quantum theory. However, as an outer measure, μ is not necessarily additive, and therefore Bell's inequality does not apply. A frequency measure P is always additive, but only where it is actually defined, e.g., on the algebra \mathcal{A}_e of all possible outcomes of a particular experiment. In this case, \mathcal{A}_e is merely a small subalgebra of \mathcal{A} . Bell's inequality then applies to P , but only on this subalgebra. We thus obtain a Bell's inequality only for every individual experiment, and this does not lead to any contradiction.

The theory is now complete with the definition of the model and the specification of the deterministic laws as well as the probabilistic law. It is an ontologically realistic theory of the quantum universe and its properties. All further considerations are merely about applying this theory to specific situations, such as experiments and their possible outcomes. Only within this framework is the quantum state defined and then applied to calculating probabilities of experimental results. The aim of these considerations is to derive the Copenhagen formalism from the theory defined here. By this it will become clear that this theory is a solution to the interpretation problem.

12. Definition of quantum states

A (conditional) quantum state can be defined for every subsystem Q of the universe, for every point in time t , and for every condition \mathcal{B} . A condition is a finite sequence $(B_1, t_1), \dots, (B_n, t_n)$ of possible events. If this sequence is empty (i.e., $n = 0$), we obtain the absolute state. In practical application, what comes into question as a condition, will primarily be the description of an experimental situation. Such a description always consists of a finite sequence of events. However, the empirical knowledge of a subject can also be described by such a sequence.

If Q is a subsystem of the universe, the Hilbert space of the universe can be represented as a tensor product:

$$\mathcal{H} = \mathcal{H}_Q \otimes \mathcal{H}_{Q^-}$$

Here, \mathcal{H}_Q is the Hilbert space of the subsystem Q and \mathcal{H}_{Q^-} is the Hilbert space of the “rest of the world”, which is denoted by Q^- .

In order to define the conditional quantum state for $t \in T$ and $\mathcal{B} = ((B_1, t_1), \dots, (B_n, t_n))$, let

$$\begin{aligned} A_j &:= U_{-t_j} B_j && (\text{for } j = 1, \dots, n) \\ L &:= \pi_{A_n} \dots \pi_{A_1} \\ W &:= LL^* / \text{tr}(LL^*) && (\text{with } L^* \text{ being the adjoint of } L) \\ W_t &:= U_t W U_{-t} \end{aligned}$$

and

$$W_{Q;t|\mathcal{B}} := \text{tr}_Q[W_t]$$

Here, $\text{tr}_Q[W_t]$ denotes the partial trace of W_t on the Hilbert space \mathcal{H}_Q .

$W_{Q;t|\mathcal{B}}$ is the conditional quantum state of Q at time t under condition \mathcal{B} . We can say that this state is *prepared* by condition \mathcal{B} .

Note: In the definition of the quantum state, A_j results from transforming condition (B_j, t_j) to time 0 (applying Schrödinger’s equation). The operator L combines the transformed conditions into a single term. W is the conditional state of the universe at time 0 and W_t is the corresponding state at time t .

As the *absolute* quantum state, we simply obtain

$$W_{Q;t|\emptyset} = I_Q / \text{tr } I_Q$$

where \emptyset is the “empty sequence” and I_Q is the identical operator on \mathcal{H}_Q . However, absolute quantum states do not play any role in practical application.

The quantum state $W_{Q;t|\mathcal{B}}$ is always a statistical operator. If this operator has rank one, it can be represented by a vector $\varphi \in \mathcal{H}$ as

$$W_{Q;t|\mathcal{B}} = \varphi \varphi^* \quad (\text{with } \varphi^* \text{ being the adjoint vector of } \varphi)$$

In this case, we speak of a *pure* state. However, in practice, such pure quantum states only occur as an approximation.

Note: The quantum states defined here are normalized in the sense that their trace is equal to one. However, this definition is possible only if the expression $\text{tr}(LL^*)$ has a positive and finite value. The case where this expression has the value zero is not relevant in practice. In the case of an infinite value, normalization is impossible; in this case, there is no *normalized* quantum state. Nevertheless, under certain circumstances, a non-normalized quantum state can still be used to predict probabilities of experimental results.

Note: In general, the projection operators that appear in the definition of a conditional quantum state are not commutable. The state defined above therefore depends on the order of the conditions. For states that are used to calculate probabilities of experimental results, the chronological order normally has to be adopted.

Note: The conditions that occur in the definition of a conditional quantum state typically do not refer to the subsystem Q under consideration, but to other parts of the universe. For this reason, it is not possible to interpret the quantum state – in the sense of state realism – as a physical property of the subsystem. Incidentally, for a subsystem Q there is not just one quantum state at a given point in time t, but rather many *conditional* quantum states at the same time. This is another reason why one cannot speak of “the quantum state” as a physical property.

In classical theory, one can define a probabilistic state analogous to quantum states. To do this, one simply has to replace the subspaces of the Hilbert space with measurable subsets of phase space, projection operators with indicator functions, the Schrödinger equation with the classical law of motion, and (partial) traces with (partial) integration, using the Lebesgue measure. In this case, a probabilistic state is a density function on phase space. As in quantum theory, these probabilistic states can be used to predict probabilities for possible outcomes of experiments (see Chapter B2, Section 3, p. 71).

Probabilistic states are not physical properties of the subsystems of the universe under consideration, nor do they represent a complete description of these subsystems. Rather, they are purely *computational* quantities that can be used to calculate probabilities. The same applies to quantum states; they simply are the probabilistic states of quantum theory.

If condition \mathcal{B} (as a sequence of events) describes a specific experiment, the corresponding conditional quantum state allows calculating probabilities of experimental results. If, on the other hand, condition \mathcal{B} describes the knowledge of a subject, the corresponding conditional quantum state $W_{Q;t|\mathcal{B}}$ indicates what the subject knows about subsystem Q at time t. The same applies to probabilistic states in classical theory.

– Remark –

It is important to understand the difference between subsystems of the universe and physical objects. A subsystem is essentially a tensor factor of the Hilbert space \mathcal{H} (for a precise definition, see Chapter B0, p. 55). Subsystems are purely mathematical entities that exist independently of time.

A physical object, on the other hand, has to be regarded as a *process*, i.e., as a sequence of events that is limited in time and whose existence is a contingent fact (see Section 21, p. 41). The complete description of a physical object at a certain time is by a subspace of Hilbert space, not by a quantum state.

Since quantum systems are expected to be entities that have quantum states, we identify quantum systems with subsystems of the universe, not with physical objects. Thus, every quantum system has a (conditional) quantum state for every condition and at each point in time.

The relationship between quantum systems and physical objects can be described as follows: The Hilbert space of quantum mechanics has a representation as a tensor product

$$\mathcal{H} = \otimes_q \mathcal{H}_q$$

where q runs through a set of subsystems that can be called “quanta”. Some of these quanta refer to electrons, and we let Q be one such quantum. For this elementary quantum system Q , we can choose a subspace A of \mathcal{H}_Q and let $A' := A \otimes \mathcal{H}_{Q^c}$ be the corresponding subspace of \mathcal{H} . Now, for every $t \in T$, the pair (A', t) specifies an “electron event”. An electron, as a physical object, is nothing but a sequence of such electron events.

In this way, a quantum system is used to *represent* a physical object, but it cannot be regarded as the same kind of entity. Mixing up these two concepts makes it impossible to clearly understand the role of quantum states.

13. Deterministic and probabilistic states

In the case of classical theory, every system (including the universe as a whole) is completely described by its deterministic state. The set of all these possible states forms the phase space Z . Such a state is a set of physical properties (e.g., locations and momenta of particles in the case of classical mechanics), by which all other properties (such as kinetic energy) are uniquely determined. As a consequence, each physical quantity corresponds to a mapping from the state space Z to \mathbb{R} .

This concept of a state can be generalized. A deterministic state, in general, is a fixed set of properties that determine every other property in a unique way. Such a state always represents a complete description of the system.

A deterministic state like this can also be defined in quantum theory. To do this, we consider the set \mathcal{U} of all factual properties, i.e., the set of closed linear subspaces of the Hilbert space. A complete description of the system is given if a truth value is specified for every $A \in \mathcal{U}$.

Thus, a deterministic state is a mapping $z^* : \mathcal{U} \rightarrow \{\text{true}, \text{false}\}$. However, not *every* such mapping corresponds to a proper state. Rather, z^* is a physically possible state only if z^* satisfies the principles of monotonicity and exclusion.

Note: The mapping $z^* : \mathcal{U} \rightarrow \{\text{true}, \text{false}\}$ satisfies the monotonicity principle if the following holds for all $A, B \in \mathcal{U}$:

$$A < B \Rightarrow (z^*(A) = \text{true} \Rightarrow z^*(B) = \text{true})$$

It satisfies the exclusion principle if the following applies to every sequence $A_j \in \mathcal{U}$:

$$A_j \text{ jointly orthogonal} \Rightarrow \exists_j (z^*(A_j) = \text{false})$$

Now, let Z^* be the set of all $z^* : \mathcal{U} \rightarrow \{\text{true}, \text{false}\}$ that satisfy these two principles. This is the deterministic state space of quantum theory. It can be formed both for the universe as a whole and for each subsystem. Every element of this state space represents a complete description of the system, by which all physical properties are determined. In particular, by a given state it is determined for each numerical quantity whether it has a value and, if so, what that value is. In the case of the universe as a whole, Schrödinger's equation provides a deterministic and reversible law of motion for this state over time, just as in the case of classical theory.

This construction of a state space can be carried out for any ontologically realistic theory, in particular for classical theory. In this case, Z^* is defined to be the set of all mappings $z^* : \mathcal{U} \rightarrow \{\text{true}, \text{false}\}$ that satisfy the monotonicity principle, the exclusion principle, and the physical “tertium non datur”. Here, \mathcal{U} is the algebra of all (Borel) measurable subsets of phase space.

For each element z of the phase space Z , let $z^* : \mathcal{U} \rightarrow \{\text{true}, \text{false}\}$ be defined by:

$$(z^*(A) = \text{true}) \Leftrightarrow z \in A \quad (\text{for all } A \in \mathcal{U})$$

It can be shown that this establishes a one-to-one relationship between the phase space Z and the state space Z^* defined here. The description of a classical system based on phase space turns out to be completely equivalent to the description based on Z^* (see T.2.2, p. 67).

An element $z^* \in Z^*$, like a point z in phase space, represents a deterministic state, i.e., it corresponds to a set of (factual) properties from which all other properties can be derived. Although this concept of state is less intuitive than that of phase space, ultimately these are just two entirely equivalent ways of completely describing a system.

We thus conclude that in quantum theory, as in the classical case, there is a deterministic state that completely describes the system. In both cases, the state of the universe moves in a deterministic and reversible way due to the law of motion. In both theories, there is also a conditional probabilistic state for every possible condition. In quantum theory, this probabilistic state is nothing other than the quantum state.

However, there is a significant difference between these two theories: In the case of classical theory, a pure probabilistic state corresponds to a density function on phase space that is concentrated on a single point. It therefore also corresponds to a deterministic state. This is

not the case in quantum theory. There, a pure quantum state is merely a statistical operator of rank one. Such an operator does not specify a truth value for every subspace of the Hilbert space and therefore does not correspond to a deterministic state. Thus, a pure quantum state (or a wave function) never represents a complete description of a quantum system, as is often assumed.

Note: Every event is described by the time t at which it occurs and by its form. This form is specified by a subspace A of Hilbert space. If the subspace is one-dimensional, i.e., if $A = [\varphi]$ with some wave function φ , then φ (together with t) completely describes the event. In this case, a wave function represents a complete description. However, it is not a quantum system that is completely described here, but an event. In this sense, a wave function can also be a complete description of a quantum object at a given point in time.

We now want to discuss the case of a conditional quantum state whose condition is the empirical knowledge of a subject. This knowledge corresponds to a finite sequence of events. In this case, the state describes the subject's knowledge of the quantum system. If it is a pure state, then we are dealing with a maximum possible knowledge. However, every real subject is finite and therefore can only have some finite knowledge. Therefore, even the maximum possible knowledge of a real subject never amounts to a complete description of the system. Such a complete description would rather correspond to the knowledge of Laplace's demon, i.e., infinite knowledge.

The lack of distinction between the maximum possible knowledge of finite subjects on the one hand and a complete description of a system on the other has caused some confusion in the interpretation of the quantum state in the past. The implicit identification (or mix-up) of the role of deterministic states in classical theory with that of probabilistic states in quantum theory (i.e., quantum states) has contributed to this as well.

With these considerations, the role of different types of states – and in particular the ontological status of the quantum state – has been fully clarified. There is no longer any problem of interpretation with regard to the quantum state.

14. The compatibility of determinism and probabilism

It is sometimes claimed that a fundamental difference between classical theory and quantum theory lies in the fact that randomness plays a different role in the two theories. In classical theory, probability is supposed to be relevant only because we as subjects do not have complete information about a system. Quantum theory, on the other hand, is said to be probabilistic in an elementary sense, i.e., there is said to be an objectively random transition from one point in time to the next. It was this idea that was rejected by Einstein when he said: "God does not play dice!"

In reality, however, we have the same situation in both theories. For the universe as a whole, in both cases there is – at the microscopic level, so to speak – a deterministic law over time, i.e., from one point in time to the next. We can refer to this as "microscopic determinism".

At the same time, the concept of probability is defined – in quantum theory as well as in classical theory – on the set Ω of physically possible worlds, i.e., those worlds that comply with the deterministic law of motion. So we have a probabilistic law *in addition* to the deterministic relationship.

Since every world is already determined by its (deterministic) initial state, the probabilistic law can be defined on the set of possible initial states. We can therefore refer to it as an “initial probability law”. In both theories, it does not matter which point in time we choose as the “initial point in time”.

For the transition from a macroscopic event (B,s) to a later event (A,t) , we obtain a transition probability on this basis. In the case of classical theory, for example, it is simply

$$P(\langle A,t \rangle | \langle B,s \rangle) = \lambda(A \cap \beta_{s,t}(B)) / \lambda(\beta_{s,t}(B))$$

where λ is the Lebesgue measure and the mapping

$$\beta_{s,t} : Z \rightarrow Z$$

describes the transition of deterministic states from s to t based on the classical law of motion. Microscopic determinism – together with the initial probability law – thus results in macroscopic transition probabilism, i.e., we obtain conditional probabilities for the occurrence of macroscopic events when one or more other macroscopic events are given.

Therefore, neither in classical theory nor in quantum theory is there any contradiction between the existence of a deterministic law of motion and the existence of a probabilistic law, between determinism and probabilism.

Note: The deterministic law of motion always applies to closed systems only. It will therefore apply only to the universe as a whole, since this is the sole system that is truly closed. Since a complete description of a proper subsystem of the universe never constitutes a complete description of the entire universe, such subsystems always show random behavior.

In summary, we can say that there is no contradiction between determinism and probabilism. Rather, microscopic determinism combined with initial probabilism results in macroscopic transitional probabilism. This applies to both classical and quantum theory.

In both cases, the not-knowing of subjects plays the same role: Since such a subject does not know all the properties of the universe, it can only have probabilistic knowledge about future events, and for this reason it is interested in the probabilities indicated by the probabilistic law. Laplace’s demon, on the other hand, who knows the (deterministic) initial state, i.e., who knows which of the possible events actually occurred at time 0, can predict all future events. Because of this, that demon is not interested in the probabilistic law.

In quantum theory, the concept of probability plays exactly the same role as in classical theory; there is no difference between quantum theory and classical theory in this respect.

15. The initial condition

We now turn to the question of how the Copenhagen quantum formalism can be derived from the theory formulated here. This formalism refers to the preparation and description of quantum systems, to measurements that can be performed on them, and to the probabilities with which the individual possible results of these measurements occur. In short, the quantum formalism refers to experiments and their results.

A prerequisite for applying the quantum formalism to an experiment is that the experiment can be evaluated at a point in time t . To this end, both the preconditions and the results of the experiment must be documented at time t in a macroscopic manner. We therefore have to address the question of what a document actually is, under what conditions document relationships exist, and when a document is macroscopic.

Document relationships can only exist in a universe that is not in thermodynamic equilibrium. The latter is true of the real universe, which is characterized by a constant increase in entropy. Without this increase in entropy, which we experience as the “arrow of time”, neither biological evolution on Earth would have been possible, nor could there be subjects that perceive the world around them.

We are therefore forced to assume that the universe had low entropy at some early point in time and, without loss of generality, we can assume this time to be 0. The assumption of low entropy can be described by a property that will be referred to as the “initial property”. In quantum theory, this property is modeled by a subspace UR of the Hilbert space of the universe (“ UR ” as in German “*Ursprung*” (origin) or “*Urknall*” (big bang)). The event consisting of the property UR being realized at time 0 – i.e., the event $(UR,0)$ – can be referred to as the “initial condition”.

In view of the reversible law of motion, the fact of a directed timeline in the real universe (i.e., the arrow of time) can only be explained by assuming such an initial condition. It says that the universe was far from thermodynamic equilibrium at time 0 and thus explains the still ongoing increase in entropy in the universe.

Note: In classical physics, one must also assume an initial condition. There, it is represented by a subset of phase space.

16. Macroscopic documents

A property is called “macroscopic” if it can be directly perceived by macroscopic subjects such as ourselves. In Section 4 we showed that all macroscopic properties of an N -particle system can be modeled by pairwise commutable subspaces. In the general case, the set of macroscopic properties is also characterized by the fact that its elements (as subspaces of the Hilbert space) are pairwise commutable.

Note: In the context of pure quantum mechanics, the commutability of macroscopic properties follows from the fact that macroscopic subjects can directly perceive only “coarse” position-momentum properties that are far from the uncertainty relation.

An *event* is called macroscopic if it consists of a macroscopic property being present at a point in time t . A macroscopic *document* is a macroscopic event that is in a document relationship with the documented event.

If a macroscopic event (D,t) is to be a document for another (usually earlier) event (A,s) , the document relationship needed will usually exist only under one or more conditions, which form a sequence of events such as $(E_0,t_0), \dots, (E_k,t_k)$. The conditional document relationship now exists if and only if with the abbreviations

$$\begin{aligned} A' &:= U_{-s} A \\ D' &:= U_{-t} D \\ B_j &:= U_{-t_j} E_j \quad (\text{for } j = 0, \dots, k) \end{aligned}$$

the equation

$$\pi_{A'} \pi_{B_k} \dots \pi_{B_0} = \pi_{D'} \pi_{B_k} \dots \pi_{B_0}$$

holds. In practice, such document relationships will always be approximate only. The memory of macroscopic subjects is also based on the existence of macroscopic documents, such as memory traces in the brain.

Note: There are various ways to justify this definition of (conditional) document relationships, including one using the classical approximation described in Section 4 (for a more detailed discussion see Chapter B6, pp. 103-105).

Note: The document relationships considered here are bidirectional: they allow conclusions to be drawn from a document (D,t) to the documented event (A,s) , but also vice versa. If A is a subspace of C , then (based on the monotonicity principle) a conclusion can also be drawn from the document (D,t) to the event (C,s) . However, the reverse conclusion is not possible in this case. Instead, there is only a *unidirectional* document relationship between (D,t) and (C,s) . This relationship is characterized by the equation

$$\pi_{(C')^\perp} \pi_{D'} \pi_{B_k} \dots \pi_{B_0} = 0 \quad (\text{with the abbreviation } C' := U_{-s} C)$$

17. Empirical accessibility

We now turn to the question of when a subject – given an existing document relationship – can infer the documented event (A,s) from its knowledge of a macroscopic document (D,t) at time t . Such a conclusion is only possible if the subject also has empirical knowledge of the conditions under which the document relationship exists. A subject can only know about such a condition (B,r) on the basis of another macroscopic document (E,t) at time t . However, the document relationship between (B,r) and (E,t) will only exist under further conditions.

In order to avoid an infinite regress, we must ultimately start from a condition for which no document is required. It is only the initial condition $(UR,0)$ that can serve this purpose.

Note: For the initial condition itself, there can be no document in this sense. Rather, this condition is the *prerequisite* for there being objectively existing document relationships in the universe.

To formally describe the concept of empirical accessibility, let us consider a sequence of possible events, such as $(E_1, t_1), \dots, (E_n, t_n)$. If these events are to be empirically accessible from a point in time t , then there must be macroscopic documents $(D_1, t), \dots, (D_n, t)$ such that, for all k , (D_k, t) is a document for (E_k, t_k) under the condition $(UR, 0), (E_1, t_1), \dots, (E_{k-1}, t_{k-1})$. This document relationship must be independent of all other events $(E_{k+1}, t_{k+1}), \dots, (E_n, t_n)$ as well as and their documents $(D_{k+1}, t), \dots, (D_n, t)$. If a subject starts from the initial condition and knows all the documents D_1, \dots, D_n at time t , then it can infer from this, step by step, the occurrence of the events $(E_1, t_1), \dots, (E_n, t_n)$.

Note: The conditional document relationship between an event (A, s) and the document (D, t) under the condition $(E_0, t_0), \dots, (E_n, t_n)$ is independent of the events $(F_1, s_1), \dots, (F_m, s_m)$ if the document relationship between (A, s) and (D, t) exists independently of whether any number of elements of the sequence $(F_1, s_1), \dots, (F_m, s_m)$ are removed from the condition $(E_0, t_0), \dots, (E_n, t_n)$ or additionally included in this condition.

18. Macroscopic experiments and their probability measure

A macroscopic experiment is an experiment whose conditions and possible results are all empirically accessible from a point in time t . In the following, we will consider such an experiment.

The conditions of the experiment form a sequence of events. The possible experimental results are divided into a (finite) set of (finite) alternatives and thus form a subalgebra \mathcal{A}_e within the algebra \mathcal{A} of all possible facts. Together, all the events involved form an empirically accessible sequence. At the beginning of this sequence, the conditions of the experiment are listed, followed by the possible experimental results. In addition, we must require here that the document relationships between the possible experimental results and their documents are independent of all other possible results and their documents.

Let G denote the possible fact that all conditions of the experiment (including the initial condition) are given. Furthermore, let N denote the possible fact that at least one of the possible outcomes of each of the alternatives is realized (so that one can speak of a successful completion of the experiment). We then define:

$$P_e(F) := \mu(F | G \wedge N) \quad (\text{for all } F \in \mathcal{A}_e)$$

Moreover, we define the associated conditional probabilities in the usual way:

$$P_e(F | F') := P_e(F \wedge F') / P_e(F') \quad (\text{for all } F, F' \in \mathcal{A}_e)$$

Under the conditions described for a (macroscopic) experiment, it can be proven that P_e is an additive probability measure in the sense of Kolmogorov on the algebra of all possible experimental results. Essential to the proof is the fact that the results of the experiment are documented by pairwise commutable properties at the time of evaluation (see T.7.3, p. 129).

These considerations make it clear why Kolmogorov's concept of probability can be successfully applied to macroscopically evaluable experiments.

Note: The outer measure $\mu(\cdot | G \wedge N)$ defined for all possible facts will, in general, not be additive on the entire algebra \mathcal{A} . Only its restriction P_e to the algebra \mathcal{A}_e of possible results of the macroscopic experiment proves to be additive and thus is a Kolmogorov probability measure.

Note: The physical “tertium non datur” cannot be included in quantum theory as a general law, as this would lead to a contradiction due to the Kochen-Specker theorem. However, it can hold for certain individual events as a contingent fact. In this sense, the possible fact N represents the contingent physical “tertium non datur” for the results of the experiment.

19. Quantum experiments and the Copenhagen formalism

A quantum experiment is basically nothing more than a special macroscopic experiment. However, the possible experimental results do not simply form a *set*, but an ordered *sequence* of alternatives, i.e., the order is important here. We denote the sequence of alternatives by

$$\mathcal{A}_1, \dots, \mathcal{A}_R$$

As with any macroscopic experiment, both the conditions of the experiment and the results must be empirically accessible.

In a quantum experiment, the experimental results are interpreted as “measurement results”. The document relationships between the experimental results, i.e., the measurement results, and the macroscopic documents at the time of evaluation must exist independently of all other measurement results.

Within the framework of such a quantum experiment, measurement relationships have to be defined. Such a relationship exists between any event (e.g., the presence of a certain quantum property) on the one hand and the measurement result on the other. The latter belongs to the empirically accessible events of the experiment. In principle, a measurement relationship has the same form as a document relationship. However, in contrast to document relationships of a macroscopic experiment, we do not assume measurement relationships to be independent of the results of subsequent measurements. (At this point, the order of the alternatives to be measured plays a role.)

For such quantum experiments, it can be shown that the (conditional) probability of a specific measurement result for one of the alternatives can be calculated using the equations known from the formalism of quantum theory on the basis of the corresponding (conditional) quan-

tum state. The condition of this quantum state must correspond to the condition of the probability to be calculated. This condition includes the conditions of the experiment as well as the results for the preceding alternatives.

Formally, we can describe this as follows: Let the measurement be about the r -th alternative, i.e., about \mathcal{A}_r with $1 \leq r \leq R$. Let Q be the quantum system under consideration and τ be the time at which the measurement takes place. Let A be one of the properties of Q that can be measured within the r -th alternative. Thus, A is a subspace of the Hilbert space of Q . Now let $A' := A \otimes \mathcal{H}_{Q^-}$ be the corresponding property of the universe (for the definition of \mathcal{H}_{Q^-} see Section 12, p. 27). The event (A', τ) then must be in a measurement relationship with one of the possible measurement results of the r -th alternative. We refer to this measurement result as M_A . Let \mathcal{B}_{r-1} be the condition which, in addition to the experimental conditions (including the initial condition), contains the measurement results M_1, \dots, M_{r-1} for the alternatives \mathcal{A}_1 to \mathcal{A}_{r-1} . Here, M_1, \dots, M_{r-1} and M_A are elements of \mathcal{A}_e , the algebra of possible results of the experiment.

Now, by

$$W_{r-1} := W_{Q; \tau | \mathcal{B}_{r-1}}$$

the quantum state “before measurement” is defined. For this state, it can be shown that the following applies (see T.8.2, p. 150):

$$P_e(M_A | M_1 \wedge \dots \wedge M_{r-1}) = \text{tr}(\pi_A W_{r-1})$$

This corresponds to the well-known equation

$$p_A = \text{tr}(\pi_A W)$$

from the Copenhagen formalism for a so-called “mixed” state W . If W is a pure state, i.e., if $W = \varphi \varphi^*$ with a vector φ , then this equation reduces to the well-known formula

$$p_A = |\pi_A \varphi|^2$$

Note: To simplify terminology, we do not distinguish here between an event $(A, t) \in \mathcal{E}$ and the associated possible fact $\langle A, t \rangle \in \mathcal{A}$.

Note: Due to the definition of P_e , the conditions of the experiment are already contained in P_e and therefore do not need to be written explicitly into the condition.

Analogous to \mathcal{B}_{r-1} , let \mathcal{B}_r be the condition which, in addition to the experimental conditions (including the initial condition), contains the measurement results M_1, \dots, M_{r-1} for the alternatives \mathcal{A}_1 to \mathcal{A}_{r-1} as well as the measurement result M_A for the r -th alternative. Obviously, \mathcal{B}_r is derived from \mathcal{B}_{r-1} by adding the measurement result M_A to it. Now let:

$$W_r := W_{Q; \tau | \mathcal{B}_r}$$

While W_{r-1} is the quantum state “before” the measurement result M_A for the r -th alternative is available, W_r is the state “thereafter”.

It can now be shown that the relationship known from the Copenhagen quantum formalism exists between the quantum states “before” and “after” the measurement, i.e., the following holds (see T.8.4, p. 152):

$$W_r = \pi_A W_{r-1} \pi_A / \text{tr}(\pi_A W_{r-1} \pi_A)$$

This is a relationship between two different conditional quantum states. Here, there is no such thing as a measurement “changing the quantum state”.

As we already established in Section 5, the motion of a quantum system, i.e., a subsystem of the universe, can be described approximately by a Schrödinger equation if its retroactive effect on the environment is so small that the effect of the environment on the system is not significantly changed by it.

These considerations show that the quantum theoretical state calculus can be applied under suitable conditions, in particular under conditions such as those that exist for macroscopic subjects. We have thus shown that the Copenhagen quantum formalism can be derived from the theory presented here. Therefore, this theory constitutes a valid interpretation of the quantum formalism. In contrast to previous, rather speculative attempts at such an interpretation, this is an ontologically realistic, logically sound, and precisely formulated theory whose consistency can be formally proven. Thus, we can speak of a *solution* to the interpretation problem.

20. Reduction of quantum states and the problem of measurement

Reasonably, a subject should be interested in those conditional probabilities whose condition corresponds to its knowledge at a given time. We refer to a conditional probability in which the condition represents the empirical knowledge of a subject as a “subject-related probability”.

Similarly, the subject reasonably assigns to a subsystem of the universe the conditional quantum state whose condition corresponds to its knowledge. In doing so, it assigns to the subsystem precisely the state that allows it to calculate the probabilities in which it is interested. We refer to this state as the “subject-related quantum state”.

From the subject’s point of view, the subject-related probability simply is “the” probability. Since the subject can, under certain circumstances, calculate such probabilities by using the subject-related quantum state, it also considers this state to be simply “the” quantum state.

Here, the subject-related quantum state does not refer to the state that the subject actually uses, but rather the one that it *should* use given its (empirical) knowledge. The same applies to subject-related probabilities. Whether the subject knows quantum theory or probability theory at all and can apply it correctly is of no relevance in this context.

We will now consider a quantum experiment and use the notations introduced in the previous section. We assume that a subject (the “observer”) already knows the results for the first $r-1$ alternatives, but not the outcome for the r -th alternative. In this case, the subject is interested in those conditional probabilities in which the expression \mathcal{B}_{r-1} appears in the condition

(subject-related probabilities). In order to calculate them, the subject needs the conditional quantum state in which the expression \mathcal{B}_{r-1} appears in the condition as well (subject-related quantum state).

Based on this subject-related quantum state, the subject can calculate the probabilities of interest for the possible outcomes of the next measurement (i.e., the r -th alternative) using the formula known from the quantum theoretical state calculus.

When the subject now reads out the result of the r -th alternative and concludes, based on the existence of the measurement relationship, that A has been measured, its knowledge changes. As a consequence, its interest now focuses on the conditional probabilities with condition \mathcal{B}_r . Along with the subject's knowledge, the subject-related probabilities as well as the associated subject-related quantum state change. The same applies if the subject obtains knowledge of the measurement result in some other way, for example, by receiving a message. The change in the subject-related quantum state for the subsystem under consideration is described by the quantum theoretical state calculus.

The abrupt change in the subject-related quantum state (the “quantum leap” or “reduction of the wave function”) that occurs “during measurement” (or more precisely: when the measurement result is read out) does not mean that there is any physical change in the quantum system under consideration. Rather, it is an expression of the equally abrupt change in the subject's knowledge and thus its interest. Moreover, there is no interaction between the subject and the system under consideration either. What is “reduced” when reading out the measurement result is solely the subject's not-knowing of this result. Neither are the (conditional) quantum states in question physical properties of the system, nor does the act of observation change any of these states.

For a second observer who does not receive any information about the new measurement result, the previous quantum state remains relevant. The same applies if the subject later forgets about the measurement result it has read (or the information obtained in another way). In this case, the original conditional state becomes relevant for it again. By analogy with the notion of a “quantum leap”, one could speak of a “quantum leap backwards” in this case.

Even if the subject-related quantum state refers to a distant object, there is no “spooky action at a distance” involved when reading out a measurement result. By the way, the question of such “remote effects” does not arise only in the context of quantum theory. It can as well be discussed with regard to probabilities of properties that a distant object has. These (subject-related) probabilities will also change when a subject receives new information. In this case, a physical change only takes place in the subject itself, not in the distant object.

The change of the quantum state, when a measurement result is read or another observation is made, normally takes place at a specific point in time and in an abrupt manner. This is a consequence of the fact that the subject's knowledge changes abruptly as well. In cases, however, where the subject's knowledge changes in a continuous way, the change of the subject-related quantum state also takes place in a continuous manner. In practice, such a case can occur when the subject reads out a pointer position and is able to recognize the position of the pointer more and more accurately over time. Consider, for example, the case where the pointer

is observed using a microscope (or a telescope) whose focus is gradually adjusted to become better and better. In such a case, the change of the subject-related probability based on a change in knowledge would no longer take place in an abrupt way. Similarly, the change of the subject-related quantum state caused by an observation could then be described as a continuous process over time.

The change in a subject's knowledge is a physical process that takes a certain amount of time and is associated with an increase in entropy. During this time interval, the subject's knowledge is not clearly defined. In this situation, the subject-related probabilities and quantum states are undefined as well, i.e., they simply have no value at all.

Up to now, we have discussed the question of how quantum states change when a measurement result is read. In the following, we will address the question of what role the interaction with a measuring device plays for the quantum state.

To do this, we consider the case where a certain property is made measurable by the additional implementation of a measuring device. The presence of the measuring device is described by additional conditions that must be included in the condition of the quantum state. For the time before the interaction between the quantum system and the measuring device, the quantum state typically does not change due to these new conditions: it is the other conditions that prepare this state.

However, based on the law of motion for the universe, the interaction with the measuring device leads to a change in the quantum state over time in the sense of decoherence. The original state W then transitions, for example, into a state of the form

$$W' = \pi_A W \pi_A + \pi_{A^\perp} W \pi_{A^\perp}$$

where A is the property to be measured. Here, there is no reduction of the quantum state.

After reading the measurement result, the subject's interest focuses on the conditional state where this result has been added to the condition. If the measurement result corresponds to property A (rather than A^\perp), this state would be

$$W'' = \pi_A W \pi_A / \text{tr}(\pi_A W \pi_A)$$

In this way, a measurement can be described in two steps, each of which affects the quantum state: the interaction with the measuring device and the reading of the result. It is crucial to understand that quantum states, like probabilistic states in classical theory, are not physical properties of the system under consideration.

The above considerations fully answer the question of what changes the states of quantum systems undergo during a measurement. This concerns both the interaction of the quantum system with the measuring device and the reading of the measurement result. There is no problem of interpretation left in this regard, i.e., a "problem of measurement" does not exist in the theory considered here.

– Remark –

The existence of a subject and its knowledge are objective facts. Therefore, subject-related quantum states and probabilities are objectively given quantities. A subject can be a human being, a cat, or even a machine. The only thing that matters here is that the subject can have different (physical) states that can be interpreted as “knowing” or “not knowing” about a certain fact.

Subjects can be understood as material reality within the universe. A philosophical dualism of mind and matter – in the sense that there is a world of minds outside the material world – is not necessary here.

Since the subject-related quantum state is an objectively existing quantity, one can speak of an “objective collapse” when a measurement result is read. However, only the subject’s not-knowing and thus the subject-related state collapses here, not a real property of the quantum system.

21. Physical objects

In everyday life, we see ourselves surrounded by macroscopic objects such as tables, billiard balls, etc. The presence of such an object constitutes an event that is described by a pair (A,t) . Here, t is the time at which the object is present, and A is a subspace of the Hilbert space that describes the “form” of the object. This “form” includes all properties that characterize the object, such as its location, momentum, angular momentum, length, or mass.

The classical view assumes that an object is composed of stable elementary particles each of which has eternal existence (atomism). As long as the composition of the object does not change, the object remains “self-identical” and as such has properties like location, length, etc.

In quantum theory, this must be viewed differently: there is no self-identity of objects here. Just as a wave on the surface of water cannot be understood as a self-identical object, but as a *process*, so too with objects in quantum theory. A physical object does not constitute an object in the classical sense, but rather a process in the universe that extends over a certain period of time.

Note: A wave on the water is certainly not a classical self-identical object. However, one could argue that such a wave requires a medium, in this case water, which could be regarded as a self-identical object. However, this does not apply to electromagnetic waves; here, the idea of such a medium (for example, in the form of an “ether”) has been reasonably rejected. In pure classical field theory, there are no self-identical objects, and the same is true in quantum theory. Of course, this does not mean that quantum theory is a classical field theory.

In quantum theory, every physical object, e.g., a moving or stationary billiard ball, has to be understood as a process. Such a process is nothing but a (continuous or discrete) sequence of events, each of which has the form (A,t) . If M is the set of points in time at which the object

exists, e.g., a time interval, then for every $t \in M$, we have a subspace A_t of the Hilbert space, and the process consists in the fact that all events (A_t, t) occur.

The uniform motion of a ball flying through empty space at velocity v , for example, is described by such a process where (for all $t, t' \in M$) $A_{t'}$ is the result of shifting the subspace A_t in space by a value of $v \cdot (t' - t)$. (Shifting a wave function in space is represented by a unitary operator on the Hilbert space; by this operator subspaces can be shifted as well.)

The stability of such an object (which leads us to the illusion of self-identity) consists in the fact that the transition probabilities from one event to the next are extremely high, i.e., they are very close to one. However, we only find this stability in macroscopic objects. This can be understood as an expression of the fact that the external properties of such objects are subject to only minor fluctuations because they are averages of a very large number of microscopic degrees of freedom.

In principle, the same applies to microscopic objects (such as electrons), i.e., they too are not self-identical objects, but processes in the sense described above. However, microscopic objects are much less stable than macroscopic objects. In their case, the transition probabilities from one event (A_t, t) to the next are much smaller. Microscopic particles therefore appear as objects that are spontaneously created and destroyed.

While in classical atomism elementary particles are infinitely stable and macroscopic objects are mutable, at least in principle, in quantum theory it is exactly the opposite: the smaller an object is, the more unstable it is and the less it resembles a classical particle. Absolutely stable (i.e., “eternal”) objects do not exist in quantum theory. The only “object” that exists eternally is the universe as a whole.

Note: In the classical view, space plays the role of a domain in which particles (or mass points) reside. At the same time, it plays the role of a base on which classical fields are defined point by point. This is not the case in quantum theory. Here, the smallest possible units are wave functions, which are always extended over a finite or infinite range in space. There is no point-like reality here. In quantum theory, space is just a set of displacement possibilities, i.e., it is not a set of *points*, but a set of (displacement) *vectors*. The same applies to time in quantum field theory, i.e., to spacetime as a whole.

– Remark 1 –

The Hilbert space of quantum mechanics can be represented as a tensor product

$$\mathcal{H} = \otimes_q \mathcal{H}_q$$

where q runs through a set of subsystems that we can refer to as “quanta”. Each permutation of quanta of the same kind corresponds to a unitary operator on \mathcal{H} . These operators form the symmetry group of “particle exchange”. An object can be modeled as a process, i.e., as a sequence of events (A_t, t) , where the subspaces A_t are symmetric with respect to this group. In this case, it is not specified which quanta the object is “composed” of.

However, it is also possible to assume that the object “consists” of *certain* quanta. In this case, the object is represented by a subsystem Q of the universe, namely the subsystem that is composed of these particular quanta. The subspaces A_t involved here then have the form $B_t \otimes \mathcal{H}_Q^-$, where B_t is a property of Q , i.e., a subspace of \mathcal{H}_Q . This representation makes it possible to apply the quantum formalism to physical objects: under certain conditions, the probability that an object, described by B_t as its form, is present at time t can be calculated using the (conditional) quantum state of Q , and this state behaves as we have described in Sections 19 and 20.

– Remark 2 –

In Section 4, we discussed the Hilbert space of quantum mechanics as an approximate description of a classical N -particle system. The Hilbert space of quantum field theory (QFT) is obtained from this, in principle, by allowing the number of particles N to take on an arbitrary value. In this sense, if \mathcal{H}_N denotes the Hilbert space of the N -particle system, let

$$\mathcal{H}_{\text{QFT}} := \bigoplus_N \mathcal{H}_N$$

This is the “unsymmetrized” Fock space. Usually, the Hilbert space \mathcal{H}_N is first symmetrized (with respect to the symmetry of particle exchange) and then the direct sum is formed. However, the reverse approach is also possible: the usual (symmetrized) Fock space is obtained by subsequently implementing particle exchange symmetry on \mathcal{H}_{QFT} .

The release of the particle number N is possible in classical mechanics as well. Let Z_N be the phase space of an N -particle system and let

$$Z := \bigcup_N Z_N$$

be the union of these phase spaces. In this phase space Z , too, every macroscopic property can be modeled by a subset: when we describe a table standing in front of us, we do not determine the number of particles in the universe or the exact number of particles that make up this table.

Macroscopic properties can be represented in this way in the non-symmetrized Fock space just as well as in the Hilbert space of quantum mechanics. Thus, everything we have said here about the modeling of physical objects applies to quantum field theory in an analogous way.

22. The model of the microscopic and its intuitiveness

The intuitive classical model of the microscopic cannot be preserved in quantum theory. It is replaced by the less intuitive Hilbert space model. The subsets of phase space are replaced here by the subspaces of Hilbert space – as those elements of the model that correspond to the actual physical properties, i.e., the predicates of the universe. As a consequence, the intuitiveness and visualizability of the classical model is substantially lost.

However, we must note that the classical model is based on a very naive assumption. In physics, we want to be able to visualize the microscopic structure. But what we can visualize is just what we could perceive if it were present. It is only the macroscopic that we can directly

perceive. A microscopic structure therefore becomes visualizable only if it corresponds to a downsized version of the macroscopic. For this reason, it was plausible to assume that the microscopic world is made up of small objects, atoms or elementary particles, which can be imagined as downsized billiard balls, for example. It was also plausible to assume that the macroscopic field structures would be found again at the microscopic level (in an infinitely fine form).

This gave rise to the classical concept of the microscopic as a duality of particles and fields. At its core, it is based on the naive and intuitive assumption that the structure of the microscopic is a miniature version of the macroscopic, an assumption that is not really justified.

The classical concept has now failed: double-slit experiments show that there are no microscopic particles in the classical sense, and the ultraviolet catastrophe has shown that fields at the microscopic level are no longer classical. The model of quantum theory describes a structure that is not a miniaturized version of the macroscopic. Physicists who are accustomed to classical, intuitive thinking may find such a structure strange or even “unphysical”.

But what can be done about this? Given that the model of reality in quantum theory (and thus the structure of the real quantum world) lacks intuitiveness, it is necessary to use methods that have proven themselves in dealing with non-intuitive things. These are the methods of mathematics. Mathematics has long been working on topics that lack visualizability, e.g., spaces of arbitrary dimensions. In order to navigate such topics safely, it was necessary to develop the methodology of logic and set theory. It is plausible, therefore, that this methodology should also be applied when considering a micro world that largely defies visualizability and intuitiveness.

Not only must genuinely *physical* topics be approached in a logically precise manner, but it is also necessary, for example, to accurately formulate the concept of probability and to clearly define the associated domain of definition, i.e., the set of possible facts in the given physical model.

Common practices in physics of setting up formulas, deriving further formulas from them, and then intuitively applying them to specific real situations is not sufficient for this purpose. Schrödinger rightly complained that “quantum theory” consists of formulas or equations that have no clear meaning. Calculating with such formulas is often referred to in physics as “the math”. However, it has little to do with the mathematical process of precisely defining every term that is used and then logically deriving statements from statements.

Particularly because of the abstract nature of the Hilbert space model, it is not appropriate in quantum physics to use an approach that involves calculating with formulas whose elements have no clear meaning. Physical theory should rather consist of precise *statements*, not formulas or equations. Of course, equations may *occur* in these statements, for example, in a law of motion.

Note: The practice of treating physical theories as “formalisms”, i.e., deriving formulas from formulas and then applying them intuitively to concrete situations, is related to the tradition

of classical physics. The model of this physics is numerically realistic, i.e., a complete description of a system is given by the values of a certain set of numerical quantities. This leads to the habit of numerical thinking, i.e., the habit in physics of searching for the “right equation”, ideally a world formula, which should preferably have the form of a differential equation.

The fundamental problems of mathematics were successfully addressed by considering logic, set theory, and mathematics itself as formal theories within “naive” set theory and mathematics, as formal logic, formal set theory, etc. A similar approach is necessary if one wants to solve the fundamental problems of physics.

To this end, a physical theory must be regarded as a formal system with the following components: the model, deterministic laws, and probabilistic laws. In model building, logical precision is important, not visualizability or intuitiveness. However, in Section 4, we showed how elements of the Hilbert space (as multivariate wave functions) and the more abstract concept of subspaces, which play the role of the real physical properties of the universe, can be understood in a concrete and somewhat intuitive way.

23. Weirdness and philosophical consequences of quantum theory

In the debate on interpretation, there are a multitude of statements circulating about the alleged “weirdness” of quantum theory and about the philosophical consequences that this theory is said to have. Here we want to discuss the question of whether quantum theory, when formulated in a reasonable way, is particularly weird and whether it does have the assumed philosophical consequences.

First, it is necessary to distinguish between two types of weirdness: weirdness that is rooted in the structure of reality (weirdness of the quantum *world*) and weirdness that is inherent in quantum *theory*, i.e., weirdness of the Copenhagen quantum formalism. It will turn out that all the oddities of this formalism can be removed, while nothing can be changed about the peculiarities of the quantum world, of course.

The peculiarities of “quantum theory” (meaning the Copenhagen formalism) include the following points in particular:

- (1) The theory has no model of reality.
- (2) Subjective concepts such as measurement, observation, and preparation are used in the formulation of the theory (subjectivism of the theory).
- (3) The theory says nothing about objective reality, or rather, according to the theory, there is no such thing as objective reality at all, and all that exists is just “information” (phenomenalism).
- (4) A measurement results in a quantum leap, i.e., a reduction of the wave function (problem of measurement).
- (5) The quantum state is supposed to constitute a complete description, but allows probabilistic predictions only (randomness of what happens in the universe).

The considerations in this text show that the peculiarities mentioned above no longer exist when the theory is formulated accordingly. On the one hand, a model of the quantum world can indeed be specified. The laws can be formulated without reference to subjective concepts such as measurement or observation; they are statements about the assumed objective reality. “Information” refers to certain states of subjects that are regarded as part of material reality and can, for example, develop in the course of biological evolution.

The quantum leap only affects the subject-related state, which (as a conditional probabilistic state) is by definition dependent on the state of knowledge of a subject. In general, probabilistic states (as in classical theory) are not physical properties of a subsystem of the universe, but rather computational quantities by which (conditional) probabilities can be calculated. The quantum state is a probabilistic state that only says something about probabilities. However, as in classical theory, there is also a deterministic state in quantum theory that completely describes the system.

One of the peculiarities of quantum theory is the existence of no-go theorems, which seem to prevent the formulation of a realistic model. However, as we have shown, the well-known no-go problems can be resolved in a meaningful way. Furthermore, the consistency of the theory can be formally proven, so that the existence of any other no-go problems can also be ruled out.

We now turn to the philosophical consequences that quantum theory is said to have. Two points in particular are worth mentioning here:

- (1) the non-existence of an objective reality that is independent of observation,
- (2) the fundamental randomness of what happens in the universe.

First of all, it should be noted that these “consequences” do not arise at all if the theory is formulated in a reasonable way. If a theory is based on a model of reality, as is the case here, it does not give rise to doubt about the existence of this reality.

It remains true that, in the sense of Immanuel Kant, the world will always be known only in the way it appears to us, and that we cannot know anything about the “world-in-itself” (nor, for that matter, whether it exists or not). However, this is a general philosophical insight that has nothing to do with a specific physical theory. Furthermore, this insight does not prevent us from reconstructing a “world-in-itself” from the phenomena we are given, which is what we do in everyday life when we say, for example, “there is a tree”, and not, “I am given the appearance of a tree”. This reconstruction of the “world-in-itself” serves us to organize the phenomena and thus make them understandable, i.e., “explain” them. In the same sense, it is the task of physics to reconstruct a “world-in-itself” from the observations we make and to formulate a model of the universe suitable for this purpose.

So, if the non-existence of an objective reality is supposed to be a consequence of “quantum theory”, then this only applies to the Copenhagen quantum formalism. Here, however, cause and effect are reversed, so to speak: the quantum formalism *refrains* from formulating a model of reality and making statements about this reality. Instead, it talks about “observables” and “measurements”, i.e., subjective terms. Rejecting the assumption of an objective reality is, in a sense, the philosophical *premise* of this formalism; it is not, however, its *consequence*.

As far as the randomness of what happens in the universe is concerned, i.e., the question of whether “God plays dice”, there is no difference between classical and quantum theory. In both cases, there is a deterministic law of motion (so God does not play dice). But in both cases, it is also necessary to assign probabilities to the possible paths in the deterministic state space. Without the probabilistic law, neither a dice experiment nor a process of entropy increase could be described even in classical theory. Therefore, a fundamental randomness of what happens in the universe is not a “philosophical consequence” of quantum theory.

In summary, it can thus be stated that the assumed “philosophical consequences” of quantum theory simply do not exist.

We have shown that the oddities of quantum *theory* disappear once the theory has been formulated not only in an ontologically realistic manner (beginning with a model of reality), but also in a logically consistent, unambiguous, and precise way. Moreover, it has become clear that the often-claimed “philosophical consequences” of quantum theory do not exist. We will now turn to the question of what the peculiarities of the quantum *world* are all about.

In order to do so, we will discuss some of the peculiarities of the theory of the quantum world presented here that distinguish this theory from the classical one. These peculiarities may be perceived as “strange” or “unphysical”. However, this is the case only if one starts from certain traditional ideas or habits of physics, especially classical physics.

a) Lack of intuitiveness of the model

The (naive) intuitive model of classical physics is replaced by the less intuitive model of the Hilbert space and its subspaces. We discussed this in the previous section. If one is accustomed to classical intuitive thinking, a structure that does not constitute a downsized version of the macroscopic may seem strange. However, there is no reason why microscopic reality should be a miniature version of the macroscopic. In other cases as well (e.g., long-range forces in Newtonian theory, the absence of ether in relativity theory), physics had to abandon intuitiveness. The logical and set-theoretical methodology developed in mathematics allows us to describe a microcosmos that largely eludes intuition.

b) Factual rather than numerical realism

Classical theory is numerically realistic, i.e., a complete description of a system is given by the values of a certain set of numerical quantities. However, numerical realism is only a special case of factual realism. Quantum theory is not a numerically realistic, but (only) a factually realistic theory. Numerical quantities play a different role in it: they represent parameterized sets of factual properties. As such, they *can* have a value, but they do not have to.

c) The theory does not allow for direct positive conclusions; it answers alternatives.

Quantum theory is a “weak” theory, i.e., a theory without the physical “tertium non datur” as a universally valid law. For this reason, it does not allow for direct positive conclusions of the form:

$$B_1 \wedge \dots \wedge B_n \Rightarrow F$$

It only allows for conclusions based on a *contingent* physical “tertium non datur”. Such conclusions have the form:

$$F_1 \vee \dots \vee F_k \Rightarrow [B_1 \wedge \dots \wedge B_n \Rightarrow F_j]$$

The theory thus makes statements about the future not in the form of direct positive predictions, but only by answering alternatives. However, this is irrelevant for practical application. Exactly the same applies to the weak variant of classical theory.

d) Non-Kolmogorov probability

Quantum theory is based on a probability theory other than Kolmogorov’s. Similarly, in the context of general relativity, Euclidean geometry had to be replaced by non-Euclidean geometry. In this case, however, the geometry was already known from other contexts. The general probability theory that is required for a correct formulation of quantum theory, on the other hand, had to be newly developed. This may give the incorrect impression that we are dealing with a special “quantum probability”.

e) No self-identical objects: Physical objects are actually processes.

As in pure field theory, there are no physical objects with self-identical character in quantum theory. Objects, even those of everyday life, are rather to be understood as processes. This contradicts our linguistic habits. The subject-predicate-object structure of our language suggests that first there are objects that exist independently of their properties, and in a second step, certain properties (or actions) are attributed to these objects.

f) Properties cannot be reduced to a small number of elementary properties.

In classical theory, all properties of an object can be derived from a small number of elementary (numerical) properties, namely the location and momentum of the elementary particles it consists of. All other quantities are uniquely determined by these. In quantum theory, even the smallest subsystems are characterized by a large class of (factual) properties, all of which can be regarded as elementary. Although these properties are not completely independent of each other (since the monotonicity and exclusion principles apply to them), none of them can be derived from the others in the sense of being uniquely determined by them. So, we have a much larger number of quasi-independent degrees of freedom here. Physicists with a classical background may regard this as “unphysical” because it contradicts their desire to explain as many phenomena as possible with as few elementary quantities as possible, as can be done, for example, when describing a clockwork mechanism.

g) Finite subjects cannot have complete knowledge of a system.

Unlike in classical theory, in quantum theory a pure probabilistic state, i.e., a state that corresponds to maximum information for a finite subject, is not equivalent to a deterministic state. Thus, from the perspective of such subjects, randomness plays a slightly different role in quantum theory than in classical theory, where a subject can, at least in principle, if not in practice, have complete knowledge of a system.

– Summary –

The sometimes claimed “weirdness” of quantum *theory* (i.e., of the Copenhagen quantum formalism) can all be resolved. This includes the lack of a model of reality, the possible non-existence of a reality that is independent of observations, the problem of measurement, and the fundamental randomness of what happens in the universe.

The alleged philosophical consequences of quantum theory are based solely on the “weirdness” of the Copenhagen formalism. Moreover, the idea that there is no objective reality is not a *consequence* of this formalism, but rather its *premise*, since this formalism dispenses with the consideration of reality from the outset. The presumed philosophical consequences of quantum theory simply do not exist.

Regardless of this, quantum theory has some peculiarities:

- a) a non-intuitive model,
- b) factual realism (instead of numerical realism),
- c) no direct positive conclusions (the theory answers alternatives instead),
- d) non-Kolmogorov probability,
- e) no self-identical objects (as in pure classical field theory),
- f) a large number of quasi-independent degrees of freedom that cannot be reduced to a small number of elementary properties,
- g) by necessity incomplete knowledge of finite subjects, hence a somewhat different role of randomness for these subjects.

The peculiarities mentioned result from the properties of the quantum *world* and the description of this world by a Hilbert space model. Although they contradict certain habits of physical thinking, they do not result in the often-discussed philosophical consequences. Regardless of this, it is of course possible to consider each of these peculiarities as a philosophical problem.

PART B Mathematical Appendix

B0. Basic Definitions

This chapter introduces a number of basic terms and notations that will be used in the following chapters. For some of these, a number of statements have been added that are either generally known or very easy to prove.

In order to achieve sufficient clarity and unambiguity of the argument, it is necessary to develop the theory on a precise logical basis. For this reason, the definitions, statements, and proofs appearing in this mathematical appendix will often be quite “technical”.

Let

- \mathcal{H} := the Hilbert space of the universe,
- \mathcal{U} := $\{ A \mid A < \mathcal{H} \}$
the set of all closed linear subspaces of \mathcal{H} ,
i.e., the set of possible properties of the universe,
- T := the time axis (a subset of \mathbb{R} , which, without loss of generality, contains 0),
- \mathcal{E} := $\mathcal{U} \times T$ (the Cartesian product of \mathcal{U} and T)
the set of possible events (A,t) with $A \in \mathcal{U}$ and $t \in T$,
- Ω_0 := $\wp(\mathcal{E})$ (the power set of \mathcal{E})
the set of possible worlds in the model given by \mathcal{E} ,
- $\langle A,t \rangle_0$:= $\{ \omega \in \Omega_0 \mid (A,t) \in \omega \}$ (for all $A \in \mathcal{U}$ and $t \in T$)
the possible fact that the event (A,t) occurs,
- \mathcal{R}_0 := $\{ \langle A,t \rangle_0 \mid A \in \mathcal{U} \text{ and } t \in T \}$
the set of all such possible facts,
- \mathcal{A}_0 := $\mathcal{A}(\mathcal{R}_0)$ (the smallest σ -algebra that includes \mathcal{R}_0)
the algebra of possible facts in the given model.

The algebra \mathcal{A}_0 consists of all logical combinations of events. Logical operations can be defined on this algebra. For $F, G, F_1, F_2, \dots \in \mathcal{A}_0$ let:

- $F \wedge G$:= $F \cap G$ (logical conjunction)
- $F \vee G$:= $F \cup G$ (logical disjunction)
- $\neg F$:= $\Omega_0 \setminus F$ (negation)
- $F \rightarrow G$:= $\neg F \vee G$ (implication)
- $F \leftrightarrow G$:= $(F \rightarrow G) \wedge (G \rightarrow F)$ (equivalence)
- $\forall_j F_j$:= $\bigcap_j F_j$ (universal quantifier)
- $\exists_j F_j$:= $\bigcup_j F_j$ (existential quantifier)
- $\overset{1}{\exists}_j F_j$:= $\exists_j (F_j \wedge \forall_{i \neq j} \neg F_i)$ (quantifier of unique existence)

These quantifiers can be applied to both finite and infinite sequences.

Based on the definitions given so far, the statements of the following lemma can be easily proven:

L.0.1 For $\omega \in \Omega_0$ and $F, G, F_1, F_2, \dots \in \mathcal{A}_0$, we have:

- (1) $\omega \in (F \wedge G) \Leftrightarrow [\omega \in F \wedge \omega \in G]$
- (2) $\omega \in (F \vee G) \Leftrightarrow [\omega \in F \vee \omega \in G]$
- (3) $\omega \in (\neg F) \Leftrightarrow \neg [\omega \in F]$
- (4) $\omega \in (F \rightarrow G) \Leftrightarrow [\omega \in F \Rightarrow \omega \in G]$
- (5) $\omega \in (F \leftrightarrow G) \Leftrightarrow [\omega \in F \Leftrightarrow \omega \in G]$
- (6) $\omega \in (\forall_j F_j) \Leftrightarrow \forall_j [\omega \in F_j]$
- (7) $\omega \in (\exists_j F_j) \Leftrightarrow \exists_j [\omega \in F_j]$
- (8) $\omega \in (\overset{1}{\exists}_j F_j) \Leftrightarrow \overset{1}{\exists}_j [\omega \in F_j]$

These statements may be applied without explicit reference to the above lemma.

The usual laws apply to the logical operators introduced here; for example, the distributive law holds for possible facts $F, G, H \in \mathcal{A}_0$:

$$F \wedge (G \vee H) = (F \wedge G) \vee (F \wedge H)$$

etc.

The following notations are used:

- $\dim A$:= the dimension of A (for a subspace A of \mathcal{H})
- $[\varphi]$:= the one-dimensional subspace of \mathcal{H} generated by φ (for $\varphi \in \mathcal{H}$)
- $[\varphi_1, \dots, \varphi_n]$:= the subspace of \mathcal{H} generated by the vectors $\varphi_1, \dots, \varphi_n$
(for $\varphi_1, \dots, \varphi_n \in \mathcal{H}$)
- φ^* := the adjoint vector of φ (for $\varphi \in \mathcal{H}$)
- $\langle \varphi, \psi \rangle$:= $\varphi^* \psi$ (the scalar product of φ and ψ , for all $\varphi, \psi \in \mathcal{H}$)
- $|\varphi|$:= $\langle \varphi, \varphi \rangle^{1/2}$ (the norm of φ , for $\varphi \in \mathcal{H}$)
- $A < B$:= $\Leftrightarrow A$ is a closed linear subspace of B (for $A, B \in \mathcal{U}$)
- $a \perp b$:= $\Leftrightarrow a^* b = 0$ (a orthogonal to b , for $a, b \in \mathcal{H}$)
- $A \perp B$:= $\Leftrightarrow \forall_{a \in A} \forall_{b \in B} a \perp b$ (A orthogonal to B , for $A, B < \mathcal{H}$)
- $a \perp B$:= $\Leftrightarrow [a] \perp B$ (a perpendicular to B , for $a \in \mathcal{H}$ and $B < \mathcal{H}$)
- A^\perp := $\{ \varphi \in \mathcal{H} \mid \varphi \perp A \}$ (the orthogonal complement of A in \mathcal{H})
- π_A := the projection operator associated with A (for $A < \mathcal{H}$)

The symbol “ o ” denotes the zero vector in \mathcal{H} , but is also used as an abbreviation for the zero subspace $[o] < \mathcal{H}$ and may as well denote the zero operator on \mathcal{H} . The meaning will always be clear from the context.

A unit vector is a vector $\varphi \in \mathcal{H}$ with $|\varphi| = 1$.

For $a, b \in \mathcal{H}$ with $a \perp b$, we have $|a+b|^2 = |a|^2 + |b|^2$ (Pythagoras).

For every $\varphi \in \mathcal{H}$, we have $\varphi^* \varphi = |\varphi|^2$, and in the case of $|\varphi| = 1$, $\pi_{[\varphi]} = \varphi \varphi^*$.

The sequence (b_k) is an orthonormal basis of \mathcal{H} if it is a vector space basis, each b_k is a unit vector, and any two different b_j and b_k are orthogonal. For example, the standard basis e_1, \dots, e_k of \mathbb{C}^k is an orthonormal basis.

Two subspaces A, B of \mathcal{H} are called commutable if their projection operators π_A and π_B commute with each other, i.e., if $\pi_A \pi_B = \pi_B \pi_A$.

If A is commutable with B , then A is also commutable with B^\perp , and A^\perp is commutable with B^\perp as well.

A sequence (A_j) of subspaces of \mathcal{H} is called “jointly orthogonal” if the A_j are pairwise commutable and $\bigcap_j A_j = 0$. In this case, we write: $\perp_j A_j$.

For subspaces E_1, E_2, \dots of \mathcal{H} , the direct sum is denoted by $\bigoplus_S E_S$. Alternative notations for this are $\bigoplus_{S \in \{1, \dots, n\}} E_S$ or $\bigoplus \{ E_S \mid s \in S \}$. The usual rules apply to the direct sum, e.g.:

$$(A \oplus B)^\perp = A^\perp \cap B^\perp \quad (\text{for } A, B < \mathcal{H})$$

$$\bigoplus_S (E_S)^\perp = (\bigcap_S E_S)^\perp \quad (\text{for } E_1, E_2, \dots < \mathcal{H})$$

and if the E_S are pairwise orthogonal:

$$\pi_{\bigoplus_S E_S} = \sum_S \pi_{E_S}$$

$$\bigoplus_{S \in S} E_S \cap \bigoplus_{S \in S'} E_S = \bigoplus \{ E_S \mid s \in S \wedge s \in S' \}$$

$$\bigoplus_{S \in S} E_S \cup \bigoplus_{S \in S'} E_S = \bigoplus \{ E_S \mid s \in S \vee s \in S' \}$$

Let H be the Hamiltonian on \mathcal{H} . Then let

$$U_t := e^{-itH/\hbar} \quad (\text{for all } t \in T)$$

be the corresponding unitary operator of motion.

With the definitions given so far, the deterministic axioms of quantum theory can now be defined.

The monotonicity principle is defined as:

$$\text{MON} := \{ \langle A, t \rangle_0 \rightarrow \langle B, t \rangle_0 \mid A, B \in \mathcal{U} \wedge t \in T \wedge A < B \}$$

The exclusion principle is defined as:

$$\text{SEC} := \{ \neg (\forall_j \langle A_j, t \rangle_0) \mid A_1, A_2, \dots \in \mathcal{U} \wedge t \in T \wedge \perp_j A_j \}$$

The physical “tertium non datur” is defined as:

$$\text{NEG} := \{ \langle A, t \rangle_0 \vee \langle A^\perp, t \rangle_0 \mid A \in \mathcal{U} \wedge t \in T \}$$

The law of motion (Schrödinger equation) is defined as:

$$\text{SE} := \{ \langle A, 0 \rangle_0 \leftrightarrow \langle U_t A, t \rangle_0 \mid A \in \mathcal{U} \wedge t \in T \}$$

Apparently, MON, SEC, NEG, and SE are subsets of the algebra \mathcal{A}_0 .

Omitting the physical “tertium non datur”, the axiom system of quantum theory is defined as:

$$AX := SE \cup MON \cup SEC$$

Now let

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega &:= \bigcap (AX) \\ &= \{ \omega \in \Omega_0 \mid \forall_{F \in AX} \omega \in F \} \end{aligned}$$

be the set of all possible worlds that satisfy the given axioms, i.e., the set of all *physically* possible worlds.

The axiom system AX defines a possibility operator \diamond_{AX} on the algebra \mathcal{A}_0 :

$$\diamond_{AX}(F) := \Leftrightarrow F \cap \Omega \neq \emptyset \quad (\text{for all } F \in \mathcal{A}_0)$$

Two possible facts $F, G \in \mathcal{A}_0$ are physically equivalent if the following holds:

$$F \cap \Omega = G \cap \Omega$$

In this sense, let

$$\mathcal{A} := \{ F \cap \Omega \mid F \in \mathcal{A}_0 \}$$

be the algebra induced on Ω by \mathcal{A}_0 . Each element of \mathcal{A} corresponds to an equivalence class of elements of \mathcal{A}_0 .

Analogous to the logical operations on \mathcal{A}_0 , logical operations can also be defined on the algebra \mathcal{A} , for example:

$$\begin{aligned} F \wedge G &:= F \cap G \quad (\text{logical conjunction, for } F, G \in \mathcal{A}) \\ \neg F &:= \Omega \setminus F \quad (\text{negation, for } F \in \mathcal{A}) \end{aligned}$$

For the symbol “ \neg ”, a distinction must be made as to whether the expression “ $\neg F$ ” refers to $F \in \mathcal{A}$ or $F \in \mathcal{A}_0$. However, since the meaning will always be clear from the context, there is no risk of confusion.

Let

$$\langle A, t \rangle := \langle A, t \rangle_0 \cap \Omega \quad (\text{for all } A \in \mathcal{U} \text{ and } t \in T)$$

be the possible fact that the event (A, t) occurs (facts that are physically equivalent are not distinguished here)

$$\langle A \rangle := \langle A, 0 \rangle \quad (\text{as an abbreviation, for all } A \in \mathcal{U})$$

$$\langle \varphi \rangle := \langle [\varphi] \rangle \quad (\text{as an abbreviation, for all } \varphi \in \mathcal{H})$$

With

$$\mathcal{R} := \{ \langle A, t \rangle \mid A \in \mathcal{U} \text{ and } t \in T \}$$

\mathcal{A} is the smallest σ -algebra that includes \mathcal{R} . A possibility operator can be defined on \mathcal{A} by the trivial statement

$$\diamond(F) := \Leftrightarrow F \neq \emptyset \quad (\text{for all } F \in \mathcal{A})$$

Let

$$\mathcal{A}^\wedge := \{ \langle A_1 \rangle \wedge \dots \wedge \langle A_n \rangle \mid n \in \mathbb{N} \wedge A_1, \dots, A_n \in \mathcal{U} \}$$

be the set of all finite logical conjunctions of events of the form $\langle A \rangle$ with $A \in \mathcal{U}$. Obviously, \mathcal{A}^\wedge is a subset of \mathcal{A} .

The following laws about the algebra \mathcal{A} can be easily derived:

$$\underline{\text{MON}} \quad A < B \Rightarrow \langle A \rangle \subset \langle B \rangle \quad (\text{for } A, B < \mathcal{H})$$

$$\underline{\text{SEC}} \quad \bigcap_j A_j = 0 \Rightarrow (\forall_j \langle A_j \rangle) = \emptyset \quad (\text{for commutable } A_1, A_2, \dots < \mathcal{H})$$

$$\underline{\text{SE}} \quad \langle A, t \rangle = \langle U_{-t} A \rangle \quad (\text{for } A < \mathcal{H} \text{ and } t \in T)$$

They can be referred to with phrases such as “according to MON”, “because of SEC”, “using the Schrödinger equation”, etc.

If we apply SEC to the sequence $[0], [0], \dots < \mathcal{H}$, we obtain $\langle 0 \rangle = \emptyset$.

By an operator L , we mean a linear mapping from \mathcal{H} to \mathcal{H} :

$$L : \mathcal{H} \rightarrow \mathcal{H}$$

For such an operator L we define:

$$L(\mathcal{H}) \quad := \{ L(\varphi) \mid \varphi \in \mathcal{H} \} \quad (\text{the image of } L)$$

$$\text{rank}(L) \quad := \dim(L(\mathcal{H})) \quad (\text{the rank of } L)$$

$$L^* \quad := \text{the adjoint operator of } L$$

Under the conditions specified in Chapter B5, we can define:

$$\text{tr } L \quad := \text{the trace of an operator } L$$

$$|L| \quad := (\text{tr } LL^*)^{1/2} \quad (\text{the Euclidean norm of } L)$$

The usual calculation rules apply here, e.g.:

$$L = (L^*)^* \quad (\text{for an operator } L)$$

$$\text{tr}(ML) = \text{tr}(LM) \quad (\text{for two operators } L \text{ and } M)$$

L is called self-adjoint if $L^* = L$. An “observable” is such a self-adjoint operator. An operator U is called “unitary” if $U^* = U^{-1}$. An operator W is “non-negative definite” if $\varphi^* W \varphi \geq 0$ for every $\varphi \in \mathcal{H}$. W is a statistical operator if it is non-negative definite and $\text{tr } W = 1$. Two operators L and M are commutable if $LM = ML$. An observable L with a finite spectrum has a spectral representation

$$L = \sum_j \lambda_j \pi_{A_j}$$

with real eigenvalues λ_j and eigenspaces A_j that satisfy the equation

$$\bigoplus_j A_j = \mathcal{H}$$

We refer to the identity operator $I_{\mathcal{H}}$ on the Hilbert space \mathcal{H} as the “unit operator”.

In general, operators are not commutable. Therefore, we write

$$\prod_{j=k..n} L_j$$

for the product

$$L_k \dots L_n$$

in the order specified.

For two Hilbert spaces \mathcal{H}_1 and \mathcal{H}_2 ,

$$\mathcal{H}_1 \otimes \mathcal{H}_2$$

denotes the tensor product of \mathcal{H}_1 and \mathcal{H}_2 .

Let $\mathcal{H} = \mathcal{H}_1 \otimes \mathcal{H}_2$. Then

$a \otimes b$:= the tensor product of a and b (for $a \in \mathcal{H}_1$ and $b \in \mathcal{H}_2$)

$A \otimes B$:= [{ $a \otimes b$ | $a \in A$ and $b \in B$ }] (for $A < \mathcal{H}_1$ and $B < \mathcal{H}_2$)

the subspace of \mathcal{H} generated by the set of all such tensor products $a \otimes b$

If L and M are operators on \mathcal{H}_1 and \mathcal{H}_2 , respectively, then the tensor product defined by

$(L \otimes M)(a \otimes b) := La \otimes Mb$ (for $a \in \mathcal{H}_1$ and $b \in \mathcal{H}_2$)

is an operator $L \otimes M$ on \mathcal{H} .

A tensor factor decomposition of the Hilbert space \mathcal{H} of the universe is an isomorphism

$$f: \mathcal{H} \cong \mathcal{H}_1 \otimes \mathcal{H}_2$$

Two such tensor factor decompositions

$$f: \mathcal{H} \cong \mathcal{H}_1 \otimes \mathcal{H}_2$$

and

$$g: \mathcal{H} \cong \mathcal{H}_3 \otimes \mathcal{H}_4$$

are equivalent if there are isomorphisms

$$r: \mathcal{H}_1 \cong \mathcal{H}_3$$

and

$$s: \mathcal{H}_2 \cong \mathcal{H}_4$$

such that g is the composition of f and $(r \otimes s)$:

$$g = (r \otimes s) \circ f$$

A subsystem Q of \mathcal{H} is an equivalence class of tensor factor decompositions with respect to this equivalence relation. By interchanging the factors in the tensor factor decompositions, we obtain, for each subsystem Q , the complementary subsystem Q^- , which corresponds to the “rest of the world”.

Based on these definitions, each subsystem Q can be assigned a Hilbert space \mathcal{H}_Q such that:

$$\mathcal{H} = \mathcal{H}_Q \otimes \mathcal{H}_{Q^-}$$

I_Q and I_{Q^-} denote the identity operators on \mathcal{H}_Q and \mathcal{H}_{Q^-} , respectively.

For a given subsystem Q , let:

$$\alpha_Q(A') := A' \otimes \mathcal{H}_{Q^-} \quad (\text{for } A' < \mathcal{H}_Q)$$

Thus, each property A' of the subsystem (i.e., each closed linear subspace of \mathcal{H}_Q) is assigned a property of the universe in a canonical way. For an operator L' on \mathcal{H}_Q , the corresponding operator on \mathcal{H} is defined in a similar manner as

$$\alpha_Q(L') := L' \otimes I_{Q^-}$$

If W is an operator on \mathcal{H} and Q is a subsystem, then $\text{tr}_Q[W]$ denotes the partial trace of W on \mathcal{H}_Q . Just as every operator W (with respect to a given orthonormal basis) can be represented by a matrix $(w_{i,j})_{i,j}$ of numbers, every operator W on $\mathcal{H} = \mathcal{H}_Q \otimes \mathcal{H}_{Q^-}$ can be represented

by a matrix of matrices:

$$W = (W_{k,l})_{k,l}$$

This allows the partial traces on \mathcal{H}_Q and \mathcal{H}_{Q^c} to be written as

$$\text{tr}_Q[W] = \sum_k W_{kk}$$

and

$$\text{tr}_{Q^c}[W] = (\text{tr } W_{kl})_{kl}$$

Let Q be a subsystem of the Hilbert space \mathcal{H} and $t \in T$ be a point in time. Furthermore, let

$$\mathcal{G} := ((E_1, t_1), \dots, (E_n, t_n))$$

be a finite sequence of events as a condition. Then let

$$A_j := U_{-t_j} E_j \quad (\text{for } j \in \{1, \dots, n\})$$

$$L := \pi_{A_n} \dots \pi_{A_1}$$

$$W := LL^* / \text{tr } LL^*$$

$$W_t := U_t W U_{-t}$$

The quantum state of Q at time t under condition \mathcal{G} is then defined as

$$W_{Q;t|\mathcal{G}} := \text{tr}_Q[W_t]$$

For every outer measure μ on \mathcal{A} ,

$$\mu(F | G) := \mu(F \wedge G) / \mu(G) \quad (\text{for } F, G \in \mathcal{A} \text{ with } 0 < \mu(G) < \infty)$$

denotes the conditional outer measure. The same applies to a probability measure P .

For any mapping $g : A \rightarrow B$ and a subset A' of A , let

$$g|_{A'} := \text{the restriction of } g \text{ to } A'$$

B1. Axioms of quantum theory and the Kochen-Specker theorem

The aim of this chapter is to show that the axioms specified for quantum theory are logically consistent, that every observable can have at most one value (based on these axioms), and that the addition of the physical “tertium non datur” would lead to a logical contradiction. This chapter consists of the following subsections:

1. The consistency of the axiom system
2. Observables and their values
3. The inconsistency of the physical “tertium non datur”

1. The consistency of the axiom system

The definitions of the axioms MON, SEC, NEG, and SE as subsets of the algebra \mathcal{A}_O of all possible facts, as given in Chapter B0, are adopted here. On this basis, it is shown that the monotonicity principle, the exclusion principle, and Schrödinger’s equation together form a logically consistent axiom system.

The axiom system of quantum theory is formally defined (omitting the physical “tertium non datur”) as

$$AX := SE \cup MON \cup SEC$$

and the corresponding set of physically possible worlds is

$$\Omega := \bigcap (AX)$$

Theorem T.1.1 $\Omega \neq \emptyset$.

Proof: We shall prove here that $\emptyset \in \Omega$. Since $\Omega = \bigcap (AX)$, we must show that $\emptyset \in F$ holds for every $F \in AX = SE \cup MON \cup SEC$. Let us first assume that $F \in SE$. Because of

$$SE = \{ \langle A,0 \rangle_O \leftrightarrow \langle U_t A, t \rangle_O \mid A \in \mathcal{U} \wedge t \in T \}$$

there exist $A \in \mathcal{U}$ and $t \in T$ with

$$F = [\langle A,0 \rangle_O \leftrightarrow \langle U_t A, t \rangle_O]$$

Now

$$\begin{aligned} \emptyset \in F &\Leftrightarrow \emptyset \in [\langle A,0 \rangle_O \leftrightarrow \langle U_t A, t \rangle_O] \\ &\Leftrightarrow [\emptyset \in \langle A,0 \rangle_O \Leftrightarrow \emptyset \in \langle U_t A, t \rangle_O] && \text{(by L.0.1 (5))} \\ &\Leftrightarrow [(A,0) \in \emptyset \Leftrightarrow (U_t A, t) \in \emptyset] && \text{(definition of } \langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_O) \\ &\Leftrightarrow [\text{false} \Leftrightarrow \text{false}] \\ &\Leftrightarrow \text{true} \end{aligned}$$

The cases $F \in MON$ and $F \in SEC$ can be proven in a quite similar way. **QED**

The logical consistency of the axiom system AX follows directly from this theorem.

Note: In the following, the application of Lemma L.0.1 and the definition of $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_O$ will no longer be presented in such detail.

2. Observables and their values

In quantum mechanics, an observable is a self-adjoint linear operator

$$L : \mathcal{H} \rightarrow \mathcal{H}$$

Here, we limit ourselves to discrete observables with at most a countably infinite range of values, i.e., to operators with a discrete spectrum. Such an operator has a spectral representation

$$L = \sum_j \lambda_j \pi_{A_j}$$

Here, λ_j are the different (real) eigenvalues of L and A_j are the corresponding (pairwise orthogonal) eigenspaces with

$$\bigoplus_j A_j = \mathcal{H}$$

In a physically possible world $\omega \in \Omega$, such an observable L has the value λ_j at time $t \in T$ if and only if the universe has the property A_j at time t , i.e., if

$$(A_j, t) \in \omega$$

Theorem T.1.2 An observable L has at most one value in every possible world $\omega \in \Omega$ and at every point in time t .

Proof: Let $\omega \in \Omega$ and $t \in T$. For $j \neq k$, we have $A_j \perp A_k$. Therefore, A_j and A_k are commutable with $A_j \cap A_k = \emptyset$. Because of $\omega \in \Omega = \bigcap (AX) \subset \bigcap (SEC)$, it follows that

$$\omega \in \neg (\langle A_j, t \rangle_{\omega} \wedge \langle A_k, t \rangle_{\omega})$$

Due to L.0.1 and the definition of $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_{\omega}$, this is equivalent to

$$\neg [(A_j, t) \in \omega \wedge (A_k, t) \in \omega]$$

which says that the observable L cannot have the values λ_j and λ_k at the same time. **QED**

3. The inconsistency of the physical “tertium non datur”

With the axioms given in Chapter B0 as subsets of \mathcal{A}_0 , let

$$AX_1 := SE \cup MON \cup SEC \cup NEG$$

and

$$\Omega_1 := \bigcap (AX_1)$$

Here, the physical “tertium non datur” has been added to the axiom system. We now want to prove that this axiom system is logically inconsistent. In order to do this, we will show that Ω_1 is the empty set (see T.1.3 below).

With Ω_1 instead of Ω , we define (only within the scope of this proof and deviating from the definitions given in Chapter B0):

$$\langle A, t \rangle := \langle A, t \rangle_{\omega} \cap \Omega_1 \quad (\text{for } A < \mathcal{H} \text{ and } t \in T)$$

$$\langle A \rangle := \langle A, 0 \rangle \quad (\text{for } A < \mathcal{H})$$

$$\langle \varphi \rangle := \langle [\varphi] \rangle \quad (\text{for } \varphi \in \mathcal{H})$$

Here, $[\varphi]$ is the one-dimensional subspace of \mathcal{H} generated by φ .

The axioms MON, SEC, and NEG directly imply the following statements:

$$\underline{\text{MON1}} \quad A < B \Rightarrow \langle A \rangle \subset \langle B \rangle \quad (\text{for } A, B < \mathcal{H})$$

$$\underline{\text{SEC1}} \quad \bigcap_j A_j = \mathbf{o} \Rightarrow (\forall_j \langle A_j \rangle) = \emptyset \quad (\text{for commutable } A_1, A_2, \dots < \mathcal{H})$$

$$\underline{\text{NEG1}} \quad \Omega_1 \subset \langle A \rangle \vee \langle A^\perp \rangle \quad (\text{for } A < \mathcal{H})$$

Furthermore, we have:

$$\underline{\text{SEC2}} \quad A \perp B \Rightarrow \langle A \rangle \wedge \langle B \rangle = \emptyset \quad (\text{for } A, B < \mathcal{H})$$

Proof: SEC2 follows directly from SEC1 by letting $A_1 := A$ and all other $A_j := B$. **QED**

We also have:

$$\underline{\text{CONJ1}} \quad \langle A \rangle \wedge \langle B \rangle \subset \langle A \cap B \rangle \quad (\text{for commutable } A, B < \mathcal{H})$$

Proof: Because of

$$A \cap B \cap (A \cap B)^\perp = \mathbf{o}$$

we get

$$\langle A \rangle \wedge \langle B \rangle \wedge \langle (A \cap B)^\perp \rangle = \emptyset \quad (\text{using SEC1})$$

and thus

$$\begin{aligned} \langle A \rangle \wedge \langle B \rangle &\subset \neg \langle (A \cap B)^\perp \rangle \\ &\subset \langle A \cap B \rangle \end{aligned} \quad (\text{using NEG1})$$

QED

Note: The operation \neg refers to Ω_1 here, i.e., for subsets $E \subset \Omega_1$, we have:

$$\neg E := \Omega_1 \setminus E$$

L.1.1 For every $\omega \in \Omega_1$ and for every orthonormal basis (b_k) of \mathcal{H} , there is exactly one element b_k of this basis with $\omega \in \langle b_k \rangle$.

Proof: It is

$$\begin{aligned} \bigcap_k [b_k]^\perp &= (\oplus_k [b_k])^\perp \\ &= \mathcal{H}^\perp \\ &= \mathbf{o} \end{aligned}$$

Using SEC1, we get

$$(\forall_k \langle [b_k]^\perp \rangle) = \emptyset$$

Because of NEG1, for all k

$$\langle \neg \langle b_k \rangle \rangle \subset \langle [b_k]^\perp \rangle$$

From this we obtain

$$(\forall_k \langle \neg \langle b_k \rangle \rangle) = \emptyset$$

It now follows that

$$\begin{aligned}\Omega_1 &= \neg\emptyset \\ &= \neg\forall_k(\neg\langle b_k \rangle) \\ &= \exists_k\langle b_k \rangle\end{aligned}$$

Thus, for every $\omega \in \Omega_1$, there is an index k with $\omega \in \langle b_k \rangle$. If there were several such k , i.e., if there were $j \neq k$ with $\omega \in \langle b_j \rangle$ and $\omega \in \langle b_k \rangle$, then $[b_j] \perp [b_k]$, and due to SEC2 it would follow that

$$\langle [b_j] \rangle \wedge \langle [b_k] \rangle = \emptyset$$

which contradicts $\omega \in \langle b_j \rangle$ and $\omega \in \langle b_k \rangle$. **QED**

We can now prove the inconsistency of the axiom system AX_1 .

Theorem T.1.3 In the case of $\dim \mathcal{H} \geq 4$, we have $\Omega_1 = \emptyset$.

Proof: We assume that Ω_1 is not empty and show that this leads to a contradiction. Let ω be a fixed element of Ω_1 . Now let (a_j) be any orthonormal basis of \mathcal{H} . According to L.1.1, there is an element a_k such that $\omega \in \langle a_k \rangle$. Without loss of generality, we can assume that $k = 1$. We let

$$A := [a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4]$$

Then A is a four-dimensional subspace of \mathcal{H} with $\omega \in \langle A \rangle$. We can now further assume without loss of generality that $A = \mathbb{C}^4$.

Every orthonormal basis (b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4) of A can be extended to an orthonormal basis of \mathcal{H} , namely to

$$(b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4, a_5, a_6, a_7, \dots)$$

According to L.1.1, there is an element b in this basis such that ω lies in $\langle b \rangle$. Since $\omega \in \langle a_1 \rangle$ and a_1 is perpendicular to all a_5, a_6, a_7 , etc., b cannot belong to these elements due to SEC2. Therefore, b is one of the elements b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4 . Thus, for every orthonormal basis of A , there is an element b of that basis with $\omega \in \langle b \rangle$, and because of SEC2, exactly *one* such element. If we now assign each vector $\varphi \in A = \mathbb{C}^4$ a color, black or white, such that φ is assigned the color “white” if and only if $\omega \in \langle \varphi \rangle$, then every orthonormal basis of A contains exactly one white element.

Now, in [1] we find a list of nine orthonormal bases of \mathbb{C}^4 , which are composed of 18 different vectors in such a way that each vector occurs exactly twice in these bases.

From this, with the coloring defined above, we obtain the following: The number of occurrences of a white vector in the nine orthonormal bases is equal to nine, because there is exactly one white vector in each of these bases. On the other hand, this number is even because each of the 18 vectors occurs exactly twice. That is a contradiction. **QED**

For the case of $\dim \mathcal{H} \geq 4$, the axiom system

$$\text{AX}_1 := \text{SE} \cup \text{MON} \cup \text{SEC} \cup \text{NEG}$$

is thus proven to be inconsistent.

Theorem T.1.3 is closely related to the well-known Kochen-Specker no-go theorem and can be regarded as a variant of this theorem.

B2. Classical mechanics

The aim of this chapter is to show that the axiom system comprising the monotonicity principle, the exclusion principle, the physical “tertium non datur”, and the law of motion corresponds to normal classical mechanics; that the empirical content of the theory does not change if the physical “tertium non datur” is omitted; and how the probabilistic state can be defined in the case of classical mechanics. (The definitions given in Chapter B0 for quantum theory do not apply here.)

The chapter consists of the following subsections:

1. Representation of classical mechanics by an axiom system
2. The empirical content of the strong and weak classical theories
3. Definition of probabilistic states in classical mechanics

1. Representation of classical mechanics by an axiom system

In this section, the axioms of classical mechanics are defined as subsets of the algebra of all possible facts as given by the model. It is then shown that normal classical mechanics is equivalent to the axiom system comprising the monotonicity principle, the exclusion principle, the physical “tertium non datur”, and the law of motion.

Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 Z &:= (\mathbb{R}^3 \times \mathbb{R}^3)^N \\
 &= \mathbb{R}^{6N} && \text{be the phase space of an } N\text{-particle system,} \\
 \mathcal{U} &:= \mathcal{B}(Z) && \text{the Borel algebra on } Z \text{ (the set of possible properties of the universe),} \\
 \mathcal{E} &:= \mathcal{U} \times T && \text{the set of possible events,} \\
 \Omega_0 &:= \wp(\mathcal{E}) && \text{the set of possible worlds as given by the model,} \\
 \langle A, t \rangle_0 &:= \{ \omega \in \Omega_0 \mid (A, t) \in \omega \} \\
 &&& \text{the possible fact that } (A, t) \text{ occurs (for all } A \in \mathcal{U} \text{ and } t \in T \text{).}
 \end{aligned}$$

Let \mathcal{A}_0 be the smallest σ -algebra on Ω_0 that contains all such $\langle A, t \rangle_0$. Then \mathcal{A}_0 is the algebra of all possible facts as given by the model. On this algebra we can define logical operations in the same way as before (see Chapter B0). Let β_t be the mapping from Z to Z that describes the law of motion. If $z \in Z$ is the state at time 0, then $\beta_t(z)$ is the state at time t .

With the definition

$$\beta_t A := \{ \beta_t(z) \mid z \in A \} \quad (\text{for all } A \in \mathcal{U} \text{ and } t \in T)$$

let:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{MON} &:= \{ \langle A, t \rangle_0 \rightarrow \langle B, t \rangle_0 \mid A, B \in \mathcal{U} \wedge t \in T \wedge A \subset B \} \\
 \text{SEC} &:= \{ \neg(\forall_j \langle A_j, t \rangle_0) \mid A_1, A_2, \dots \in \mathcal{U} \wedge t \in T \wedge \bigcap_j A_j = \emptyset \} \\
 \text{NEG} &:= \{ \langle A, t \rangle_0 \vee \langle Z \setminus A, t \rangle_0 \mid A \in \mathcal{U} \wedge t \in T \} \\
 \text{LM} &:= \{ \langle A, 0 \rangle_0 \leftrightarrow \langle \beta_t A, t \rangle_0 \mid A \in \mathcal{U} \wedge t \in T \}
 \end{aligned}$$

MON is the monotonicity principle, SEC is the exclusion principle, NEG is the physical “tertium non datur” and LM is the law of motion, each described as a subset of the algebra of possible facts. The entire axiom system is defined as

$$AX := LM \cup MON \cup SEC \cup NEG$$

We then have $AX \subset \mathcal{A}_0$. Now let

$$\Omega_{AX} := \bigcap (AX)$$

be the set of all possible worlds that comply with the axiom system AX.

We now define “normal” classical mechanics. A path is understood to be a mapping p from the time axis into phase space. The set of all these paths is

$$\mathcal{P} := \{ p \mid p : T \rightarrow Z \}$$

Each path $p \in \mathcal{P}$ can be assigned a possible world $\omega_p \in \Omega_0$ in a canonical way by

$$\omega_p := \{ (A,t) \in \mathcal{E} \mid p(t) \in A \}$$

Within the set of paths, we can distinguish those that obey the law of motion:

$$\mathcal{P}_\beta := \{ p \in \mathcal{P} \mid \forall t \in T \ p(t) = \beta_t(p(0)) \}$$

By this we can define the set of physically possible worlds in “normal” classical mechanics:

$$\Omega := \{ \omega_p \mid p \in \mathcal{P}_\beta \}$$

We can now prove:

$$\Omega = \Omega_{AX} \quad (\text{see T.2.1 below})$$

This will show the equivalence of the classical path concept with the theory specified by the axiom system AX.

For $\omega \in \Omega_0$ and $F, G \in \mathcal{A}_0$ (or $F_1, F_2, \dots \in \mathcal{A}_0$), the following lemmas are easy to prove:

$$\underline{\text{L.2.1}} \quad \omega \in (F \wedge G) \Leftrightarrow [\omega \in F \wedge \omega \in G]$$

$$\underline{\text{L.2.2}} \quad \omega \in (F \vee G) \Leftrightarrow [\omega \in F \vee \omega \in G]$$

$$\underline{\text{L.2.3}} \quad \omega \in (\neg F) \Leftrightarrow \neg [\omega \in F]$$

$$\underline{\text{L.2.4}} \quad \omega \in (F \rightarrow G) \Leftrightarrow [\omega \in F \Rightarrow \omega \in G]$$

$$\underline{\text{L.2.5}} \quad \omega \in (F \leftrightarrow G) \Leftrightarrow [\omega \in F \Leftrightarrow \omega \in G]$$

$$\underline{\text{L.2.6}} \quad \omega \in (\forall_j F_j) \Leftrightarrow \forall_j [\omega \in F_j]$$

For $\omega \in \Omega_{AX}$; $A, B \in \mathcal{U}$; $A_1, A_2, \dots \in \mathcal{U}$; and $t \in T$, the following lemmas hold:

$$\underline{\text{L.2.7}} \quad A \cap B = \emptyset \Rightarrow \neg [\omega \in \langle A, t \rangle_0 \wedge \omega \in \langle B, t \rangle_0]$$

Proof: Let $A_1 := A$ and $A_j := B$ for all $j \neq 1$. Then use $\forall_{F \in \text{SEC}} (\omega \in F)$. **QED**

$$\underline{\text{L.2.8}} \quad Z = \bigcup_j A_j \Rightarrow \exists_j [\omega \in \langle A_j, t \rangle_0]$$

Proof: If there were no such j under the given premise, we would have (for all j):

$$\omega \notin \langle A_j, t \rangle_0$$

Because of $\forall_{F \in \text{NEG}} (\omega \in F)$, we have (for all j):

$$\omega \in (\langle A_j, t \rangle_0 \vee \langle Z \setminus A_j, t \rangle_0)$$

Using L.2.2, we then get (for all j)

$$\omega \in \langle Z \setminus A_j, t \rangle_0$$

and from this, using L.2.6:

$$\omega \in (\forall j \langle Z \setminus A_j, t \rangle_0)$$

However, because of

$$\begin{aligned} \bigcap_j (Z \setminus A_j) &= Z \setminus \bigcup_j A_j \\ &= Z \setminus Z \\ &= \emptyset \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\forall_{F \in \text{SEC}} \omega \in F$$

it follows that

$$\omega \in \neg(\forall j \langle Z \setminus A_j, t \rangle_0)$$

This is a contradiction. **QED**

L.2.9 ($Z = \bigcup_j A_j$ and A_j pairwise disjoint) $\Rightarrow \exists^1_j [\omega \in \langle A_j, t \rangle_0]$

Proof: L.2.9 follows directly from L.2.8 and L.2.7. **QED**

Theorem T.2.1 $\Omega = \Omega_{AX}$

Proof: First, we must show that $\Omega \subset \Omega_{AX}$. Because of

$$\Omega = \{ \omega_p \mid p \in \mathcal{P}_\beta \}$$

it suffices to show that for all $p \in \mathcal{P}_\beta$, we have $\omega_p \in \Omega_{AX}$. So let $p \in \mathcal{P}_\beta$.

Now, for every $A \in \mathcal{U}$ and $t \in T$:

$$p(0) \in A \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad \beta_t(p(0)) \in \beta_t(A) \quad (\text{since } \beta_t \text{ is bijective})$$

$$\Leftrightarrow p(t) \in \beta_t(A) \quad (\text{since } p \in \mathcal{P}_\beta)$$

$$(A, 0) \in \omega_p \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad (\beta_t(A), t) \in \omega_p \quad (\text{definition of } \omega_p)$$

$$\omega_p \in \langle A, 0 \rangle_0 \Leftrightarrow \omega_p \in \langle \beta_t(A), t \rangle_0 \quad (\text{definition of } \langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_0)$$

$$\omega_p \in (\langle A, 0 \rangle_0 \leftrightarrow \langle \beta_t(A), t \rangle_0) \quad (\text{L.2.5})$$

Because A and t can be chosen arbitrarily, it follows that:

$$(01) \quad \forall_{F \in \text{LM}} [\omega_p \in F]$$

For any $A, B \in \mathcal{U}$ with $A \subset B$ and $t \in T$:

$$p(t) \in A \quad \Rightarrow \quad p(t) \in B$$

$$(A, t) \in \omega_p \quad \Rightarrow \quad (B, t) \in \omega_p \quad (\text{definition of } \omega_p)$$

$$\omega_p \in \langle A, t \rangle_0 \Rightarrow \omega_p \in \langle B, t \rangle_0 \quad (\text{definition of } \langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_0)$$

$$\omega_p \in (\langle A, t \rangle_0 \rightarrow \langle B, t \rangle_0) \quad (\text{L.2.4})$$

Since A , B , and t can be chosen arbitrarily (with $A \subset B$), it follows that:

$$(02) \quad \forall_{F \in \text{MON}} [\omega_p \in F]$$

For any $A_j \in \mathcal{U}$ with $\bigcap_j A_j = \emptyset$ and $t \in T$:

$$\begin{aligned} p(t) &\notin \bigcap_j A_j \\ \neg \forall_j [p(t) \in A_j] \\ \neg \forall_j [(A_j, t) \in \omega_p] &\quad (\text{definition of } \omega_p) \\ \neg \forall_j [\omega_p \in \langle A_j, t \rangle_0] &\quad (\text{definition of } \langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_0) \\ \omega_p \in \neg(\forall_j \langle A_j, t \rangle_0) &\quad (\text{L.2.3 and L.2.6}) \end{aligned}$$

Since A_j and t can be chosen arbitrarily (with $\bigcap_j A_j = \emptyset$), it follows that:

$$(03) \quad \forall_{F \in \text{SEC}} [\omega_p \in F]$$

For any $A \in \mathcal{U}$ and $t \in T$:

$$\begin{aligned} p(t) \in A \vee p(t) \in Z \setminus A \\ (A, t) \in \omega_p \vee (Z \setminus A, t) \in \omega_p &\quad (\text{definition of } \omega_p) \\ \omega_p \in \langle A, t \rangle_0 \vee \omega_p \in \langle Z \setminus A, t \rangle_0 &\quad (\text{definition of } \langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_0) \\ \omega_p \in (\langle A, t \rangle_0 \vee \langle Z \setminus A, t \rangle_0) &\quad (\text{L.2.2}) \end{aligned}$$

Since A and t can be chosen arbitrarily, it follows that:

$$(04) \quad \forall_{F \in \text{NEG}} [\omega_p \in F]$$

From (01) to (04), we immediately obtain

$$(05) \quad \forall_{F \in \text{AX}} [\omega_p \in F]$$

and thus

$$\omega_p \in \Omega_{\text{AX}} \quad \text{QED } (\Omega \subset \Omega_{\text{AX}})$$

It now remains to be proven that $\Omega_{\text{AX}} \subset \Omega$. So let $\omega \in \Omega_{\text{AX}}$ be chosen arbitrarily. We then have to show that $\omega \in \Omega$. For every $M \in \mathbb{N}$ and $k \in \mathbb{Z}$, we define the half-open real interval

$$I_{M;k} := ((k-1) \cdot 2^{-M}, k \cdot 2^{-M}]$$

It then follows that

$$\mathbb{R} = \bigcup_{k \in \mathbb{Z}} I_{M;k} \quad (\text{for all } M)$$

For indices $k_1, \dots, k_{6N} \in \mathbb{Z}$, we define the Cartesian product

$$I_{M;k_1, \dots, k_{6N}} := I_{M;k_1} \times \dots \times I_{M;k_{6N}}$$

By this, for each M , the phase space Z is represented as a disjoint union of cube-shaped sets:

$$Z = \bigcup_{k_1 \in \mathbb{Z}} \dots \bigcup_{k_{6N} \in \mathbb{Z}} I_{M;k_1, \dots, k_{6N}}$$

If we define the index range

$$\text{IND} := \mathbb{Z}^{6N}$$

and abbreviate a $6N$ -tuple (k_1, \dots, k_{6N}) as \mathbf{k} , we can also write:

$$Z = \bigcup_{\mathbf{k} \in \text{IND}} I_{M;\mathbf{k}}$$

Using L.2.9, we can now conclude:

$$\forall_{M \in \mathbb{N}} \exists \mathbf{k} \in \text{IND} [\omega \in \langle I_{M;\mathbf{k}}, 0 \rangle_0]$$

If we denote the respective element $\mathbf{k} \in \text{IND}$ as \mathbf{k}_M , we can define

$$I_M := I_M; \mathbf{k}_M$$

This gives us

$$\forall M \in \mathbb{N} [\omega \in \langle I_M, 0 \rangle_0]$$

and by L.2.6,

$$\omega \in (\forall M \langle I_M, 0 \rangle_0)$$

Because of $\forall F \in \text{SEC } \omega \in F$ and L.2.3, with

$$I := \bigcap_M I_M$$

we obtain

$$I \neq \emptyset$$

However, the set I can contain at most one element, since for $z, z' \in I$, we have for all M :

$$z, z' \in I_M$$

Because I_M is a $6N$ -dimensional cube with an edge length of 2^{-M} , we obtain according to the Pythagorean theorem:

$$|z - z'|^2 \leq 6N (2^{-M})^2$$

Since this holds for all M , $z = z'$ must be true.

We thus have $I = \{z_0\}$ for one specific element $z_0 \in Z$. Now let

$$p(t) := \beta_t(z_0) \quad (\text{for all } t \in T)$$

Since $\beta_0 = \text{id}$, it is clear that $p \in \mathcal{P}_\beta$ and thus $\omega_p \in \Omega$. It remains to be shown that $\omega = \omega_p$, which implies $\omega \in \Omega$ as desired.

We start by proving the following statement: For all $B \in \mathcal{U}$,

$$(06) \quad \omega \in \langle B, 0 \rangle_0 \Leftrightarrow p(0) \in B$$

To prove this equivalence, let us first assume that $p(0) \in B$. Because of

$$\begin{aligned} \bigcap_M I_M &= I \\ &= \{p(0)\} \end{aligned}$$

we then have

$$(Z \setminus B) \cap \bigcap_M I_M = \emptyset$$

Due to $\forall F \in \text{SEC } \omega \in F$, it follows that

$$\omega \in \neg (\langle Z \setminus B, 0 \rangle_0 \wedge \forall M \langle I_M, 0 \rangle_0)$$

and by L.2.3, L.2.1, and L.2.6, we obtain

$$\neg (\omega \in \langle Z \setminus B, 0 \rangle_0 \wedge \forall M [\omega \in \langle I_M, 0 \rangle_0])$$

Since for all M ,

$$\omega \in \langle I_M, 0 \rangle_0$$

it follows that

$$\omega \notin \langle Z \setminus B, 0 \rangle_0$$

Because of $\forall_{F \in \text{NEG}} \omega \in F$, we obtain (using L.2.2)

$$\omega \in \langle B, 0 \rangle_0 \quad \text{QED (“\Leftarrow”)}$$

Now let $p(0) \notin B$. Then $p(0) \in Z \setminus B$, and according to what has just been proven, we obtain (by replacing B with $Z \setminus B$)

$$\omega \in \langle Z \setminus B, 0 \rangle_0$$

By means of L.2.7, it immediately follows that

$$\omega \notin \langle B, 0 \rangle_0 \quad \text{QED (“\Rightarrow”)}$$

This proves statement (06).

QED (06)

Let $A \in \mathcal{U}$ and $t \in T$. Let $B := (\beta_t)^{-1}(A)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} (A, t) \in \omega &\Leftrightarrow \omega \in \langle A, t \rangle_0 && \text{(definition of } \langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_0) \\ &\Leftrightarrow \omega \in \langle \beta_t(B), t \rangle_0 && \text{(definition of } B) \\ &\Leftrightarrow \omega \in \langle B, 0 \rangle_0 && \text{(by L.2.5, since } \forall_{F \in \text{LM}} \omega \in F) \\ &\Leftrightarrow p(0) \in B && \text{(according to (06))} \\ &\Leftrightarrow \beta_t(p(0)) \in \beta_t(B) && \text{(since } \beta_t \text{ is bijective)} \\ &\Leftrightarrow p(t) \in A && \text{(} p \in \mathcal{P}_\beta \text{ and definition of } B) \\ &\Leftrightarrow (A, t) \in \omega_p && \text{(definition of } \omega_p) \end{aligned}$$

Since this holds for all A and t , it follows that $\omega = \omega_p$. The proof of Theorem T.2.1 is thus complete. QED

In classical theory, the general deterministic state space Z^* is defined as the set of all mappings $z^* : \mathcal{U} \rightarrow \{\text{true}, \text{false}\}$ which satisfy the monotonicity principle, the exclusion principle, and the physical “tertium non datur”. Here, \mathcal{U} is the algebra of all (Borel) measurable subsets of the phase space Z .

For each element z of Z , let $z^* : \mathcal{U} \rightarrow \{\text{true}, \text{false}\}$ be defined by:

$$(+) (z^*(A) = \text{true}) :\Leftrightarrow z \in A \quad (\text{for all } A \in \mathcal{U})$$

It is easy to prove that z^* satisfies the principles of monotonicity and exclusion as well as the physical “tertium non datur”, so z^* belongs to Z^* . Let F be the mapping from Z to Z^* which maps every z to z^* as defined by (+). Obviously, F is an injective mapping.

In order to prove that F is also surjective, choose $z^* \in Z^*$. Since Z , Z^* , and F do not depend on T , we can assume, without loss of generality, that $T = \{0\}$. Now let

$$\omega := \{ (A, 0) \mid z^*(A) = \text{true} \}$$

Because z^* satisfies the principles mentioned above, ω belongs to Ω_{AX} . Due to T.2.1, we have $\Omega_{\text{AX}} = \Omega$, and so there is a path $p \in \mathcal{P}$ with $\omega = \omega_p$. With $z := p(0)$, it is easy to show that $z^* = F(z)$. Thus, F is a bijective mapping from Z to Z^* , and we get:

Theorem T.2.2 There is a one-to-one relationship between the phase space Z and the deterministic state space Z^* .

2. The empirical content of the strong and weak classical theories

Based on Ω , a possibility operator on \mathcal{A}_0 can be defined by

$$\diamond_{AX}(A) := \Leftrightarrow \Omega_{AX} \cap A \neq \emptyset$$

The empirical content of the theory (in the sense of Karl Popper) is defined to be the set of possible empirical materials that are physically impossible in the theory given by AX. A (possible) empirical material is a finite set of possible events. Therefore, the set of all possible empirical materials is:

$$\mathcal{M} := \{ \mathcal{B} \mid \mathcal{B} \subset \mathcal{E} \text{ and } \mathcal{B} \text{ is finite} \}$$

For an empirical material

$$\mathcal{B} = \{(A_1, t_1), \dots, (A_k, t_k)\}$$

we define the corresponding possible fact

$$F_{\mathcal{B}} := \langle A_1, t_1 \rangle_0 \wedge \dots \wedge \langle A_k, t_k \rangle_0$$

as an element of \mathcal{A}_0 . $F_{\mathcal{B}}$ is the logical conjunction of the events that belong to \mathcal{B} . With this we can define

$$\text{EMP}_{AX} := \{ \mathcal{B} \in \mathcal{M} \mid \neg \diamond_{AX}(F_{\mathcal{B}}) \}$$

to be the empirical content of the theory given by AX.

Now let

$$AX' := LM \cup MON \cup SEC$$

The axiom system AX' (in which the axiom NEG has been omitted) defines the weak classical theory. The terms $\Omega_{AX'}$ and $\diamond_{AX'}$ as well as $\text{EMP}_{AX'}$ can be defined for this theory in a way analogous to Ω_{AX} , \diamond_{AX} , and EMP_{AX} . In order to show that the empirical content of both theories coincide, we have to prove the following equation:

$$\text{EMP}_{AX'} = \text{EMP}_{AX} \quad (\text{see T.2.3 below})$$

L.2.10 For all $F \in \mathcal{A}_0$:

$$\diamond_{AX}(F) \Rightarrow \diamond_{AX'}(F)$$

Proof: Because of $AX' \subset AX$, we have $\Omega_{AX} \subset \Omega_{AX'}$. For $F \in \mathcal{A}_0$ it follows that:

$$\begin{aligned} \diamond_{AX}(F) &\Rightarrow F \cap \Omega_{AX} \neq \emptyset \\ &\Rightarrow F \cap \Omega_{AX'} \neq \emptyset \\ &\Rightarrow \diamond_{AX'}(F) \end{aligned}$$

QED

L.2.11 For any $(A_1, t_1), \dots, (A_n, t_n) \in \mathcal{E}$:

$$\diamond_{AX'}(\forall_j \langle A_j, t_j \rangle_0) \Rightarrow \diamond_{AX}(\forall_j \langle A_j, t_j \rangle_0)$$

Proof: For all j , let $B_j := (\beta_{t_j})^{-1}(A_j)$. Then:

$$\begin{aligned} \diamond_{AX'}(\forall_j \langle A_j, t_j \rangle_0) &\Rightarrow \exists \omega \in \Omega_{AX'} [\omega \in (\forall_j \langle A_j, t_j \rangle_0)] && \text{(definition of } \diamond_{AX'}) \\ &\Rightarrow \exists \omega \in \Omega_{AX'} \forall_j [\omega \in \langle A_j, t_j \rangle_0] && \text{(using L.2.6)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\Rightarrow \exists \omega \in \Omega_{AX'} \forall_j [\omega \in \langle \beta_{t_j}(B_j), t_j \rangle_0] && \text{(definition of } B_j) \\
 &\Rightarrow \exists \omega \in \Omega_{AX'} \forall_j [\omega \in \langle B_j, 0 \rangle_0] && \text{(by L.2.5, since } \omega \in \Omega_{AX'} \\
 & && \text{implies } \forall_{F \in LM} \omega \in F) \\
 &\Rightarrow \exists \omega \in \Omega_{AX'} [\omega \in (\forall_j \langle B_j, 0 \rangle_0)] && \text{(using L.2.6)} \\
 &\Rightarrow \bigcap_j (B_j) \neq \emptyset
 \end{aligned}$$

because if $\bigcap_j (B_j) = \emptyset$ were true, then we would have (for all $\omega \in \Omega_{AX'}$):

$$\begin{aligned}
 \omega &\in \neg (\forall_j \langle B_j, 0 \rangle_0) && \text{(since } \forall_{F \in SEC} \omega \in F) \\
 \omega &\notin (\forall_j \langle B_j, 0 \rangle_0) && \text{(using L.2.3)}
 \end{aligned}$$

Let z be any element of $\bigcap_j (B_j)$, and let

$$\omega := \{ (A, t) \in \mathcal{E} \mid z \in (\beta_t)^{-1}(A) \}$$

First, we want to show that $\omega \in \Omega_{AX}$.

For any $A \in \mathcal{U}$ and $t \in T$:

$$\begin{aligned}
 z \in (\beta_0)^{-1}(A) &\Leftrightarrow z \in (\beta_t)^{-1}(\beta_t(A)) && \text{(since } \beta_0 = \text{id)} \\
 (A, 0) \in \omega &\Leftrightarrow (\beta_t(A), t) \in \omega && \text{(definition of } \omega) \\
 \omega \in \langle A, 0 \rangle_0 &\Leftrightarrow \omega \in \langle \beta_t(A), t \rangle_0 && \text{(definition of } \langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_0) \\
 \omega \in (\langle A, 0 \rangle_0 \leftrightarrow \langle \beta_t(A), t \rangle_0) &&& \text{(using L.2.5)}
 \end{aligned}$$

Since this holds for any A and t , it follows that:

$$(07) \quad \forall_{F \in LM} [\omega \in F]$$

For any $A, B \in \mathcal{U}$ with $A \subset B$ and $t \in T$:

$$\begin{aligned}
 z \in (\beta_t)^{-1}(A) &\Rightarrow z \in (\beta_t)^{-1}(B) && \text{(since } \beta_t \text{ is bijective)} \\
 (A, t) \in \omega &\Rightarrow (B, t) \in \omega && \text{(definition of } \omega) \\
 \omega \in \langle A, t \rangle_0 &\Rightarrow \omega \in \langle B, t \rangle_0 && \text{(definition of } \langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_0) \\
 \omega \in (\langle A, t \rangle_0 \rightarrow \langle B, t \rangle_0) &&& \text{(using L.2.4)}
 \end{aligned}$$

Since this holds for any A, B , and t (with $A \subset B$), it follows that:

$$(08) \quad \forall_{F \in MON} [\omega \in F]$$

For any $E_1, E_2, \dots \in \mathcal{U}$ with $\bigcap_k E_k = \emptyset$ and $t \in T$:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \bigcap_k (\beta_t)^{-1}(E_k) &= \emptyset && \text{(since } \beta_t \text{ is bijective)} \\
 z &\notin \bigcap_k (\beta_t)^{-1}(E_k) \\
 \neg \forall_k [z \in (\beta_t)^{-1}(E_k)] \\
 \neg \forall_k [(E_k, t) \in \omega] &&& \text{(definition of } \omega) \\
 \neg \forall_k [\omega \in \langle E_k, t \rangle_0] &&& \text{(definition of } \langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_0) \\
 \neg [\omega \in (\forall_k \langle E_k, t \rangle_0)] &&& \text{(using L.2.6)} \\
 \omega &\in \neg (\forall_k \langle E_k, t \rangle_0) && \text{(using L.2.3)}
 \end{aligned}$$

Since this holds for any E_k and t (with $\bigcap_k E_k = \emptyset$), it follows that:

$$(09) \quad \forall_{F \in \text{SEC}} [\omega \in F]$$

For any $A \in \mathcal{U}$ and $t \in T$:

$$\begin{aligned} z \in (\beta_t)^{-1}(A) \vee z \in (\beta_t)^{-1}(Z \setminus A) & \quad (\text{since } \beta_t \text{ is bijective}) \\ (A, t) \in \omega \vee (Z \setminus A, t) \in \omega & \quad (\text{definition of } \omega) \\ \omega \in \langle A, t \rangle_0 \vee \omega \in \langle Z \setminus A, t \rangle_0 & \quad (\text{definition of } \langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_0) \\ \omega \in (\langle A, t \rangle_0 \vee \langle Z \setminus A, t \rangle_0) & \quad (\text{using L.2.2}) \end{aligned}$$

Since this holds for any A and t , it follows that:

$$(10) \quad \forall_{F \in \text{NEG}} [\omega \in F]$$

From (07) to (10), we immediately obtain

$$(11) \quad \forall_{F \in \text{AX}} [\omega \in F]$$

and thus $\omega \in \Omega_{\text{AX}}$.

QED ($\omega \in \Omega_{\text{AX}}$)

Now, for all j :

$$\begin{aligned} z \in B_j & \\ z \in (\beta_{t_j})^{-1}(A_j) & \quad (\text{definition of } B_j) \\ (A_j, t_j) \in \omega & \quad (\text{definition of } \omega) \\ \omega \in \langle A_j, t_j \rangle_0 & \quad (\text{definition of } \langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_0) \end{aligned}$$

Thus, due to L.2.6,

$$\omega \in (\forall_j \langle A_j, t_j \rangle_0)$$

It follows that

$$\exists_{\omega \in \Omega_{\text{AX}}} [\omega \in (\forall_j \langle A_j, t_j \rangle_0)]$$

and thus

$$\diamond_{\text{AX}}(\forall_j \langle A_j, t_j \rangle_0)$$

QED

Theorem T.2.3 It is

$$\text{EMP}_{\text{AX}'} = \text{EMP}_{\text{AX}}$$

Proof: Let $\mathcal{B} \in \mathcal{M}$ be an empirical material. Based on the definition of EMP_{AX} , we have

$$\mathcal{B} \in \text{EMP}_{\text{AX}} \Leftrightarrow \neg \diamond_{\text{AX}}(F_{\mathcal{B}})$$

and the analogous statement for AX' . \mathcal{B} can be represented as

$$\mathcal{B} = \{(A_1, t_1), \dots, (A_k, t_k)\}$$

with $A_j \in \mathcal{U}$ and $t_j \in T$ for all j . It follows that:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{B} \in \text{EMP}_{\text{AX}'} & \Leftrightarrow \neg \diamond_{\text{AX}'}(F_{\mathcal{B}}) \\ & \Leftrightarrow \neg \diamond_{\text{AX}'}(\langle A_1, t_1 \rangle_0 \wedge \dots \wedge \langle A_k, t_k \rangle_0) \\ & \Leftrightarrow \neg \diamond_{\text{AX}'}(\forall_j \langle A_j, t_j \rangle_0) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\Leftrightarrow \neg \diamond_{AX}(\forall_j \langle A_j, t_j \rangle_o) \quad (\text{by L.2.10 and L.2.11}) \\
 &\Leftrightarrow \neg \diamond_{AX}(\langle A_1, t_1 \rangle_o \wedge \dots \wedge \langle A_k, t_k \rangle_o) \\
 &\Leftrightarrow \neg \diamond_{AX}(F_{\mathcal{B}}) \\
 &\Leftrightarrow \mathcal{B} \in \text{EMP}_{AX}
 \end{aligned}$$

Since this applies to all $\mathcal{B} \in \mathcal{M}$, the assertion of the theorem follows. **QED**

3. Definition of probabilistic states in classical mechanics

Analogous to the approach in quantum theory, a conditional “probabilistic state” can also be defined in classical mechanics for every subsystem Q of the universe, for every point in time, and for every sequence of events as a condition. In this case, a subsystem is a Cartesian factor of phase space. Projection operators are replaced by indicator functions, and the Schrödinger equation is replaced by the classical law of motion. The trace of an operator is replaced by the integral over the phase space of the universe, and the partial trace on Q is replaced by the integration over the phase space of the complementary subsystem Q^- . The probabilistic state defined in this way is a probability density on the phase space of Q and thus corresponds to a probability measure. As in the case of quantum theory, conditional probabilities can be calculated on this basis.

Formally, the conditional probabilistic states in classical mechanics are defined as follows:

For $(E_j, t_j) \in \mathcal{E}$ let

$$\mathcal{G} := ((E_1, t_1), \dots, (E_n, t_n))$$

$$A_j := (\beta_{t_j})^{-1}(E_j) \quad (\text{for } j \in \{1, \dots, n\})$$

$$L := \mathbf{1}_{A_n} \dots \mathbf{1}_{A_1} \quad (\text{for } A \subset Z, \text{ by } \mathbf{1}_A \text{ we denote the indicator function on } A)$$

$$W := L / \int L \, d\lambda \quad (\text{where } \lambda \text{ is the Lebesgue measure on } Z)$$

$$W_\tau := W \circ (\beta_\tau)^{-1} \quad (\text{as a composition of mappings})$$

With

$$M := \beta_\tau(\bigcap_j A_j)$$

(using Liouville’s theorem) we obtain the simple relationship

$$W_\tau = \mathbf{1}_M / \lambda(M)$$

W_τ is a probability density on Z , the phase space of the universe.

Z is the Cartesian product of the phase spaces of Q and Q^- :

$$Z = Z_Q \times Z_{Q^-}$$

The probabilistic state of Q at time τ under condition \mathcal{G} is now defined as

$$W_{Q;\tau|\mathcal{G}} := \int W_\tau \, d\lambda_{Q^-}$$

where λ_{Q^-} is the Lebesgue measure on Z_{Q^-} .

B3. The Schrödinger equation

The aim of this chapter is to show that, under certain conditions, the quantum state of a subsystem of the Hilbert space moves approximately according to a Schrödinger equation. The condition is that the retroactive effect of the system on its environment is so small that it does not significantly alter the influence of the environment on the system under consideration.

Let Q be a subsystem of \mathcal{H} . Then Q^- denotes the associated “rest of the world”, and we have

$$\mathcal{H} = \mathcal{H}_Q \otimes \mathcal{H}_{Q^-}$$

Let

$$\mathcal{G} := ((E_1, t_1), \dots, (E_n, t_n))$$

be a finite sequence of events. With

$$A_j := U_{-t_j} E_j \quad (\text{for } j \in \{1, \dots, n\})$$

$$L := \pi_{A_n} \dots \pi_{A_1}$$

$$W := LL^* / \text{tr} LL^*$$

$$W_\tau := U_\tau W U_{-\tau} \quad (\text{for } \tau \in T)$$

the quantum state of Q at time τ under condition \mathcal{G} is defined as

$$W_{Q; \tau | \mathcal{G}} = \text{tr}_Q[W_\tau]$$

Here we consider the case in which the rest of the world Q^- acts unilaterally on the subsystem Q without any significant retroactive effect. In particular, this effect of Q on Q^- should be so small that it does not significantly influence the reverse effect of Q^- on Q .

In this case, the energy of Q is described by the operator H_Q on the Hilbert space \mathcal{H}_Q . This includes both the energy of the subsystem Q when considered on its own and without taking into account the interaction between Q and Q^- , as well as the energy resulting from the effect of Q^- on Q under the conditions given by \mathcal{G} . The energy of the subsystem Q^- considered on its own, i.e., without taking into account the interaction between Q and Q^- , is described by the operator H_{Q^-} on the Hilbert space \mathcal{H}_{Q^-} .

Example: The subsystem Q consists of a single electron. The rest of the world generates (under condition \mathcal{G}) an electric field in which the electron moves. The behavior of the electron has no significant effect on the rest of the world. The operator H_Q then describes both the “internal” energy of the electron, in this case the kinetic energy, and the effect of the rest of the world on Q , i.e., the potential energy of the electron in the electric field generated by Q^- . H_{Q^-} , on the other hand, describes the energy of the rest of the world as if the electron did not exist at all.

Note: Conditions of the type described are only given under some condition \mathcal{G} and during a time interval $[t_1, t_2]$. For example, \mathcal{G} can describe an experimental setup in which, in the time interval $[t_1, t_2]$, an electric field is generated wherein electrons move.

For the following, we define

$$\alpha_Q(H_Q) := H_Q \otimes I_{Q^-}$$

$$\alpha_{Q^-}(H_{Q^-}) := I_Q \otimes H_{Q^-}$$

where I_Q and I_{Q^-} are the identity operators on \mathcal{H}_Q and \mathcal{H}_{Q^-} , respectively. Now let

$$H' := \alpha_Q(H_Q) + \alpha_{Q^-}(H_{Q^-})$$

The Hamilton operator H for the universe can thus be represented as

$$H = H' + H_X$$

The operator H_X defined on \mathcal{H} describes the part of the interaction that goes beyond the effect of Q^- on Q and is therefore not yet covered by H_Q .

We assume that (apart from the effect of Q^- on Q described by H_Q) under the conditions given by \mathcal{G} and in the time interval $[t_1, t_2]$, there is only a very small additional interaction between Q and Q^- . Specifically, we assume that under these conditions the energy described by H_X is always close to zero.

This is expressed by the fact that, given the statistical operator W_τ , the “expected value” of $(H_X)^2$ is approximately zero. We thus have for $\tau \in [t_1, t_2]$:

$$\begin{aligned} E_{W_\tau}((H_X)^2) &:= \text{tr}((H_X)^2 W_\tau) \\ &\approx 0 \end{aligned}$$

With the (Euclidean) norm

$$|M| := (\text{tr} MM^*)^{1/2}$$

defined on the linear space of all operators on \mathcal{H} and with

$$L_\tau := U_\tau L$$

as an abbreviation, we obtain

$$W_\tau = L_\tau (L_\tau)^* / |L|^2$$

and it follows that:

$$\begin{aligned} E_{W_\tau}((H_X)^2) &= \text{tr}((H_X)^2 W_\tau) \\ &= \text{tr}(H_X W_\tau H_X) \\ &= \text{tr}(H_X L_\tau (L_\tau)^* H_X) / |L|^2 \\ &= |H_X L_\tau|^2 / |L|^2 \end{aligned}$$

Since $| \cdot |$ is a norm, we find

$$H_X L_\tau \approx 0$$

and from this, because of

$$H_X W_\tau = H_X L_\tau (L_\tau)^* / |L|^2$$

we obtain

$$(1) H_X W_\tau \approx 0 \quad (\text{for } \tau \in [t_1, t_2])$$

This statement is equivalent to

$$(2) H W_\tau \approx H' W_\tau \quad (\text{for } \tau \in [t_1, t_2])$$

and (since one can switch to the adjoint expressions and H, H' as well as W_τ are self-adjoint)

it is also equivalent to

$$(3) W_\tau H \approx W_\tau H' \quad (\text{for } \tau \in [t_1, t_2])$$

Note: If Q does not represent a physically meaningful subsystem, then there is no condition \mathcal{G} and no time interval $[t_1, t_2]$ for which H is given by

$$\alpha_Q(H_Q) + \alpha_{Q^-}(H_{Q^-}) + H_X$$

with

$$H_X W_\tau \approx 0 \quad (\text{for } \tau \in [t_1, t_2])$$

In this case, the motion of the subsystem Q cannot be described by a separate equation.

The equation of motion for the statistical operator belonging to \mathcal{G} is:

$$W_\tau = U_\tau W U_{-\tau}$$

It can also be expressed in the form of a differential equation. We have:

$$U_\tau = e^{-i\tau H/\hbar}$$

$$\partial/\partial\tau(U_\tau) = (-iH/\hbar) U_\tau$$

$$U_{-\tau} = e^{i\tau H/\hbar}$$

$$\partial/\partial\tau(U_{-\tau}) = U_{-\tau} (iH/\hbar)$$

Here, H and U_τ are commutable operators, and H does not depend on the parameter τ .

We obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \partial/\partial\tau(W_\tau) &= \partial/\partial\tau(U_\tau) W U_{-\tau} + U_\tau W \partial/\partial\tau(U_{-\tau}) \\ &= (-iH/\hbar) U_\tau W U_{-\tau} + U_\tau W U_{-\tau} (iH/\hbar) \\ &= (-i/\hbar) (H W_\tau - W_\tau H) \end{aligned}$$

and thus

$$(4) i\hbar \partial/\partial\tau(W_\tau) = H W_\tau - W_\tau H$$

This is a version of the Schrödinger equation which describes the time dependence of the statistical operator W_τ in the form of a differential equation.

Based on a specific orthonormal basis, every statistical operator W' on \mathcal{H} can be represented by a matrix:

$$W' = (w_{ij})_{ij}$$

Similarly, the operator W' on the tensor product

$$\mathcal{H} = \mathcal{H}_Q \otimes \mathcal{H}_{Q^-}$$

can be represented as

$$W' = (W_{kl})_{kl}$$

where W_{kl} are themselves matrices:

$$W_{kl} = (w_{ijkl})_{ij}$$

The partial traces on \mathcal{H}_Q and \mathcal{H}_{Q-} can then be written as (see Chapter B0):

$$\text{tr}_Q[W'] = \sum_k W_{kk}$$

and

$$\text{tr}_{Q-}[W'] = (\text{tr } W_{kl})_{kl}$$

For the following, let W' be any statistical operator on \mathcal{H} . We then have:

$$\underline{\text{L.3.1}} \quad \text{tr}_Q[\alpha_Q(H_Q) W'] = H_Q \text{tr}_Q[W']$$

Proof: It is

$$\alpha_Q(H_Q) W' = (H_Q W_{kl})_{kl}$$

and consequently

$$\begin{aligned} \text{tr}_Q[\alpha_Q(H_Q) W'] &= \text{tr}_Q[(H_Q W_{kl})_{kl}] \\ &= \sum_k (H_Q W_{kk}) \\ &= H_Q (\sum_k W_{kk}) \\ &= H_Q \text{tr}_Q[W'] \end{aligned}$$

QED

$$\underline{\text{L.3.2}} \quad \text{tr}_Q[W' \alpha_Q(H_Q)] = \text{tr}_Q[W'] H_Q$$

Proof: It is

$$W' \alpha_Q(H_Q) = (W_{kl} H_Q)_{kl}$$

and consequently

$$\begin{aligned} \text{tr}_Q[W' \alpha_Q(H_Q)] &= \text{tr}_Q[(W_{kl} H_Q)_{kl}] \\ &= \sum_k (W_{kk} H_Q) \\ &= (\sum_k W_{kk}) H_Q \\ &= \text{tr}_Q[W'] H_Q \end{aligned}$$

QED

$$\underline{\text{L.3.3}} \quad \text{tr}_{Q-}[\alpha_Q(H_Q) W'] = \text{tr}_{Q-}[W' \alpha_Q(H_Q)]$$

Proof: It is

$$\begin{aligned} \text{tr}_{Q-}[\alpha_Q(H_Q) W'] &= \text{tr}_{Q-}[\alpha_Q(H_Q) (W_{kl})_{kl}] \\ &= \text{tr}_{Q-}[(H_Q W_{kl})_{kl}] \\ &= (\text{tr } H_Q W_{kl})_{kl} \end{aligned}$$

as well as

$$\begin{aligned} \text{tr}_{Q-}[W' \alpha_Q(H_Q)] &= \text{tr}_{Q-}[(W_{kl})_{kl} \alpha_Q(H_Q)] \\ &= \text{tr}_{Q-}[(W_{kl} H_Q)_{kl}] \\ &= (\text{tr } W_{kl} H_Q)_{kl} \end{aligned}$$

These two expressions are identical, since for all operators L and M:

$$\text{tr} LM = \text{tr} ML$$

QED

$$\text{L.3.4 } \text{tr}_Q[\alpha_{Q-(H_{Q-})} W'] = \text{tr}_Q[W' \alpha_{Q-(H_{Q-})}]$$

Proof: This statement is obtained from L.3.3 by swapping the roles of the two tensor factors \mathcal{H}_Q and \mathcal{H}_{Q-} . **QED**

So, for every statistical operator W' on \mathcal{H} , the following rules apply:

$$\text{tr}_Q[\alpha_Q(H_Q) W'] = H_Q \text{tr}_Q[W'] \quad (\text{cf. L.3.1})$$

$$\text{tr}_Q[W' \alpha_Q(H_Q)] = \text{tr}_Q[W'] H_Q \quad (\text{cf. L.3.2})$$

$$\text{tr}_Q[\alpha_{Q-(H_{Q-})} W'] = \text{tr}_Q[W' \alpha_{Q-(H_{Q-})}] \quad (\text{cf. L.3.4})$$

It now follows that

$$\begin{aligned} i\hbar \partial/\partial\tau \text{tr}_Q[W_\tau] &= \text{tr}_Q[i\hbar \partial/\partial\tau(W_\tau)] \\ &= \text{tr}_Q[H W_\tau - W_\tau H] && (\text{by (4)}) \\ &\approx \text{tr}_Q[H' W_\tau - W_\tau H'] && (\text{by (2) and (3)}) \\ &= \text{tr}_Q[H' W_\tau] - \text{tr}_Q[W_\tau H'] \\ &= \text{tr}_Q[\alpha_Q(H_Q) W_\tau] + \text{tr}_Q[\alpha_{Q-(H_{Q-})} W_\tau] \\ &\quad - \text{tr}_Q[W_\tau \alpha_Q(H_Q)] - \text{tr}_Q[W_\tau \alpha_{Q-(H_{Q-})}] \quad (\text{definition of } H') \\ &= H_Q \text{tr}_Q[W_\tau] - \text{tr}_Q[W_\tau] H_Q \quad (\text{by L.3.1, L.3.2 and L.3.4}) \end{aligned}$$

Based on the definition of $W_{Q;\tau|\mathcal{G}}$, we obtain the following relationship (analogous to (4)):

$$i\hbar \partial/\partial\tau(W_{Q;\tau|\mathcal{G}}) \approx H_Q W_{Q;\tau|\mathcal{G}} - W_{Q;\tau|\mathcal{G}} H_Q$$

This is the Schrödinger equation (which in general applies only approximately) for the state of the subsystem Q under condition \mathcal{G} for each τ in the time interval $[t_1, t_2]$. It describes how the state of Q under condition \mathcal{G} changes over time.

The operator H_Q itself can be explicitly time-dependent. In this case,

$$H'(\tau) = \alpha_Q(H_Q(\tau)) + \alpha_{Q-(H_{Q-})}$$

and instead of (2) and (3), the following holds for $\tau \in [t_1, t_2]$:

$$H W_\tau \approx H'(\tau) W_\tau$$

$$W_\tau H \approx W_\tau H'(\tau)$$

Here, the Schrödinger equation for the state $W_{Q;\tau|\mathcal{G}}$ is:

$$i\hbar \partial/\partial\tau(W_{Q;\tau|\mathcal{G}}) \approx H_Q(\tau) W_{Q;\tau|\mathcal{G}} - W_{Q;\tau|\mathcal{G}} H_Q(\tau)$$

If H_Q is *not* time-dependent in this way, the equation of motion for Q can also be written in closed form. With

$$U_{Q;\tau} := e^{-i\tau H_Q/\hbar}$$

we obtain:

Theorem T.3.1 Under the conditions described,

$$W_{Q;\tau|\mathcal{G}} \approx U_{Q;\tau-t_1} W_{Q;t_1|\mathcal{G}} U_{Q;-(\tau-t_1)} \quad (\text{for } \tau \in [t_1, t_2])$$

Also in this closed form, the Schrödinger equation for a subsystem Q will in general be merely an approximation. Only in the case of Q being the entire universe does it hold in the sense of exact equality.

B4. Bell's inequality

In this chapter we show that the axioms of quantum theory contradict Bell's inequality. So there is a contradiction between these axioms on the one hand and Kolmogorov's theory of probability on the other.

The chapter consists of the following subsections:

1. Logical inconsistency due to Bell's inequality
2. Incompatibility of Kolmogorov's probability theory with quantum realism

1. Logical inconsistency due to Bell's inequality

This section uses an example to show that Bell's inequality contradicts the laws of quantum theory.

Let P be a probability measure on \mathcal{A} , i.e., an additive and normalized function from \mathcal{A} to the interval $[0,1]$. Because of

$$(A \wedge \neg C) \subset (A \wedge \neg B) \vee (B \wedge \neg C) \quad (\text{for } A, B, C \in \mathcal{A})$$

this function satisfies the triangle inequality

$$P(A \wedge \neg C) \leq P(A \wedge \neg B) + P(B \wedge \neg C)$$

Applying this inequality twice yields

$$P(A \wedge \neg D) \leq P(A \wedge \neg B) + P(B \wedge \neg C) + P(C \wedge \neg D) \quad (\text{for } A, B, C, D \in \mathcal{A})$$

Since P is additive, we can deduce:

$$P(A) - P(A \wedge D) \leq P(A) - P(A \wedge B) + P(B) - P(B \wedge C) + P(C) - P(C \wedge D)$$

Rearranging this gives:

$$(*) \quad P(A \wedge B) + P(B \wedge C) + P(C \wedge D) \leq P(A \wedge D) + P(B) + P(C)$$

which can be regarded as a simple variant of Bell's inequality.

We now want to show that the equation

$$(**) \quad P(\langle A, t \rangle \mid \langle B, t \rangle) = \text{tr } \pi_A \pi_B / \text{tr } \pi_B$$

contradicts this Bell's inequality. Here, A and B are subspaces of \mathcal{H} , t is a point in time, tr denotes the trace function, and π_A and π_B are the projection operators associated with A and B , respectively.

For brevity, we let $\langle A \rangle := \langle A, 0 \rangle$ for all $A < \mathcal{H}$. The axioms MON, SEC, and SE immediately yield the following statements (see Chapter B0):

$$\underline{\text{MON}} \quad A < B \Rightarrow \langle A \rangle \subset \langle B \rangle \quad (\text{for } A, B < \mathcal{H})$$

$$\underline{\text{SEC}} \quad \bigcap_j A_j = \mathbf{o} \Rightarrow (\forall_j \langle A_j \rangle) = \mathbf{\emptyset} \quad (\text{for commutable } A_1, A_2, \dots < \mathcal{H})$$

$$\underline{\text{SE}} \quad \langle A, t \rangle = \langle U_{-t} A \rangle \quad (\text{for } A < \mathcal{H} \text{ and } t \in T)$$

We now consider a fixed unit vector $\varphi \in \mathcal{H}$. By letting $B := [\varphi]$ and $t := 0$, the following statement can be derived from (**):

$$\underline{\text{PROB}} \quad P(\langle A \rangle \mid \langle [\varphi] \rangle) = |\pi_A \varphi|^2 \quad (\text{for all } A < \mathcal{H})$$

For brevity, let

$$P_\varphi(F) := P(F | \langle [\varphi] \rangle) \quad (\text{for all } F \in \mathcal{A})$$

Then P_φ is a probability measure on \mathcal{A} .

L.4.1 For commutable subspaces $A, B < \mathcal{H}$, the following equation holds

$$\text{PROB2 } P_\varphi(\langle A \rangle \wedge \langle B \rangle) = |\pi_{A \cap B} \varphi|^2$$

Proof: Let $A, B < \mathcal{H}$ be two commutable subspaces. Because of MON,

$$\langle A \cap B \rangle \subset \langle A \rangle \wedge \langle B \rangle$$

and it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} P_\varphi(\langle A \rangle \wedge \langle B \rangle) &\geq P_\varphi(\langle A \cap B \rangle) \\ &= |\pi_{A \cap B} \varphi|^2 \quad (\text{because of PROB and the definition of } P_\varphi) \end{aligned}$$

Conversely, because of SEC,

$$\langle A \rangle \wedge \langle B \rangle \subset \neg \langle (A \cap B)^\perp \rangle$$

and we have:

$$\begin{aligned} P_\varphi(\langle A \rangle \wedge \langle B \rangle) &\leq P_\varphi(\neg \langle (A \cap B)^\perp \rangle) \\ &= 1 - P_\varphi(\langle (A \cap B)^\perp \rangle) \\ &= 1 - |\pi_{(A \cap B)^\perp} \varphi|^2 \quad (\text{because of PROB and the definition of } P_\varphi) \\ &= |\pi_{A \cap B} \varphi|^2 \end{aligned} \quad \text{QED}$$

We now consider the case $\mathcal{H} = \mathbb{C}^4$. This Hilbert space can be represented as

$$\mathcal{H} := \mathcal{H}_1 \otimes \mathcal{H}_2$$

with

$$\mathcal{H}_1 := \mathbb{C}^2$$

$$\mathcal{H}_2 := \mathbb{C}^2$$

Hilbert spaces formed in this way can be used, for example, to describe the spin properties of two electrons.

We consider the unit vector (writing elements of \mathcal{H} as row vectors for simplicity)

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi &:= 1/\sqrt{2} (1, 0, 0, 1) \\ &\in \mathcal{H} \end{aligned}$$

This “state vector” φ can be interpreted as a description of the case in which the two electrons have opposite spins.

For some $\beta \in [0, 360^\circ)$, we now define the unit vectors

$$a := (\cos \beta, \sin \beta) \in \mathbb{C}^2$$

$$b := (1, 0) \in \mathbb{C}^2$$

$$c := (\cos \beta, -\sin \beta) \in \mathbb{C}^2$$

and let

$$A := [a] \otimes \mathcal{H}_2 < \mathcal{H}$$

$$B := [b] \otimes \mathcal{H}_2 < \mathcal{H}$$

$$B' := \mathcal{H}_1 \otimes [b] < \mathcal{H}$$

$$C' := \mathcal{H}_1 \otimes [c] < \mathcal{H}$$

A and B (or B' and C') can be interpreted as spin properties that can be measured on the first (or second) electron. A is commutable with B', as are A with C', B with B', and B with C'.

With the standard orthonormal basis (e_1, e_2) of \mathbb{C}^2 , we have

$$A = [a \otimes e_1] \oplus [a \otimes e_2]$$

and therefore (because of PROB and the definition of P_φ)

$$\begin{aligned} P_\varphi(\langle A \rangle) &= |\pi_A \varphi|^2 \\ &= |\pi_{[a \otimes e_1]} \varphi|^2 + |\pi_{[a \otimes e_2]} \varphi|^2 \\ &= |(a \otimes e_1)^* \varphi|^2 + |(a \otimes e_2)^* \varphi|^2 \\ &= 1/2 \cos^2 \beta + 1/2 \sin^2 \beta \\ &= 1/2 \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, we obtain

$$P_\varphi(\langle B \rangle) = P_\varphi(\langle B' \rangle) = P_\varphi(\langle C' \rangle) = 1/2$$

We have

$$a \otimes b = (\cos \beta, 0, \sin \beta, 0)$$

and consequently

$$(a \otimes b)^* \varphi = 1/\sqrt{2} \cos \beta$$

Due to

$$\begin{aligned} A \cap B' &= [a] \otimes \mathcal{H}_2 \cap \mathcal{H}_1 \otimes [b] \\ &= [a \otimes b] \end{aligned}$$

we get:

$$\begin{aligned} P_\varphi(\langle A \rangle \wedge \langle B' \rangle) &= |\pi_{A \cap B'} \varphi|^2 \quad (\text{because of PROB2}) \\ &= |\pi_{[a \otimes b]} \varphi|^2 \\ &= |(a \otimes b)^* \varphi|^2 \\ &= 1/2 \cos^2 \beta \end{aligned}$$

In a similar way, we find:

$$\begin{aligned} P_\varphi(\langle B \rangle \wedge \langle C' \rangle) &= |(b \otimes c)^* \varphi|^2 \\ &= 1/2 \cos^2 \beta \end{aligned}$$

Because of

$$b \otimes b = (1, 0, 0, 0)$$

and

$$(b \otimes b)^* \varphi = 1/\sqrt{2}$$

we also have

$$\begin{aligned} P_{\varphi}(\langle B \rangle \wedge \langle B' \rangle) &= |(b \otimes b)^* \varphi|^2 \\ &= 1/2 \end{aligned}$$

Because of

$$a \otimes c = (\cos^2 \beta, -\cos \beta \sin \beta, \cos \beta \sin \beta, -\sin^2 \beta)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} (a \otimes c)^* \varphi &= 1/\sqrt{2} (\cos^2 \beta - \sin^2 \beta) \\ &= 1/\sqrt{2} \cos(2\beta) \end{aligned}$$

we further obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} P_{\varphi}(\langle A \rangle \wedge \langle C' \rangle) &= |(a \otimes c)^* \varphi|^2 \\ &= 1/2 \cos^2(2\beta) \end{aligned}$$

Note: The probabilities thus calculated determine the correlations for measurements of one spin property of the first and another spin property of the second electron.

From the inequality (*), we get:

$$\begin{aligned} P_{\varphi}(\langle A \rangle \wedge \langle B' \rangle) + P_{\varphi}(\langle B \rangle \wedge \langle B' \rangle) + P_{\varphi}(\langle B \rangle \wedge \langle C' \rangle) \\ \leq P_{\varphi}(\langle A \rangle \wedge \langle C' \rangle) + P_{\varphi}(\langle B \rangle) + P_{\varphi}(\langle B' \rangle) \end{aligned}$$

Substituting the calculated values, we obtain:

$$1/2 \cos^2 \beta + 1/2 + 1/2 \cos^2 \beta \leq 1/2 \cos^2(2\beta) + 1/2 + 1/2$$

Multiplying by 2, we get:

$$1 + 2 \cos^2 \beta \leq 2 + \cos^2(2\beta)$$

This can be transformed into

$$\sin^2(2\beta) \leq 2 \sin^2 \beta$$

For $0 < \beta < 45^\circ$, this inequality is false.

A similar example can be given for any Hilbert space whose dimension is at least four. Moreover, for an arbitrary “state” vector φ , it is possible to define subspaces A, B, B', and C' that result in a contradiction. To this end, one simply needs to choose a suitable orthonormal basis. This contradiction can also be derived if the axioms MON and SEC as well as the statement PROB are assumed only for a subsystem Q (with $\dim \mathcal{H}_Q \geq 4$). We have thus shown that the statement PROB is not compatible with the axioms MON and SEC. As a consequence, equation (***) is in contradiction to Bell’s inequality, provided that the axioms MON and SEC are assumed.

2. Incompatibility of Kolmogorov’s probability theory with quantum realism

In this section we show that if one assumes the existence of an objective reality and starts from the well-known equations for calculating probabilities of certain events, Kolmogorov’s probability theory leads to a contradiction.

The example discussed in Section 1 shows that the following three statements are logically inconsistent:

- (1) Every subspace of the Hilbert space is assigned a truth value at each point in time, such that the monotonicity and exclusion principles apply (realism).
- (2) P is a Kolmogorov probability measure on the algebra \mathcal{A} of all possible facts as given by the model of quantum theory (Kolmogorov's probability theory).
- (3) At a given point in time t , the probability that the event $\langle A, t \rangle$ occurs can be calculated (for every subspace A of \mathcal{H}) by the formula

$$P(\langle A, t \rangle | \langle [\varphi], t \rangle) = |\pi_A \varphi|^2$$

where φ is an element of the Hilbert space.

B5. The law of probability in quantum theory

In this chapter, the following statements are proven:

- The mapping ρ , with the required properties, can be defined without contradiction.
- The outer measure μ is well defined and proves to be continuous.
- The usual equations apply to μ , e.g., $\mu(\langle A \rangle | \langle [\phi] \rangle) = |\pi_A \phi|^2$.
- The constructive approach to the formation of μ guarantees that μ is properly defined on the entire algebra \mathcal{A} and has the specified properties without any contradictions occurring, comparable to those related to Bell's inequality.

The chapter consists of the following subsections:

1. The Euclidean norm on the space of continuous operators
2. The subspace-metric δ on the set \mathcal{U} of linear subspaces of \mathcal{H}
3. Definition of the mapping ρ on the set \mathcal{A}^\wedge of all finite logical conjunctions of events, with its characterizing property
4. Definition of the outer measure μ on the algebra \mathcal{A} and its explicit representation
5. On the continuity of ρ and μ
6. The validity of common equations for μ and the logical consistency of the theory

1. The Euclidean norm on the space of continuous operators

In the following section, the (Euclidean) norm on the set of all continuous operators on the Hilbert space \mathcal{H} is introduced and some of its properties are given.

Definition D.5.1 Let L be the linear space of all continuous linear operators on \mathcal{H} .

Note: L is closed with respect to the formation of products. Furthermore, L contains all projections and all unitary operators. With $L \in L$, the adjoint L^* belongs to L as well.

For $b \in \mathcal{H}$, b^* is the adjoint vector of b . Thus, the expression b^*a represents the scalar product $\langle a, b \rangle$ of the two vectors a and $b \in \mathcal{H}$.

Definition D.5.2 For $L \in L$, the trace of L can be defined if and only if the (potentially infinite) series

$$\sum_j (b_j)^* L b_j$$

is convergent for every orthonormal basis (b_j) of \mathcal{H} , and if it always has the same limit. This limit is then referred to as $\text{tr } L$. We explicitly allow the two values $-\infty$ and $+\infty$ as a limit.

L.5.1 If $L \in \mathcal{L}$ and (b_j) is an orthonormal basis of \mathcal{H} , then obviously

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_j (b_j)^* L L^* b_j &= \sum_j |L^* b_j|^2 \\ &\in [0, \infty] \end{aligned}$$

L.5.2 For all $L \in \mathcal{L}$, the trace of $L L^*$ exists and

$$\text{tr } L L^* \in [0, \infty]$$

Proof: Either the series specified in L.5.1 has the value ∞ for every orthonormal basis. In this case, $\text{tr } L L^* = \infty$. Otherwise, there is an orthonormal basis (b_j) with

$$\sum_j |L^* b_j|^2 < \infty$$

In this case, L belongs to the so-called Hilbert-Schmidt class. It is well known that the value of the series is then independent of the choice of the orthonormal basis and thus $\text{tr } L L^*$ exists.

QED

Definition D.5.3 For all $L \in \mathcal{L}$, the (generalized) Euclidean norm is defined as

$$|L| := (\text{tr } L L^*)^{1/2}$$

L.5.3 Obviously, for all $L \in \mathcal{L}$, we have $|L| \in [0, \infty]$.

L.5.4 If (b_j) is an orthonormal basis and $L \in \mathcal{L}$, then

$$|L|^2 = \sum_j |L^* b_j|^2$$

Proof: This follows directly from D.5.3 and L.5.1.

QED

L.5.5 For $L \in \mathcal{L}$, the following holds: $|L| = 0 \Leftrightarrow L = o$

Proof: The implication “ \Rightarrow ” follows from L.5.4.

QED

Definition D.5.4 Let

$$\mathcal{L}_e := \{ L \in \mathcal{L} \mid |L| < \infty \}$$

Note: \mathcal{L}_e is the so-called Hilbert-Schmidt class. As is well known, it represents a linear subspace of \mathcal{L} . If $L \in \mathcal{L}_e$ and $M \in \mathcal{L}$, then the products LM and ML belong to \mathcal{L}_e . For every $L \in \mathcal{L}_e$, its adjoint L^* belongs to \mathcal{L}_e as well. Each $L \in \mathcal{L}$ with $\text{rank}(L) < \infty$ is an element of \mathcal{L}_e . For $L, M \in \mathcal{L}_e$, the trace of the product LM always exists, with the usual calculation rules for the trace function. With

$$\langle L, M \rangle := \text{tr } L M^*$$

a scalar product is defined on \mathcal{L}_e , which makes \mathcal{L}_e a Hilbert space. For all $L \in \mathcal{L}_e$ we have

$$\langle L, L \rangle = |L|^2 \text{ (in the sense of definition D.5.3).}$$

L.5.6 For $L \in \mathcal{L}$, $|L^*| = |L|$.

Proof: If $|L| < \infty$, then L belongs to \mathcal{L}_e . In this case,

$$\begin{aligned} |L^*|^2 &= \text{tr } L^*L \\ &= \text{tr } LL^* \\ &= |L|^2 \end{aligned}$$

If $|L| = \infty$, then $|L^*|$ cannot be finite either, because otherwise we would have $L^* \in \mathcal{L}_e$ and thus $L = (L^*)^* \in \mathcal{L}_e$, i.e., $|L| < \infty$. So, in the case of $|L| = \infty$, we also have $|L^*| = \infty$. **QED**

L.5.7 If (b_j) is an orthonormal basis, $\pi_n := \pi[b_1, \dots, b_n]$, $L \in \mathcal{L}$, and $L_n := \pi_n L$, then $|L_n|$ is a monotonically increasing sequence that converges to $|L|$.

Proof: It is

$$\begin{aligned} |L_n|^2 &= |\pi_n L|^2 \\ &= \sum_j |(\pi_n L)^* b_j|^2 && \text{(according to L.5.4)} \\ &= \sum_j |L^* \pi_n b_j|^2 \\ &= \sum_{j \leq n} |L^* b_j|^2 \\ &\rightarrow \sum_j |L^* b_j|^2 && \text{(monotonic convergence)} \\ &= |L|^2 && \text{(according to L.5.4)} \end{aligned}$$

QED

L.5.8 The norm $||$ introduced by D.5.3 satisfies the triangle inequality

$$|L + M| \leq |L| + |M| \quad (\text{for } L, M \in \mathcal{L})$$

This also applies if $|L|$, $|M|$ or $|L + M|$ has the value ∞ .

Proof: Let (b_j) be an orthonormal basis. In addition, let

$$\pi_n := \pi[b_1, \dots, b_n]$$

and $L_n := \pi_n L$ as well as $M_n := \pi_n M$. Then $L_n \in \mathcal{L}_e$ and $M_n \in \mathcal{L}_e$ and, since $||$ is a norm on \mathcal{L}_e , it follows that:

$$\begin{aligned} |L_n + M_n| &\leq |L_n| + |M_n| \\ &\leq |L| + |M| \end{aligned} \quad (\text{L.5.7})$$

Since $|L_n + M_n|$ converges to $|L + M|$ due to L.5.7, we find:

$$|L + M| \leq |L| + |M|$$

QED

L.5.9 For $A < \mathcal{H}$ and $L \in \mathcal{L}$, $|\pi_A L| \leq |L|$.

Proof: Let (a_j) be an orthonormal basis of \mathcal{H} such that A is generated by a subset $\{ a_j \mid j \in J_A \}$.

Then

$$\begin{aligned} |\pi_A L|^2 &= \sum_j |L^* \pi_A a_j|^2 && (\text{L.5.4}) \\ &= \sum_{j \in J_A} |L^* a_j|^2 \\ &\leq \sum_j |L^* a_j|^2 \\ &= |L|^2 && (\text{L.5.4}) \end{aligned}$$

QED

L.5.10 For $L \in \mathcal{L}_e$ and $A < \mathcal{H}$,

$$|\pi_A L|^2 = \text{tr } \pi_A L L^*$$

Proof: It is

$$\begin{aligned} |\pi_A L|^2 &= \text{tr } \pi_A L (\pi_A L)^* \\ &= \text{tr } \pi_A L L^* \pi_A \\ &= \text{tr } \pi_A \pi_A L L^* \\ &= \text{tr } \pi_A L L^* \end{aligned}$$

QED

L.5.11 For $A < \mathcal{H}$ and $L \in \mathcal{L}$ with $\text{rank}(L) < \infty$,

$$|\pi_A L|^2 = \text{tr } \pi_A L L^*$$

Proof: This follows from L.5.10, since every $L \in \mathcal{L}$ with $\text{rank}(L) < \infty$ belongs to \mathcal{L}_e .

QED

For subspaces A , B , and C of \mathcal{H} , the following lemmas hold:

L.5.12 If $\dim A < \infty$, then $|\pi_A \pi_B|^2 = \text{tr } \pi_A \pi_B$

Proof: It is

$$\begin{aligned} |\pi_A \pi_B|^2 &= |\pi_B \pi_A|^2 && \text{(L.5.6)} \\ &= \text{tr } \pi_B \pi_A && \text{(L.5.11)} \\ &= \text{tr } \pi_A \pi_B \end{aligned}$$

QED

L.5.13 $|\pi_A \pi_B \pi_C| = |\pi_C \pi_B \pi_A|$ (Corollary to L.5.6)

L.5.14 $|\pi_A \pi_B| = |\pi_B \pi_A|$ (Corollary to L.5.13)

L.5.15 $|\pi_A \pi_B \pi_C| \leq |\pi_B \pi_C|$ (Corollary to L.5.9)

L.5.16 $|\pi_A \pi_B \pi_C| \leq |\pi_A \pi_B|$

Proof: It is

$$\begin{aligned} |\pi_A \pi_B \pi_C| &= |\pi_C \pi_B \pi_A| && \text{(L.5.13)} \\ &\leq |\pi_B \pi_A| && \text{(L.5.15)} \\ &= |\pi_A \pi_B| && \text{(L.5.14)} \end{aligned}$$

QED

2. The subspace-metric δ on the set \mathcal{U} of linear subspaces of \mathcal{H}

Definition D.5.5 A subspace-metric on \mathcal{U} is a mapping

$$\delta : \mathcal{U} \times \mathcal{U} \rightarrow [0, \infty]$$

with the following properties:

$$\begin{aligned} \delta(A,B) = 0 &\Leftrightarrow A \leq B \\ \delta(A,C) &\leq \delta(A,B) + \delta(B,C) \quad (\text{triangle inequality}) \end{aligned}$$

for elements $A,B,C \in \mathcal{U}$. If δ is a subspace-metric, then $\delta(A,B) \approx 0$ expresses the fact that the relationship $A \lesssim B$ exists, i.e., that A is approximately a subspace of B .

L.5.17 From D.5.5 it follows immediately that every subspace-metric δ on \mathcal{U} is bimonotonic (increasing in the first argument and decreasing in the second), i.e.:

$$\begin{aligned} A \leq A' &\Rightarrow \delta(A,B) \leq \delta(A',B) \quad (\text{for } A,A',B \in \mathcal{U}) \\ B \leq B' &\Rightarrow \delta(A,B') \leq \delta(A,B) \quad (\text{for } A,B,B' \in \mathcal{U}) \end{aligned}$$

Definition D.5.6 For all $A,B < \mathcal{H}$, let

$$\delta(A,B) := |\pi_A \pi_{B^\perp}|$$

Because of L.5.3, this is equivalent to

$$\delta(A,B) = |\pi_{B^\perp} \pi_A|$$

L.5.18 For all $A,B,C \in \mathcal{U}$,
 $\delta(A,C) \leq \delta(A,B) + \delta(B,C)$

Proof: It is

$$\begin{aligned} \delta(A,C) &= |\pi_A \pi_{C^\perp}| && \text{(D.5.6)} \\ &= |\pi_A (\pi_{B^\perp} + \pi_B) \pi_{C^\perp}| \\ &= |\pi_A \pi_{B^\perp} \pi_{C^\perp} + \pi_A \pi_B \pi_{C^\perp}| \\ &\leq |\pi_A \pi_{B^\perp} \pi_{C^\perp}| + |\pi_A \pi_B \pi_{C^\perp}| && \text{(L.5.8)} \\ &\leq |\pi_A \pi_{B^\perp}| + |\pi_B \pi_{C^\perp}| && \text{(L.5.16 and L.5.15)} \\ &= \delta(A,B) + \delta(B,C) && \text{(D.5.6)} \end{aligned}$$

QED

L.5.19 For all $A,B \in \mathcal{U}$,
 $A < B \Leftrightarrow \delta(A,B) = 0$

Proof: It is

$$\begin{aligned} A < B &\Leftrightarrow \pi_{B^\perp} \pi_A = 0 \\ &\Leftrightarrow |\pi_A \pi_{B^\perp}| = 0 && \text{(L.5.5)} \\ &\Leftrightarrow \delta(A,B) = 0 && \text{(D.5.6)} \end{aligned}$$

QED

L.5.20 δ is a subspace-metric on \mathcal{U} .

Proof: See L.5.18 and L.5.19.

QED

L.5.21 For $A,B < \mathcal{H}$,
 $\delta(A,B) = \delta(B^\perp, A^\perp)$.

Proof: It is

$$\begin{aligned} |\pi_A \pi_{B^\perp}|^2 &= |\pi_{B^\perp} \pi_A|^2 & (L.5.14) \\ &= |\pi_{B^\perp} \pi_{(A^\perp)^\perp}|^2 \end{aligned}$$

and thus

$$\begin{aligned} \delta(A, B) &= |\pi_A \pi_{B^\perp}| & (D.5.6) \\ &= |\pi_{B^\perp} \pi_{(A^\perp)^\perp}| \\ &= \delta(B^\perp, A^\perp) & (D.5.6) \end{aligned}$$

QED

L.5.22 For any finite sequence E_1, \dots, E_n of pairwise commutable subspaces of \mathcal{H} ,

$$\delta(\oplus_j E_j, B) \leq \sum_j \delta(E_j, B)$$

Proof: For $k \leq n$, let

$$F_k := E_k \cap (\oplus_{j < k} E_j)^\perp$$

The F_k are then pairwise orthogonal and we have $\oplus_j F_j = \oplus_j E_j$. It follows that:

$$\begin{aligned} \delta(\oplus_j E_j, B) &= |\pi_{\oplus_j E_j} \pi_{B^\perp}| & (D.5.6) \\ &= |\pi_{\oplus_j F_j} \pi_{B^\perp}| \\ &= |\sum_j \pi_{F_j} \pi_{B^\perp}| \\ &\leq \sum_j |\pi_{F_j} \pi_{B^\perp}| & (L.5.8) \\ &= \sum_j |\pi_{F_j} \pi_{E_j} \pi_{B^\perp}| & (\text{since } F_j < E_j) \\ &\leq \sum_j |\pi_{E_j} \pi_{B^\perp}| & (L.5.15) \\ &= \sum_j \delta(E_j, B) & (D.5.6) \end{aligned}$$

QED

L.5.23 For any finite sequence E_1, \dots, E_n of pairwise commutable subspaces of \mathcal{H} ,

$$\delta(A, \cap_j E_j) \leq \sum_j \delta(A, E_j)$$

Proof: For $j \leq n$, let $D_j := (E_j)^\perp$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \delta(A, \cap_j E_j) &= |\pi_A \pi_{(\cap_j E_j)^\perp}| & (D.5.6) \\ &= |\pi_A \pi_{\oplus_j (E_j)^\perp}| \\ &= |\pi_A \pi_{\oplus_j D_j}| \\ &= |\pi_{\oplus_j D_j} \pi_A| & (L.5.14) \\ &= \delta(\oplus_j D_j, A^\perp) & (D.5.6) \\ &\leq \sum_j \delta(D_j, A^\perp) & (L.5.22) \\ &= \sum_j |\pi_{D_j} \pi_A| & (D.5.6) \\ &= \sum_j |\pi_A \pi_{D_j}| & (L.5.14) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \Sigma_j \delta(A, (D_j)^\perp) \\
 &= \Sigma_j \delta(A, E_j)
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{D.5.6}$$

QED

3. Definition of the mapping ρ on the set \mathcal{A}^\wedge of all finite logical conjunctions of events, with its characterizing property

L.5.24 For $A_1, \dots, A_n < \mathcal{H}$ let $(\forall_j \langle A_j \rangle) \neq \emptyset$. With

$$\omega := \{ (G, t) \in \mathcal{E} \mid \exists_j (A_j < U_{-t}G) \}$$

it follows that

$$\omega \in \forall_j \langle A_j \rangle$$

Proof: It can be easily shown that

$$\omega \in \cap(\text{SE})$$

and

$$\omega \in \cap(\text{MON})$$

Now, if

$$\omega \notin \cap(\text{SEC})$$

there would exist commutable $D_1, D_2, \dots < \mathcal{H}$ with $\cap_k D_k = 0$ and $t \in T$ such that

$$\omega \in \forall_k \langle D_k, t \rangle_0$$

and thus for all k

$$(D_k, t) \in \omega$$

Based on the definition of ω , it would follow that

$$\forall_k \exists_j (A_j < U_{-t}D_k)$$

However, for any k ,

$$A_j < U_{-t}D_k$$

implies

$$\langle A_j \rangle \subset \langle D_k, t \rangle \quad (\text{because of MON and SE})$$

and thus

$$(\forall_j \langle A_j \rangle) \subset \langle D_k, t \rangle$$

Since this is to hold for every k , it would follow that

$$\begin{aligned}
 (\forall_j \langle A_j \rangle) &\subset \forall_k \langle D_k, t \rangle \\
 &= \emptyset \quad (\text{because of SEC})
 \end{aligned}$$

which contradicts the assumption

$$(\forall_j \langle A_j \rangle) \neq \emptyset$$

Consequently, we have $\omega \in \cap(\text{SEC})$ and thus $\omega \in \Omega$. Since $(A_j, 0) \in \omega$ for all j , it follows that $\omega \in \forall_j \langle A_j \rangle$. **QED**

L.5.25 For finitely many $A_j < \mathcal{H}$ and $B_k < \mathcal{H}$,
if $(\forall_j \langle A_j \rangle) \neq \emptyset$ and $(\forall_j \langle A_j \rangle) \subset (\forall_k \langle B_k \rangle)$ then $\forall_k \exists_j (A_j < B_k)$

Proof: Let

$$\omega := \{ (G,t) \in \mathcal{E} \mid \exists_j (A_j < U_{-t}G) \}$$

By L.5.24, we then have

$$\begin{aligned} \omega &\in \forall_j \langle A_j \rangle \\ &\subset \forall_k \langle B_k \rangle \end{aligned}$$

and consequently $(B_k,0) \in \omega$ for all k . Therefore, based on the definition of ω , for every k there is an index j such that $A_j < B_k$. **QED**

L.5.26 For finitely many $A_j < \mathcal{H}$ with $(\forall_j \langle A_j \rangle) = \emptyset$, there exist pairwise commutable subspaces $D_j < \mathcal{H}$ with $\bigcap_j D_j = o$, such that $A_j < D_j$ for all j .

Proof: Let

$$\omega := \{ (G,t) \in \mathcal{E} \mid \exists_j (A_j < U_{-t}G) \}$$

Then

$$\omega \in \bigcap (SE)$$

and

$$\omega \in \bigcap (MON)$$

as well as

$$\omega \in \forall_j \langle A_j \rangle_o$$

Now, if $(\forall_j \langle A_j \rangle) = \emptyset$, then ω cannot be in Ω and thus cannot be in $\bigcap (SEC)$. Consequently, there are commutable $E_k < \mathcal{H}$ with $\bigcap_k E_k = o$ and $t \in T$, such that

$$\omega \in \forall_k \langle E_k, t \rangle_o$$

and thus for all k

$$(E_k, t) \in \omega$$

Based on the definition of ω , with

$$F_k := U_{-t}E_k \quad (\text{for all } k)$$

we obtain

$$\forall_k \exists_j (A_j < F_k)$$

There is thus a mapping f from the index range of k to the index range of j with

$$\forall_k (A_{f(k)} < F_k)$$

Let

$$D_j := \bigcap_{k \in f^{-1}(j)} F_k \quad (\text{In the case of } f^{-1}(j) = \emptyset, \text{ let } D_j := \mathcal{H}.)$$

Then the D_j are commutable as well and we have

$$\bigcap_j D_j = o$$

Now, for any fixed j holds: For all $k \in f^{-1}(j)$, $f(k) = j$ and thus

$$\begin{aligned} A_j &= A_{f(k)} \\ &< F_k \end{aligned}$$

Since this applies to all $k \in f^{-1}(j)$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} A_j &< \bigcap_{k \in f^{-1}(j)} F_k \\ &= D_j \end{aligned}$$

QED

Definition D.5.7 As in Chapter B0, let

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{A}^\wedge &:= \{ \langle A_1 \rangle \wedge \dots \wedge \langle A_n \rangle \mid n \in \mathbb{N} \wedge A_1, \dots, A_n \in \mathcal{U} \} \\ &= \{ \forall_j \langle A_j \rangle \mid n \in \mathbb{N} \wedge A_1, \dots, A_n \in \mathcal{U} \} \end{aligned}$$

\mathcal{A}^\wedge is the set of all finite logical conjunctions of events of the form $\langle A \rangle$ with $A \in \mathcal{U}$.

L.5.27 For $F \in \mathcal{A}^\wedge$ and an infinite sequence $F_1, F_2, \dots \in \mathcal{A}^\wedge$,

$$F \subset \exists_k F_k \Rightarrow \exists_k (F \subset F_k)$$

Proof: Let $A_i < \mathcal{H}$ and $B_{jk} < \mathcal{H}$ with

$$F = \forall_i \langle A_i \rangle$$

and

$$F_k = \forall_j \langle B_{jk} \rangle$$

In the case of $F = \emptyset$, there is nothing to prove. So let $F \neq \emptyset$, i.e.:

$$(\forall_i \langle A_i \rangle) \neq \emptyset$$

According to the premise of the implication to be proven, we have

$$(\forall_i \langle A_i \rangle) \subset \exists_k \forall_j \langle B_{jk} \rangle$$

Now let

$$\omega := \{ (G, t) \in \mathcal{E} \mid \exists_i (A_i < U_{-t}G) \}$$

Using L.5.24, we obtain

$$\omega \in \forall_i \langle A_i \rangle$$

From this we get

$$\omega \in \exists_k \forall_j \langle B_{jk} \rangle$$

and one can choose an index k such that

$$\omega \in \forall_j \langle B_{jk} \rangle$$

Then:

$$\forall_j [\omega \in \langle B_{jk} \rangle]$$

$$\forall_j [(B_{jk}, 0) \in \omega]$$

$$\forall_j \exists_i (A_i < B_{jk}) \quad (\text{definition of } \omega)$$

$$\forall_j \exists_i (\langle A_i \rangle \subset \langle B_{jk} \rangle) \quad (\text{because of MON})$$

Therefore, for all j ,
 $(\forall_i \langle A_i \rangle) \subset \langle B_{jk} \rangle$

and thus

$$\begin{aligned} F &= \forall_i \langle A_i \rangle \\ &\subset \forall_j \langle B_{jk} \rangle \\ &= F_k \end{aligned}$$

QED

L.5.28 There exist $D_1, \dots, D_n \in \mathcal{U}$ with $(\forall_j \langle D_j \rangle) = \emptyset$.

Proof: It suffices to set $n := 1$ and $D_1 := \mathbf{o}$.

QED

Definition D.5.8 For $A_1, \dots, A_n \in \mathcal{U}$, we define:

$$\rho^\delta(A_1, \dots, A_n) := \inf \{ \sum_j \delta(A_j, D_j) \mid D_1, \dots, D_n \in \mathcal{U} \wedge (\forall_j \langle D_j \rangle) = \emptyset \}$$

The value of $\rho^\delta(A_1, \dots, A_n)$ always lies in the interval $[0, \infty]$.

L.5.29 The mapping ρ^δ is monotonic in the sense that for any sequences $A_1, \dots, A_n \in \mathcal{U}$ and $B_1, \dots, B_m \in \mathcal{U}$,

$$(\forall_j \langle A_j \rangle) \subset (\forall_k \langle B_k \rangle) \Rightarrow \rho^\delta(A_1, \dots, A_n) \leq \rho^\delta(B_1, \dots, B_m)$$

Proof: Let $(\forall_j \langle A_j \rangle) \subset (\forall_k \langle B_k \rangle)$. If $(\forall_j \langle A_j \rangle) = \emptyset$, then $\rho^\delta(A_1, \dots, A_n) = 0$, and there is nothing to prove. Otherwise, according to L.5.25, there is a mapping of the index ranges

$$\sigma : \{1, \dots, m\} \rightarrow \{1, \dots, n\}$$

such that for all $k \in \{1, \dots, m\}$,

$$A_{\sigma(k)} < B_k$$

For $\varepsilon > 0$, let $D_1, \dots, D_m \in \mathcal{U}$ with $(\forall_k \langle D_k \rangle) = \emptyset$ and

$$\rho^\delta(B_1, \dots, B_m) + \varepsilon \geq \sum_k \delta(B_k, D_k)$$

Due to L.5.26 and the monotonicity of δ , it can be assumed without loss of generality that the D_k are pairwise commutable with $\bigcap_k D_k = \mathbf{o}$.

For each j , let

$$K(j) := \sigma^{-1}(j)$$

and

$$G_j := \bigcap_{k \in K(j)} D_k$$

The G_j are pairwise commutable as well and they satisfy

$$\bigcap_j G_j = \mathbf{o}$$

Using SEC, it follows that $(\forall_j \langle G_j \rangle) = \emptyset$.

Now

$$\begin{aligned} \rho^\delta(A_1, \dots, A_n) &\leq \sum_j \delta(A_j, G_j) && \text{(definition of } \rho^\delta) \\ &\leq \sum_j \sum_{k \in K(j)} \delta(A_j, D_k) && \text{(L.5.23)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\leq \sum_j \sum_{k \in K(j)} \delta(B_k, D_k) && \text{(monotonicity of } \delta) \\
 &= \sum_k \delta(B_k, D_k) \\
 &\leq \rho^\delta(B_1, \dots, B_m) + \varepsilon
 \end{aligned}$$

Since this applies to all ε , it follows that

$$\rho^\delta(A_1, \dots, A_n) \leq \rho^\delta(B_1, \dots, B_m)$$

and thus the monotonicity of ρ^δ is proven. **QED**

L.5.30 For any $A_1, \dots, A_n \in \mathcal{U}$ and $B_1, \dots, B_m \in \mathcal{U}$,

$$(\forall_j \langle A_j \rangle) = (\forall_k \langle B_k \rangle) \Rightarrow \rho^\delta(A_1, \dots, A_n) = \rho^\delta(B_1, \dots, B_m)$$

Proof: This follows directly from L.5.29. **QED**

Definition D.5.9 Based on L.5.30, a mapping

$$\rho : \mathcal{A}^\wedge \rightarrow [0, \infty]$$

can be defined by

$$\rho(\forall_j \langle A_j \rangle) := \rho^\delta(A_1, \dots, A_n) \quad (\text{for } A_1, \dots, A_n \in \mathcal{U})$$

Theorem T.5.1 For all $A_1, \dots, A_n \in \mathcal{U}$,

$$\rho(\forall_j \langle A_j \rangle) = \inf \{ \sum_j \delta(A_j, D_j) \mid D_1, \dots, D_n \in \mathcal{U} \wedge \perp_j D_j \}$$

Proof: The direction “ \leq ” of the theorem follows from the definition of ρ^δ and from the fact that for commutable subspaces D_1, \dots, D_n of \mathcal{H} with $\bigcap_j D_j = 0$, we always have

$$(\forall_j \langle D_j \rangle) = \emptyset.$$

In order to prove the direction “ \geq ”, let $D_1, \dots, D_n < \mathcal{H}$ with $(\forall_j \langle D_j \rangle) = \emptyset$ and, in addition,

$$d := \sum_j \delta(A_j, D_j)$$

According to L.5.26, there are commutable E_j with $\bigcap_j E_j = 0$ and $D_j < E_j$ for every j .

Let

$$e := \sum_j \delta(A_j, E_j)$$

All that remains to be shown is that $e \leq d$. However, for all j :

$$\delta(A_j, E_j) \leq \delta(A_j, D_j) + \delta(D_j, E_j)$$

Because of $D_j < E_j$, we have $\delta(D_j, E_j) = 0$ and thus

$$\delta(A_j, E_j) \leq \delta(A_j, D_j)$$

It follows that $e \leq d$, as desired. **QED**

4. Definition of the outer measure μ on the algebra \mathcal{A} and its explicit representation

Definition D.5.10 Let f be the function defined by

$$f(x) := x^2 \quad (\text{for } x \in [0, \infty])$$

Then f is a bijective, strictly increasing, and continuous mapping from $[0, \infty]$ to $[0, \infty]$.

Definition D.5.11 If \mathcal{M} is any non-empty set of outer measures on the algebra \mathcal{A} , we define:

$$\mu(\mathcal{A}) := \sup \{ \mu'(\mathcal{A}) \mid \mu' \in \mathcal{M} \} \quad (\text{for all } \mathcal{A} \in \mathcal{A})$$

It can be easily shown that μ is an outer measure as well. We call this outer measure the supremum of \mathcal{M} and denote it by $\sup(\mathcal{M})$.

Definition D.5.12 We define \mathcal{M} as the set of all outer measures μ' on \mathcal{A} that satisfy the condition

$$(*) \quad \mu'|_{\mathcal{A}^\wedge} \leq \rho^2 \quad (\mu'|_{\mathcal{A}^\wedge} \text{ denotes the restriction of } \mu' \text{ on } \mathcal{A}^\wedge)$$

Since the trivial outer measure $\mu_0 \equiv 0$ belongs to \mathcal{M} , \mathcal{M} is not empty. Therefore, we can define the outer measure μ on \mathcal{A} as:

$$\mu := \sup(\mathcal{M})$$

L.5.31 The outer measure μ satisfies condition $(*)$ and thus belongs to \mathcal{M} .

Proof: The statement follows directly from the definition of μ . **QED**

Definition D.5.13 For every $\mathcal{A} \in \mathcal{A}$, let:

$$\psi(\mathcal{A}) := \inf \{ \sum_j f(\rho(F_j)) \mid F_1, F_2, \dots \in \mathcal{A}^\wedge \text{ and } \mathcal{A} \subset \exists_j F_j \}$$

L.5.32 ψ is an outer measure.

Proof:

a) $\psi(\emptyset) = 0$: To prove this, let $F_j := \langle o \rangle$ for all j (with “ o ” being the zero subspace in \mathcal{H}). Then for all j :

$$\begin{aligned} f(\rho(F_j)) &= f(\rho(\langle o \rangle)) \\ &= f(\rho(\emptyset)) \\ &= f(0) \\ &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

Because of $\emptyset \subset \exists_j F_j$, $\psi(\emptyset)$ is the infimum of a set of non-negative real numbers which contains the element 0. Thus $\psi(\emptyset)$ is itself equal to 0.

b) ψ is monotonic: Let $\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B} \in \mathcal{A}$ with $\mathcal{A} \subset \mathcal{B}$. Consequently, for all sequences $F_1, F_2, \dots \in \mathcal{A}^\wedge$ with $\mathcal{B} \subset \exists_j F_j$, we have $\mathcal{A} \subset \exists_j F_j$. Therefore, $\psi(\mathcal{A})$ is the infimum of a larger set (compared to the set defining $\psi(\mathcal{B})$) and thus is less than or equal to $\psi(\mathcal{B})$.

c) ψ is σ -subadditive: For $k \geq 1$, let $\mathcal{A}_k \in \mathcal{A}$, let $\mathcal{A} := \exists_k \mathcal{A}_k$ be the union of these sets, and let $\varepsilon > 0$. By D.5.13, there exist $F_{k,j} \in \mathcal{A}^\wedge$ with $\mathcal{A}_k \subset \exists_j F_{k,j}$ and

$$\psi(\mathcal{A}_k) + \varepsilon/2^k \geq \sum_j f(\rho(F_{k,j})) \quad (\text{for all } k)$$

We then have

$$\mathcal{A} \subset \exists_k \exists_j F_{k,j}$$

and consequently

$$\begin{aligned}
 \psi(A) &\leq \sum_{k,j} f(\rho(F_{k,j})) && \text{(because of D.5.13)} \\
 &= \sum_k \sum_j f(\rho(F_{k,j})) \\
 &\leq \sum_k [\psi(A_k) + \varepsilon/2^k] \\
 &\leq \sum_k \psi(A_k) + \varepsilon \sum_k 1/2^k \\
 &\leq \sum_k \psi(A_k) + \varepsilon
 \end{aligned}$$

Since this holds for all $\varepsilon > 0$, σ -subadditivity follows. **QED**

L.5.33 ψ satisfies condition (*).

Proof: Let $F \in \mathcal{A}^\wedge$. Let $F_1 := F$ and $F_j := \langle \emptyset \rangle$ for all $j > 1$. Since $F \subset \exists_j F_j$, it follows that:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \psi(F) &\leq \sum_j f(\rho(F_j)) \\
 &= f(\rho(F_1)) + \sum_{j>1} f(\rho(\emptyset)) \\
 &= f(\rho(F))
 \end{aligned}$$

QED

L.5.34 For every $A \in \mathcal{A}$, $\mu(A) = \psi(A)$.

Proof: Since μ satisfies condition (*), we have for all $F \in \mathcal{A}^\wedge$:

$$\mu(F) \leq f(\rho(F))$$

For $F_j \in \mathcal{A}^\wedge$ and $A \subset \exists_j F_j$ we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mu(A) &\leq \mu(\exists_j F_j) && \text{(monotonicity of } \mu) \\
 &\leq \sum_j \mu(F_j) && \text{(\sigma-subadditivity of } \mu) \\
 &\leq \sum_j f(\rho(F_j)) && \text{(because of (*))}
 \end{aligned}$$

and from this (due to D.5.13) the direction “ \leq ” of the claimed equation. On the other hand, ψ is an outer measure that satisfies condition (*). The maximality of μ then implies the direction “ \geq ” of the equation. **QED**

Theorem T.5.2 For every $A \in \mathcal{A}$, the value of μ can be given in a closed form as:

$$\mu(A) = \inf \{ \sum_j \rho(F_j) \mid F_1, F_2, \dots \in \mathcal{A}^\wedge \text{ and } A \subset \cup_j F_j \}$$

Here, F_1, F_2, \dots is a finite or infinite sequence of elements of \mathcal{A}^\wedge .

Proof: T.5.2 follows directly from L.5.34 and the definitions of ψ and f . **QED**

5. On the continuity of ρ and μ

L.5.35 The following continuity condition applies to the mapping ρ :

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{MON}^\delta \quad \rho(\forall_j \langle A_j \rangle) - \rho(\forall_j \langle B_j \rangle) &\leq \sum_j \delta(A_j, B_j) \\
 &\text{(for any } A_1, \dots, A_n \in \mathcal{U} \text{ and } B_1, \dots, B_n \in \mathcal{U})
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof: Due to the definition of ρ^δ , for every $\varepsilon > 0$ there are elements $D_1, \dots, D_n \in \mathcal{U}$ with

$$(\forall_j \langle D_j \rangle) = \emptyset$$

and

$$\rho(\forall_j \langle B_j \rangle) + \varepsilon \geq \sum_j \delta(B_j, D_j)$$

The triangle inequality for δ yields

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_j \delta(A_j, D_j) &\leq \sum_j \delta(A_j, B_j) + \sum_j \delta(B_j, D_j) \\ &\leq \sum_j \delta(A_j, B_j) + \rho_\delta(\forall_j \langle B_j \rangle) + \varepsilon \end{aligned}$$

Due to the definition of ρ^δ ,

$$\rho(\forall_j \langle A_j \rangle) \leq \sum_j \delta(A_j, D_j)$$

and thus

$$\rho(\forall_j \langle A_j \rangle) \leq \sum_j \delta(A_j, B_j) + \rho(\forall_j \langle B_j \rangle) + \varepsilon$$

for all $\varepsilon > 0$. This implies the claimed inequality. **QED**

L.5.36 For the outer measure μ ,

$$(**) \mu|_{\mathcal{A}^\wedge} = \rho^2$$

Proof: By a covering of $A \in \mathcal{A}$ with elements of \mathcal{A}^\wedge we mean a sequence $F_1, F_2, \dots \in \mathcal{A}^\wedge$ with $A \subset \bigcup_j F_j$. The value of this covering is given by the sum

$$\sum_j f(\rho(F_j))$$

Due to T.5.2, the value $\mu(A)$ is given by the infimum of the values of all possible coverings of A with elements of \mathcal{A}^\wedge . If there is a minimal covering in this sense, then $\mu(A)$ is simply equal to the value of this covering.

From L.5.27 and the monotonicity of ρ and f , it follows that there is no covering of $A \in \mathcal{A}^\wedge$ that has a smaller value than the special covering consisting only of A itself. Accordingly, not only does condition (*) apply to μ , but also (**). **QED**

L.5.37 The following continuity condition applies to the outer measure μ :

$$\begin{aligned} \text{MON}^{\delta, f} \quad f^{-1}(\mu(\forall_j \langle A_j \rangle)) - f^{-1}(\mu(\forall_j \langle B_j \rangle)) &\leq \sum_j \delta(A_j, B_j) \\ &\text{(for any } A_1, \dots, A_n \in \mathcal{U} \text{ and } B_1, \dots, B_n \in \mathcal{U}) \end{aligned}$$

Proof: Since ρ satisfies the condition MON^δ , it immediately follows from (**) that μ satisfies $\text{MON}^{\delta, f}$. **QED**

Theorem T.5.3 Since μ satisfies the condition $\text{MON}^{\delta, f}$, μ is continuous in the sense of

$$\begin{aligned} \forall_j (A_j \approx B_j) &\Rightarrow \mu(\forall_j \langle A_j \rangle) \approx \mu(\forall_j \langle B_j \rangle) \\ &\text{(for } A_1, \dots, A_n \in \mathcal{U} \text{ and } B_1, \dots, B_n \in \mathcal{U}) \end{aligned}$$

Proof: From $A_j \approx B_j$ it follows that both $\delta(A_j, B_j) \approx 0$ and $\delta(B_j, A_j) \approx 0$ hold. Applying L.5.37, we immediately obtain what is claimed by the theorem. **QED**

6. The validity of common equations for μ and the logical consistency of the theory

In this section we show that certain equations, which would be expected to hold in quantum theory, do apply to μ , for example, $\mu(\langle A \rangle | \langle [\varphi] \rangle) = |\pi_A \varphi|^2$. Moreover, the theory turns out to be logically consistent.

L.5.38 For $A, B < \mathcal{H}$,

$$\rho(\langle A \rangle \wedge \langle B \rangle) \geq |\pi_A \pi_B|$$

Proof: If we assume

$$\rho(\langle A \rangle \wedge \langle B \rangle) < |\pi_A \pi_B|$$

then it follows by T.5.1 that there exist commutable $D, E < \mathcal{H}$ with

$$D \cap E = 0$$

and

$$\delta(A, D) + \delta(B, E) < |\pi_A \pi_B|$$

Thus, because of $E \perp D$ and $E < D^\perp$,

$$\begin{aligned} \delta(A, D) + \delta(B, D^\perp) &\leq \delta(A, D) + \delta(B, E) \\ &< |\pi_A \pi_B| \end{aligned} \quad (\text{L.5.20})$$

On the other hand:

$$\begin{aligned} |\pi_A \pi_B| &= |\pi_A \pi_{D^\perp} \pi_B + \pi_A \pi_D \pi_B| \\ &\leq |\pi_A \pi_{D^\perp} \pi_B| + |\pi_A \pi_D \pi_B| \quad (\text{L.5.8}) \\ &\leq |\pi_A \pi_{D^\perp}| + |\pi_D \pi_B| \quad (\text{L.5.16 and L.5.15}) \\ &= \delta(A, D) + \delta(B, D^\perp) \quad (\text{D.5.6 and L.5.14}) \end{aligned}$$

That is a contradiction. **QED**

L.5.39 For $A_1, \dots, A_n < \mathcal{H}$ and commutable $D_1, \dots, D_n < \mathcal{H}$ with $\bigcap_j D_j = 0$,

$$\mu(\forall_j \langle A_j \rangle) \leq [\sum_j \delta(A_j, D_j)]^2$$

Proof: It is

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(\forall_j \langle A_j \rangle) &\leq \rho^2(\forall_j \langle A_j \rangle) \\ &\leq [\sum_j \delta(A_j, D_j)]^2 \quad (\text{according to T.5.1}) \end{aligned} \quad \text{QED}$$

L.5.40 For $A < \mathcal{H}$ and commutable $D_1, \dots, D_n < \mathcal{H}$,

$$|\pi_A \pi_{\bigoplus_k D_k}|^2 \leq \sum_k |\pi_A \pi_{D_k}|^2$$

Proof: For all k , let

$$E_k := D_k \cap [\bigoplus_{j < k} D_j]^\perp$$

Then the E_k are pairwise orthogonal and we have

$$\bigoplus_k E_k = \bigoplus_k D_k$$

Furthermore, let (a_j) be an orthonormal basis of \mathcal{H} , such that A is generated by a subset $\{a_j \mid j \in J_A\}$ of this basis. Then:

$$\begin{aligned} |\pi_A \pi_{\bigoplus_k D_k}|^2 &= \sum_j |(\pi_A \pi_{\bigoplus_k D_k})^* a_j|^2 && \text{(L.5.4)} \\ &= \sum_j |\pi_{\bigoplus_k D_k} \pi_A a_j|^2 \\ &= \sum_{j \in J_A} |\pi_{\bigoplus_k D_k} a_j|^2 \\ &= \sum_{j \in J_A} |\pi_{\bigoplus_k E_k} a_j|^2 \\ &= \sum_{j \in J_A} |\sum_k \pi_{E_k} a_j|^2 \\ &= \sum_{j \in J_A} \sum_k |\pi_{E_k} a_j|^2 && \text{(Pythagoras)} \\ &= \sum_k \sum_{j \in J_A} |\pi_{E_k} a_j|^2 \\ &= \sum_k \sum_j |\pi_{E_k} \pi_A a_j|^2 \\ &= \sum_k \sum_j |(\pi_A \pi_{E_k})^* a_j|^2 \\ &= \sum_k |\pi_A \pi_{E_k}|^2 && \text{(L.5.4)} \\ &= \sum_k |\pi_A \pi_{D_k} \pi_{E_k}|^2 && \text{(since } E_k < D_k) \\ &\leq \sum_k |\pi_A \pi_{D_k}|^2 && \text{(L.5.16)} \end{aligned}$$

QED

L.5.41 For $A < \mathcal{H}$ and commutable $E_1, \dots, E_n < \mathcal{H}$,

$$\mu(\langle A \rangle \wedge \exists_s \langle E_s \rangle) \geq |\pi_A \pi_{\bigoplus_s E_s}|^2$$

Proof: We can assume without loss of generality that for each s :

$$\langle A \rangle \wedge \langle E_s \rangle \neq \emptyset$$

since, if there were any index s with

$$\langle A \rangle \wedge \langle E_s \rangle = \emptyset$$

then, due to L.5.26,

$$A \perp E_s$$

and one could remove E_s on both sides of the inequality without changing anything about the expressions

$$\langle A \rangle \wedge \exists_s \langle E_s \rangle$$

and

$$\pi_A \pi_{\bigoplus_s E_s}$$

We now assume that

$$\mu(\langle A \rangle \wedge \exists_s \langle E_s \rangle) < |\pi_A \pi_{\oplus_s E_s}|^2$$

Then for

$$G := \langle A \rangle \wedge \exists_s \langle E_s \rangle$$

due to the explicit representation of μ by

$$\mu(G) = \inf \{ \sum_k \rho^2(F_k) \mid F_1, F_2, \dots \in \mathcal{A}^\wedge \text{ and } G \subset \exists_k F_k \} \quad (\text{T.5.2})$$

there exists a finite or infinite sequence F_1, F_2, \dots of elements of \mathcal{A}^\wedge with

$$G \subset \exists_k F_k$$

and

$$(***) \sum_k \rho^2(F_k) < |\pi_A \pi_{\oplus_s E_s}|^2$$

Since elements of the form $\langle o \rangle$ can always be added, the sequence of the F_k , without loss of generality, can be assumed to have infinitely many elements.

Now, for every s ,

$$\langle A \rangle \wedge \langle E_s \rangle \subset \exists_k F_k$$

and according to L.5.27, there is an index k with

$$\langle A \rangle \wedge \langle E_s \rangle \subset F_k$$

For each s , we select $f(s)$ from the index range of k such that

$$\langle A \rangle \wedge \langle E_s \rangle \subset F_{f(s)}$$

So, for all k , we have

$$\forall_{s \in f^{-1}(k)} [\langle A \rangle \wedge \langle E_s \rangle \subset F_k]$$

For each k , let

$$D_k := \oplus \{ E_s \mid s \in f^{-1}(k) \}$$

The D_k are (just like the E_s) pairwise commutable, and we have

$$\oplus_k D_k = \oplus_s E_s$$

Since there is only a finite number of indices s , only a finite number of these D_k differ from the zero subspace.

Because of $F_k \in \mathcal{A}^\wedge$, there exists $B_{jk} < \mathcal{H}$ with

$$F_k = \forall_j \langle B_{jk} \rangle$$

It now follows for all k :

$$\forall_{s \in f^{-1}(k)} [\langle A \rangle \wedge \langle E_s \rangle \subset \forall_j \langle B_{jk} \rangle]$$

Then, according to L.5.25 and because of $\langle A \rangle \wedge \langle E_s \rangle \neq \emptyset$,

$$\forall_{s \in f^{-1}(k)} \forall_j [A < B_{jk} \vee E_s < B_{jk}]$$

Consequently, for all k ,

$$\forall_j [A < B_{jk} \vee \forall_{s \in f^{-1}(k)} (E_s < B_{jk})]$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \forall_j [A < B_{jk} \vee D_k < B_{jk}] \\
 & \forall_j [(\langle A \rangle \subset \langle B_{jk} \rangle) \vee (\langle D_k \rangle \subset \langle B_{jk} \rangle)] \quad (\text{because of MON}) \\
 & \forall_j [\langle A \rangle \wedge \langle D_k \rangle \subset \langle B_{jk} \rangle] \\
 & \langle A \rangle \wedge \langle D_k \rangle \subset \forall_j \langle B_{jk} \rangle \\
 & \rho^2(\langle A \rangle \wedge \langle D_k \rangle) \leq \rho^2(\forall_j \langle B_{jk} \rangle) \quad (\text{since } \rho \text{ is monotonic})
 \end{aligned}$$

It is therefore

$$\begin{aligned}
 |\pi_A \pi_{\oplus_S E_S}|^2 &= |\pi_A \pi_{\oplus_k D_k}|^2 \\
 &\leq \Sigma_k |\pi_A \pi_{D_k}|^2 \quad (\text{according to L.5.40}) \\
 &\leq \Sigma_k \rho^2(\langle A \rangle \wedge \langle D_k \rangle) \quad (\text{according to L.5.38}) \\
 &\leq \Sigma_k \rho^2(\forall_j \langle B_{jk} \rangle) \\
 &= \Sigma_k \rho^2(F_k)
 \end{aligned}$$

which contradicts (***) .

QED

L.5.42 For $A < \mathcal{H}$ and commutable $E_1, \dots, E_n < \mathcal{H}$,

$$\mu(\langle A \rangle \wedge \forall_j \langle E_j \rangle) \leq |\pi_A \pi_{\cap_j E_j}|^2$$

Proof: Let $E := \cap_j E_j$. Then E_j and E^\perp are commutable with

$$\cap_j E_j \cap E^\perp = o$$

Because of L.5.39, we get:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mu(\langle A \rangle \wedge \forall_j \langle E_j \rangle) &\leq [\delta(A, E^\perp) + \Sigma_j \delta(E_j, E_j)]^2 \\
 &= \delta^2(A, E^\perp) \quad (\text{L.5.19}) \\
 &= |\pi_A \pi_{(E^\perp)^\perp}|^2 \quad (\text{D.5.6}) \\
 &= |\pi_A \pi_E|^2 \\
 &= |\pi_A \pi_{\cap_j E_j}|^2
 \end{aligned}$$

QED

For the following, we formulate a general assumption:

(+) Let S be a finite index set and, for each $s \in S$, let J_s be a finite index set as well. For $s \in S$ and $j \in J_s$ let $E_{js} < \mathcal{H}$, and let all these subspaces be commutable with each other.

L.5.43 Under the assumption (+), let

$$\begin{aligned}
 J &:= \times_{s \in S} J_s \\
 &:= \{ g : S \rightarrow \cup_s J_s \mid \forall_{s \in S} [g(s) \in J_s] \}
 \end{aligned}$$

be the Cartesian product of the index sets J_s . Then the following hold:

$$(1) (\exists_{s \in S} \forall_{j \in J_s} \langle E_{js} \rangle) = \forall_{g \in J} \exists_{s \in S} \langle E_{g(s), s} \rangle$$

and

$$(2) \bigoplus_{s \in S} \bigcap_{j \in J_s} E_{js} = \bigcap_{g \in J} \bigoplus_{s \in S} E_{g(s),s}$$

Proof: Statement (1) is based on the distributive law of set theory. It is a generalization of the following statement:

$$\begin{aligned} & (A \cap B \cap C) \cup (D \cap E) \\ &= [A \cup (D \cap E)] \cap [B \cup (D \cap E)] \cap [C \cup (D \cap E)] \\ &= (A \cup D) \cap (A \cup E) \cap (B \cup D) \cap (B \cup E) \cap (C \cup D) \cap (C \cup E) \end{aligned}$$

Statement (2) follows in a completely analogous manner, since all E_{js} , due to their commutability, can be represented by *one* orthonormal basis such that each E_{js} is generated by a subset of this same basis. **QED**

L.5.44 Under the assumption (+),

$$\mu(\langle A \rangle \wedge \exists_s \forall_j \langle E_{js} \rangle) \leq |\pi_A \pi_{\bigoplus_s \bigcap_j E_{js}}|^2$$

Proof: Let

$$J := \{ g : S \rightarrow \bigcup_s J_s \mid \forall_s \in S [g(s) \in J_s] \}$$

Since for all $g \in J$ and $s \in S$,

$$E_{g(s),s} < \bigoplus_s E_{g(s),s}$$

it follows by MON that

$$\langle E_{g(s),s} \rangle \subset \langle \bigoplus_s E_{g(s),s} \rangle$$

and since this applies to every s , we have for all $g \in J$:

$$(\exists_s \langle E_{g(s),s} \rangle) \subset \langle \bigoplus_s E_{g(s),s} \rangle$$

It now follows that

$$\begin{aligned} & \mu(\langle A \rangle \wedge \exists_s \forall_j \langle E_{js} \rangle) \\ &= \mu(\langle A \rangle \wedge \forall_{g \in J} \exists_s \langle E_{g(s),s} \rangle) && \text{(L.5.43 (1))} \\ &\leq \mu(\langle A \rangle \wedge \forall_{g \in J} \langle \bigoplus_s E_{g(s),s} \rangle) && \text{(since } \mu \text{ is monotonic)} \\ &\leq |\pi_A \pi_{\bigcap_{g \in J} \bigoplus_s E_{g(s),s}}|^2 && \text{(L.5.42)} \\ &= |\pi_A \pi_{\bigoplus_s \bigcap_j E_{js}}|^2 && \text{(L.5.43 (2))} \end{aligned}$$

QED

L.5.45 Under the assumption (+),

$$\mu(\langle A \rangle \wedge \exists_s \forall_j \langle E_{js} \rangle) \geq |\pi_A \pi_{\bigoplus_s \bigcap_j E_{js}}|^2$$

Proof: For all $j \in J_s$,

$$\bigcap_{j \in J_s} E_{js} < E_{js}$$

and thus (due to MON):

$$\langle \bigcap_{j \in J_s} E_{js} \rangle \subset \forall_{j \in J_s} \langle E_{js} \rangle$$

Now:

$$\begin{aligned} |\pi_A \pi_{\oplus_s \cap_j E_{js}}|^2 &\leq \mu(\langle A \rangle \wedge \exists_s \langle \cap_j E_{js} \rangle) && \text{(L.5.41)} \\ &\leq \mu(\langle A \rangle \wedge \exists_s \forall_j \langle E_{js} \rangle) && \text{(since } \mu \text{ is monotonic)} \end{aligned}$$

QED

Theorem T.5.4 Under the assumption (+),

$$\mu(\langle A \rangle \wedge \exists_s \forall_j \langle E_{sj} \rangle) = |\pi_A \pi_{\oplus_s \cap_j E_{sj}}|^2$$

and in the case of $\dim A < \infty$,

$$\mu(\langle A \rangle \wedge \exists_s \forall_j \langle E_{sj} \rangle) = \text{tr}(\pi_A \pi_{\oplus_s \cap_j E_{sj}})$$

Proof: The theorem follows directly from L.5.44, L.5.45, and L.5.12.

QED

For every $B < \mathcal{H}$ with $0 < \dim B < \infty$, by

$$W_B := \pi_B / \text{tr} \pi_B$$

we define a statistical operator, i.e., a non-negative definite operator with $\text{tr} W_B = 1$. Applying T.5.4 to the pairwise commutable $E_{s,j} < \mathcal{H}$, we get:

$$\mu(\exists_s \forall_j \langle E_{s,j} \rangle | \langle B \rangle) = \text{tr}(\pi_{\oplus_s \cap_j E_{s,j}} W_B)$$

In particular, the following equation holds for all $A < \mathcal{H}$:

$$\mu(\langle A \rangle | \langle B \rangle) = \text{tr} \pi_A \pi_B / \text{tr} \pi_B$$

From this, using the Schrödinger equation, we obtain:

Theorem T.5.5 For every point in time t and for all $A, B < \mathcal{H}$ with $0 < \dim B < \infty$,

$$\mu(\langle A, t \rangle | \langle B, t \rangle) = \text{tr} \pi_A \pi_B / \text{tr} \pi_B$$

and as a special case, for every $\varphi \in \mathcal{H}$,

$$\mu(\langle A \rangle | \langle [\varphi] \rangle) = |\pi_A \varphi|^2$$

The constructive approach to the formation of μ guarantees that μ is defined on the entire algebra \mathcal{A} and has the specified properties without any contradictions arising, comparable to those that are related to Bell's inequality. According to T.1.1, the axiom system AX is logically consistent as well. This implies the consistency of the entire theory formulated here, and we obtain:

Theorem T.5.6 The theory given by the axiom system AX and the outer measure μ is logically consistent.

B6. Document relationships

This chapter describes the conditions under which a document relationship exists between two events.

The immediate perception by a (macroscopic) subject is limited to macroscopic events. Such events have the form (A,t) with $A \in \mathcal{U}$ and $t \in T$, where A is a macroscopic property of the universe. These events can be directly perceived by a subject at time t . However, the empirical knowledge of a subject at time t may also include events $(A,s) \in \mathcal{E}$ that lie in the past, i.e., events with $s < t$.

The subject can have empirical knowledge of such a past event (A,s) at time t only if a document of (A,s) exists. Such a document must be perceptible to the subject at time t , i.e., it must be a macroscopic event of the form (D,t) with $D \in \mathcal{U}$. Even if the subject directly remembers the event (A,s) , such a document exists. Since the subject itself is part of the universe, every memory corresponds to a physical engram and thus to a document of the past event.

This raises the question of when a document relationship exists between two events. In the simplest case, such a relationship exists between $(A',s) \in \mathcal{E}$ and $(D',t) \in \mathcal{E}$ if and only if the two events are equivalent based on the law of motion, i.e., if with the abbreviations

$$A := U_{-s}A'$$

and

$$D := U_{-t}D'$$

we have

$$(*) \quad A = D$$

In this case, we can speak of an unconditional document relationship: The event $(A',s) \in \mathcal{E}$ is “unconditionally documented” by $(D',t) \in \mathcal{E}$ if $(*)$ is valid.

However, this concept of document relationships is insufficient for the general case. Consider the case of a star orbited by a planet, for example. The star generates a regular flow of “particles” that stream out into space. A “shadow” forms behind the planet, i.e., a zone with lower particle density. This shadow documents the location of the planet. Due to the finite speed at which the particles move, this occurs with a time delay. Thus, an event is documented at a later point in time.

If we use (A',s) to describe the event that the planet was at a certain location, and (D',t) to describe the event that, at a later point in time t , there was a low particle density at the corresponding location in space further away from the star, then there is a document relationship between (A',s) and (D',t) . However, this relationship only exists if the star was present as a particle source at an earlier point in time $r < s$. The document relationship therefore only exists under a certain physical *condition*. In the simplest case, this condition is just another event (B',r) with $B' < \mathcal{H}$.

In most cases, the relationship between a document and the documented event is not based solely on the law of motion, but also on the existence of a certain condition. For example, the relationship between a photo (as a document) and a bird depicted in it (as the documented fact) is based on the fact that a camera ready to take a picture was available beforehand and

that the process was not disturbed. Without these prerequisites, the photo would not have been created as a document of the depicted fact.

With the additional definition

$$B := U_{-r}B'$$

the existence of a document relationship between (A',s) and (D',t) based on the condition (B',r) can be described in quantum theory by the relationships

$$(1) \pi_{D^\perp} \pi_A \pi_B = 0$$

and

$$(2) \pi_D \pi_{A^\perp} \pi_B = 0$$

Here, (1) states that if events (B',r) and (A',s) are given, then event $((D')^\perp, t)$ cannot occur. Similarly, (2) states that if events (B',r) and $((A')^\perp, s)$ are given, then event (D',t) cannot occur.

It can be shown that the two equations (1) and (2) are equivalent to the simple equation

$$(3) \pi_D \pi_B = \pi_A \pi_B$$

If this equation is satisfied, we say that the event $(A',s) \in \mathcal{E}$ is documented by $(D',t) \in \mathcal{E}$ under the condition (B',r) .

To justify equations (1) and (2), let us consider the case where the document relationship can also be described classically. This applies, for example, to the case discussed above, where a planet creates a shadow in the radiation of a star. A macroscopic property can be represented both quantum-theoretically by a subspace $S < \mathcal{H}$ and classically by a subset $\underline{S} \subset Z$. (As before, Z is the phase space of the universe.) The complementary property $S^\perp < \mathcal{H}$ then corresponds to the set complement $Z \setminus \underline{S}$, and if changes over time can be described classically in a certain time interval $[0, \tau]$, i.e., if “quantum effects” do not play any role here, then $U_\tau S$ and $\beta_\tau(\underline{S})$ correspond to each other as well.

In terms of classical modeling, let \underline{A} , \underline{D} , and \underline{B} be the subsets of Z that correspond to the properties which are modeled by A , D , and $B < \mathcal{H}$ in quantum theory. With definitions given in Chapter B2, we let

$$\langle \underline{A}, t \rangle := \langle \underline{A}, t \rangle_0 \cap \Omega_{AX} \quad (\text{for all } \underline{A} \in \mathcal{U} \text{ and } t \in T)$$

as well as

$$\langle \underline{A} \rangle := \langle \underline{A}, 0 \rangle \quad (\text{for all } \underline{A} \in \mathcal{U})$$

Now, under the condition (\underline{B}, r) , there is a document relationship between (\underline{A}, s) and (\underline{D}, t) if the equivalence of $\langle \underline{A}, s \rangle$ and $\langle \underline{D}, t \rangle$ follows from $\langle \underline{B}, r \rangle$. This is the case if the following two inclusions hold:

$$(a1) \langle \underline{B}, r \rangle \wedge \langle \underline{A}, s \rangle \subset \langle \underline{D}, t \rangle$$

$$(a2) \langle \underline{B}, r \rangle \wedge \langle \underline{D}, t \rangle \subset \langle \underline{A}, s \rangle$$

With the definitions

$$\underline{A} := \beta_{-s}(\underline{A})$$

$$\underline{D} := \beta_{-t}(\underline{D})$$

$$\underline{B} := \beta_{-r}(\underline{B})$$

this is equivalent to

- (b1) $\langle \underline{B} \rangle \wedge \langle \underline{A} \rangle \subset \langle \underline{D} \rangle$
- (b2) $\langle \underline{B} \rangle \wedge \langle \underline{D} \rangle \subset \langle \underline{A} \rangle$

If for every subset $C \subset Z$ we define the indicator function

$$\mathbf{1}_C : Z \rightarrow \{0,1\}$$

by

$$\mathbf{1}_C(z) = 1 \iff z \in C \quad (\text{for all } z \in Z)$$

then (b1) and (b2) can be reformulated as

$$(c1) \mathbf{1}_{Z \setminus \underline{D}} \mathbf{1}_{\underline{A}} \mathbf{1}_{\underline{B}} = 0$$

$$(c2) \mathbf{1}_{\underline{D}} \mathbf{1}_{Z \setminus \underline{A}} \mathbf{1}_{\underline{B}} = 0$$

The two relationships (c1) and (c2) can be combined into the equation:

$$(c) \mathbf{1}_{\underline{A}} \mathbf{1}_{\underline{B}} = \mathbf{1}_{\underline{D}} \mathbf{1}_{\underline{B}}$$

For simplicity, we assume (without loss of generality) that $r = 0$. Provided that, in the relevant time interval $[0,t]$, quantum effects do not play a role for the document relationship under consideration, A and \underline{A} , D and \underline{D} , as well as B and \underline{B} also correspond to each other. By transferring equations (c1) and (c2) into the quantum-theoretical model, we obtain the two statements

$$(1) \pi_{\underline{D}^\perp} \pi_A \pi_B = 0$$

$$(2) \pi_D \pi_{\underline{A}^\perp} \pi_B = 0$$

The existence of a document is an objective physical fact. This applies to the shadow cast by a planet orbiting a star, it applies to a film recording the movement of a bird (or the course of a quantum experiment), but it also applies to the memories of a subject who is itself part of the universe.

It is possible that the document relationship between (A',s) and (D',t) does not only depend on one event (B',r) , but on several events $(B'_0,r_0), \dots, (B'_m,r_m) \in \mathcal{E}$ as a condition, with points in time $r_0 \leq \dots \leq r_m < s$. With

$$B_j := U_{-r_j} B'_j \quad (\text{for } j \in \{0, \dots, m\})$$

equation (3) then has to be replaced by:

$$(3') \pi_D \pi_{B_m} \dots \pi_{B_0} = \pi_A \pi_{B_m} \dots \pi_{B_0}$$

This equation can also be justified by the classical analogue.

Equation (3') represents an ideal situation. In general, this equation will only be valid approximately. However, when dealing with truly macroscopic events, we can come very close to exact equality.

B7. Macroscopic experiments and their probability measure

In this chapter, we describe when a sequence of possible events can be considered empirically accessible and what a macroscopic experiment is. Then we show how a Kolmogorov probability measure, consistent with the probabilistic law of quantum theory, can be defined on the algebra of all possible results of such an experiment.

Many definitions, lemmas, and proofs in this and the following chapter are rather “technical” and may be hard to understand. However, this is inevitable because the structures we have to consider here are quite complex. We are dealing with several alternatives, each with a different number of possible outcomes, additionally provided with a network of conditional document relationships (as well as measurement relationships). It would be possible to consider just simple examples instead, but these could not replace the proof of the general case. At the same time, mathematically precise arguments are necessary.

The chapter consists of the following subsections:

1. Empirically accessible events
2. The nesting property
3. Formal representation of macroscopic experiments
4. Certain possible facts and their properties
5. Some statements about outcome constellations
6. From the outer measure μ to the probability measure for the experiment

1. Empirically accessible events

In this section, we discuss under what circumstances a finite set of events is empirically accessible from a specific point in time t . To do this, we consider a sequence of events

$$(E_1, t_1), \dots, (E_n, t_n) \in \mathcal{E}$$

with the index set

$$J := \{1, \dots, n\}$$

If these events are to be empirically accessible at time t , then for each $k \in J$, there must be a macroscopic document (F_k, t) as well as a (conditional) document relationship between the events (E_k, t_k) and (F_k, t) . The conditions that appear here (with the exception of the initial condition) must themselves be empirically accessible. We understand the concept of empirical accessibility of a set of events to mean that the conditions necessary for the existence of the document relationships belong to this same set.

With the definitions

$$A_k := U_{-t_k} E_k \quad (\text{for } k \in J)$$

$$D_k := U_{-t} F_k \quad (\text{for } k \in J)$$

$\langle A_k \rangle$ stands for the event (E_k, t_k) and $\langle D_k \rangle$ stands for its document (F_k, t) .

The document relationship between the events $\langle A_k \rangle$ and $\langle D_k \rangle$ only exists if (in addition to the initial condition $\langle UR \rangle$) certain other $\langle A_j \rangle$ are given as conditions. In this sense, we define for all $j, k \in J$:

$j \ll k \Leftrightarrow$ the document relationship between $\langle A_k \rangle$ and $\langle D_k \rangle$ only exists if $\langle A_j \rangle$ is given.

We refer to the relation \ll defined on the index set J as “dependency relation”. This dependency relation must not be cyclic. Therefore, we can arrange the events $\langle A_j \rangle$ without loss of generality such that the following holds:

$j \ll k \Rightarrow j < k$ (for all $j, k \in J$)

As a rule, the conditions under which a document relationship exists precede the documented event in time, and all events considered precede the point in time from which they are empirically accessible. Therefore, the following should hold:

$t_1 \leq \dots \leq t_n \leq t$

For every $k \in J$, by

$J_k := \{j \in J \mid j \ll k\}$

we describe the set of events $\langle A_j \rangle$ on which the document relationship between $\langle A_k \rangle$ and $\langle D_k \rangle$ depends.

Furthermore, the document relationship between $\langle A_k \rangle$ and $\langle D_k \rangle$ must exist independently of whether any of those $\langle A_j \rangle$ on which it does *not* depend is given or not (and the same applies to the associated document $\langle D_j \rangle$). For all

$j \in J \setminus J_k \setminus \{k\}$

the document relationship between $\langle A_k \rangle$ and $\langle D_k \rangle$ must therefore be independent of whether $\langle A_j \rangle$ or $\langle D_j \rangle$ has occurred. Formally, this can be described as follows:

Definition D.7.1 The events $(E_1, t_1), \dots, (E_n, t_n)$ are empirically accessible from the point in time t with the dependency relation \ll on the index set $J := \{1, \dots, n\}$, in short: t -accessible, if the following holds:

1) The dependency relation is a subrelation of $<$, i.e.,

$j \ll k \Rightarrow j < k$ (for all $j, k \in J$)

It specifies which of the events (in addition to the initial condition) must be given for a specific event (E_k, t_k) to be documented at time t .

2) For every $k \in J$, there is a macroscopic property $F_k < \mathcal{H}$, such that with the abbreviations

$A_k := U_{-t_k} E_k$

$D_k := U_{-t} F_k$

$J_k := \{j \in J \mid j \ll k\}$

for every sequence $B_1, \dots, B_n < \mathcal{H}$ that satisfies the conditions

(i) $B_j = A_j$ (for all $j \in J_k$)

(ii) $B_j \in \{A_j, D_j, \mathcal{H}\}$ (for all $j \in J \setminus J_k \setminus \{k\}$)

(iii) $B_k = \mathcal{H}$

the document relationship

$$(DR) \quad \pi_{A_k} \pi_{B_n} \dots \pi_{B_1} \pi_{UR} = \pi_{D_k} \pi_{B_n} \dots \pi_{B_1} \pi_{UR}$$

holds. By this, (F_k, t) is a document of the event (E_k, t_k) at time t .

Point (i) describes the dependency of the document relationships and states that all $\langle A_j \rangle$ on which the relationship between $\langle A_k \rangle$ and $\langle D_k \rangle$ depends must appear as a condition in the equation. Point (ii) states that for each $\langle A_j \rangle$ on which $\langle A_k \rangle$ does *not* depend, either the factor π_{A_j} or the factor π_{D_j} can be arbitrarily inserted on both sides of the equation. It describes the independence of the document relationships. (If $B_j = \mathcal{H}$, the ineffective factor $\pi_{\mathcal{H}}$ is inserted instead of π_{A_j} or π_{D_j} .) Point (iii) states that π_{A_k} or π_{D_k} will never be inserted. The subspaces D_k are pairwise commutable (since the F_k are macroscopic).

2. The nesting property

For t -accessible sequences of events, we now want to prove a “nesting property”. The significance of this property can be described as follows: Macroscopic properties of the universe that can be observed directly at the same point in time are commutable. This, in contrast, does not generally apply to non-simultaneous macroscopic events. However, if non-commutable events are empirically accessible via document relationships, they can be nested by commutable events. By this, many statements that apply to commutable events can also be proven for empirically accessible sequences of events, i.e., for events that take place at different times but are documented by commutable properties at a common point in time t . Two events (A, s) and (B, t) are called commutable if the two subspaces $U_{-s}A$ and $U_{-t}B$ are commutable.

We consider a t -accessible sequence of events

$$(E_1, t_1), \dots, (E_n, t_n) \in \mathcal{E}$$

with the dependency relation \ll on the index set

$$J := \{1, \dots, n\}$$

For this sequence of events, let the expressions F_k , A_k , D_k , and J_k be defined for each k as in D.7.1, and let the document relationship (DR) hold for each sequence $B_1, \dots, B_n < \mathcal{H}$ that satisfies conditions (i), (ii), and (iii).

For all $k \in J$, let

$$A_{k;1} := A_k$$

$$A_{k;0} := (A_k)^\perp$$

$$A_{k;\emptyset} := \mathcal{H}$$

Likewise, let

$$D_{k;1} := D_k$$

$$D_{k;0} := (D_k)^\perp$$

$$D_{k;\emptyset} := \mathcal{H}$$

Then, for every $\tau \in \{0,1,\emptyset\}$,

$$A_{k;\tau} < \mathcal{H}$$

$$D_{k;\tau} < \mathcal{H}$$

Let

$$\mathcal{W} := \{ \sigma : J \rightarrow \{0,1,\emptyset\} \mid \forall_{k \in J} [\sigma(k) \neq \emptyset \Leftrightarrow \forall_{j \ll k} \sigma(j) = 1] \}$$

be the set of “assignments” on the index set J .

Every assignment $\sigma \in \mathcal{W}$ assigns, to each index $k \in J$, either the value 0 or the value 1, or “no value at all”. The latter is done by setting $\sigma(k) = \emptyset$. A “real” value (i.e., 0 or 1) is assigned to an index k if and only if all events $\langle A_j \rangle$ on which the document relationship between $\langle A_k \rangle$ and $\langle D_k \rangle$ depends, have been assigned the value 1.

By an assignment $\sigma \in \mathcal{W}$, we want to describe how, for each $k \in J$, either A_k or $(A_k)^\perp$, or neither of the two is selected. The selection of A_k or $(A_k)^\perp$ takes place if and only if, for all j with $j \ll k$, the event A_j has been selected.

Now let:

$$\pi_\sigma := \pi_{A_n;\sigma(n)} \cdots \pi_{A_1;\sigma(1)} \quad (\text{for all } \sigma \in \mathcal{W})$$

$$M_\sigma := \bigcap_{k \in J} A_{k;\sigma(k)} \quad (\text{for all } \sigma \in \mathcal{W})$$

$$M^\wedge := \bigoplus \{ M_\sigma \mid \sigma \in \mathcal{W} \}$$

For all $k \in J$, let:

$$B_{k;\tau} := \bigoplus \{ M_\sigma \mid \sigma \in \mathcal{W} \wedge \sigma(k) = \tau \} \quad (\text{for } \tau \in \{0,1,\emptyset\})$$

$$C_{k;\tau} := B_{k;\tau} \oplus B_{k;\emptyset} \oplus (M^\wedge)^\perp \quad (\text{for } \tau \in \{0,1\})$$

$$C_{k;\emptyset} := \mathcal{H}$$

L.7.1 The M_σ are pairwise orthogonal.

Proof: Let σ and σ' be different elements of \mathcal{W} . Let k be the smallest index in which σ and σ' differ from each other. If we had $\sigma(k) = \emptyset$, then by the definition of \mathcal{W} there would be some $j \ll k$ with $\sigma(j) \neq 1$. Consequently, $\sigma'(j) \neq 1$ and thus $\sigma'(k) = \emptyset$, contradicting $\sigma(k) \neq \sigma'(k)$.

It follows that $\sigma(k) \in \{0,1\}$. In the same way, it can be shown that $\sigma'(k) \in \{0,1\}$. Because of $\sigma(k) \neq \sigma'(k)$, we can assume without loss of generality that $\sigma(k) = 1$ and $\sigma'(k) = 0$.

It follows

$$A_{k;\sigma(k)} = A_k$$

$$A_{k;\sigma'(k)} = (A_k)^\perp$$

and because of

$$M_{\sigma} < A_{k;\sigma(k)}$$

and

$$M_{\sigma'} < A_{k;\sigma'(k)}$$

we have

$$M_{\sigma} \perp M_{\sigma'}$$

QED

L.7.2 All subspaces M^{\wedge} , $B_{k;\tau}$ and $C_{k;\tau}$ are pairwise commutable.

Proof: This follows directly from the definition of these subspaces and the orthogonality of all M_{σ} . **QED**

For the following lemma, let

$$\mathcal{W}' := \{ \sigma : J \rightarrow \{0,1,\emptyset\} \mid \forall_{k \in J} [\sigma(k) \neq \emptyset \Rightarrow \forall_{j \ll k} \sigma(j) = 1] \}$$

It then follows that $W \subset \mathcal{W}'$.

L.7.3 For all $k \in J$ and $\sigma \in \mathcal{W}'$, with the abbreviations

$$G_j := A_{j;\sigma(j)} \quad (\text{for all } j \in J)$$

$$H_j := D_{j;\sigma(j)} \quad (\text{for all } j \in J)$$

and for every sequence $B_1, \dots, B_n < \mathcal{H}$ that satisfies the conditions

$$(i') \quad B_j = G_j \quad (\text{for all } j \in J_k)$$

$$(ii') \quad B_j \in \{G_j, H_j, \mathcal{H}\} \quad (\text{for all } j \in J \setminus J_k \setminus \{k\})$$

$$(iii') \quad B_k = \mathcal{H}$$

the following equation holds:

$$(DR') \quad \pi_{G_k} \pi_{B_n} \dots \pi_{B_1} \pi_{UR} = \pi_{H_k} \pi_{B_n} \dots \pi_{B_1} \pi_{UR}$$

Note: Conditions (i') to (iii') as well as (DR') are identical to the statements that appear in the definition of t-accessibility, with the only difference being that A_j has been replaced by $A_{j;\sigma(j)}$ and D_j by $D_{j;\sigma(j)}$ throughout.

Proof: For $k \in J$ and $\sigma \in \mathcal{W}'$, let B_1, \dots, B_n be a sequence that satisfies conditions (i') to (iii').

In the case of $\sigma(k) = \emptyset$, the assertion is trivial, because we then have:

$$G_k = H_k = \mathcal{H}.$$

For the case of $\sigma(k) \neq \emptyset$, the proof is carried out by complete induction on

$$r := \# \{ j \in J \mid \sigma(j) = 0 \}$$

i.e., on the number of zeros in the assignment σ .

Case $r = 0$

For all $j \ll k$, because of $\sigma(k) \neq \emptyset$ and $\sigma \in \mathcal{W}'$, we have $\sigma(j) = 1$.

Since $r = 0$, for all $j \in J$,

$$\sigma(j) \in \{1, \emptyset\}$$

and consequently:

$$G_j \in \{A_j, \mathcal{H}\}$$

$$H_j \in \{D_j, \mathcal{H}\}$$

$$B_j \in \{A_j, D_j, \mathcal{H}\} \quad (\text{due to (i'), (ii') and (iii')})$$

For $j \ll k$,

$$B_j = G_j = A_j \quad (\text{because of (i') and } \sigma(j) = 1)$$

Furthermore, due to (iii'),

$$B_k = \mathcal{H}$$

Thus, conditions (i), (ii), and (iii) are satisfied. Because of $\sigma(k) \in \{1, \emptyset\}$ and $\sigma(k) \neq \emptyset$, we have $\sigma(k) = 1$, and consequently

$$G_k = A_k \quad \text{and} \quad H_k = D_k$$

Therefore, the equation (DR') to be proven is precisely one of the document relationships (DR) which hold due to the t -accessibility of $(E_1, t_1), \dots, (E_n, t_n)$. **QED** (case $r = 0$)

Case $r > 0$ (induction step)

We assume that for all $\sigma' \in \mathcal{W}'$ with

$$r' := \# \{j \in J \mid \sigma'(j) = 0\} < r$$

and for all suitable sequences B_1, \dots, B_n , equation (DR') holds (induction hypothesis).

Let

$$v := \max \{j \in J \mid \sigma(j) = 0\}$$

be the last position in which σ has a 0. Since $r > 0$, there is at least one such position, i.e., $v \in J$ and $\sigma(v) = 0$.

Let

$$\sigma'(v) := 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma'(j) := \sigma(j) \quad (\text{for all } j \neq v)$$

$$\sigma''(v) := \emptyset \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma''(j) := \sigma(j) \quad (\text{for all } j \neq v)$$

Like σ , both σ' and σ'' belong to \mathcal{W}' .

Since σ' has fewer zeros than σ and $\sigma'(k) \neq \emptyset$, the induction hypothesis can be applied to σ' . For σ' , equation (DR') thus holds for any suitable sequence B_1, \dots, B_n . If $v \neq k$, the same applies to σ'' because $\sigma''(k) = \sigma(k) \neq \emptyset$.

Subcase $v = k$

In this case, every sequence B_1, \dots, B_n that is suitable for σ is suitable for σ' as well, since σ' only differs from σ at the index k . For brevity, we let:

$$L := \pi_{B_n} \dots \pi_{B_1} \pi_{UR}$$

By applying the induction hypothesis to σ' , with

$$G' := (G_k)^\perp$$

$$H' := (H_k)^\perp$$

we obtain the equation:

$$\pi_{G'} L = \pi_{H'} L$$

From this it follows that

$$\pi_{G_k} L = L - \pi_{G'} L$$

$$= L - \pi_{H'} L$$

$$= \pi_{H_k} L$$

This is the statement (DR') we are looking for.

QED (subcase $v = k$)

Subcase $v \neq k$ and $B_v \in \{G_v, H_v\}$

Let

$$B' := (B_v)^\perp$$

If $B_1, \dots, B_v, \dots, B_n$ is a sequence that is suitable for σ , then the sequence $B_1, \dots, B', \dots, B_n$ is suitable for σ' , and likewise $B_1, \dots, \mathcal{H}, \dots, B_n$ is suitable for σ'' . Applying the induction hypothesis to σ' yields the equation

$$\pi_{G_k} \pi_{B_n} \dots \pi_{B'} \dots \pi_{B_1} \pi_{UR} = \pi_{H_k} \pi_{B_n} \dots \pi_{B'} \dots \pi_{B_1} \pi_{UR}$$

Similarly, with σ'' we get:

$$\pi_{G_k} \pi_{B_n} \dots \pi_{\mathcal{H}} \dots \pi_{B_1} \pi_{UR} = \pi_{H_k} \pi_{B_n} \dots \pi_{\mathcal{H}} \dots \pi_{B_1} \pi_{UR}$$

By subtracting the former equation from the latter, we obtain

$$\pi_{G_k} \pi_{B_n} \dots \pi_{B_v} \dots \pi_{B_1} \pi_{UR} = \pi_{H_k} \pi_{B_n} \dots \pi_{B_v} \dots \pi_{B_1} \pi_{UR}$$

and thus the statement (DR') to be proven.

QED (Subcase $v \neq k$ and $B_v \in \{G_v, H_v\}$)

Subcase $v \neq k$ and $B_v \notin \{G_v, H_v\}$

In this case, $v \in J \setminus J_k \setminus \{k\}$ and $B_v = \mathcal{H}$. The equation (DR') to be proven is then identical to one of those equations that hold for σ' based on the induction hypothesis.

QED (subcase $v \neq k$ and $B_v \notin \{G_v, H_v\}$)

QED (case $r > 0$)

QED

Note: Because of $\mathcal{W} \subset \mathcal{W}'$, L.7.3 applies to all $\sigma \in \mathcal{W}$, in particular. Thus, L.7.3 represents a generalization of the statements in the definition of t-accessibility, wherein, according to the rules specified by $\sigma \in \mathcal{W}$, A_j is replaced by A_j or $(A_j)^\perp$ or \mathcal{H} and, correspondingly, D_j is replaced by D_j or $(D_j)^\perp$ or \mathcal{H} .

L.7.4 Let $\sigma \in \mathcal{W}$. Using the abbreviations

$$G_j := A_{j;\sigma(j)} \quad (\text{for all } j \in J)$$

$$H_j := D_{j;\sigma(j)} \quad (\text{for all } j \in J)$$

we have for all $k \in J \cup \{0\}$,

$$\pi_{G_k} \cdots \pi_{G_1} \pi_{UR} = \pi_{H_k} \cdots \pi_{H_1} \pi_{UR}$$

Proof: The proof is by complete induction on the index k . The case of $k = 0$ is trivial.

Let $k \in J$. Then:

$$\pi_{G_k} \pi_{G_{k-1}} \cdots \pi_{G_1} \pi_{UR}$$

$$= \pi_{H_k} \pi_{G_{k-1}} \cdots \pi_{G_1} \pi_{UR} \quad (\text{due to L.7.3,}$$

with $B_j := G_j$ for $j < k$ and $B_j := \mathcal{H}$ for $j \geq k$)

$$= \pi_{H_k} \pi_{H_{k-1}} \cdots \pi_{H_1} \pi_{UR} \quad (\text{by the induction hypothesis})$$

QED

L.7.5 For all $\sigma \in \mathcal{W}$,

$$\pi_\sigma \pi_{UR} = \pi_{M_\sigma} \pi_{UR}$$

Proof: Let $\sigma \in \mathcal{W}$. Using the abbreviations

$$G_j := A_{j;\sigma(j)} \quad (\text{for all } j \in J)$$

$$H_j := D_{j;\sigma(j)} \quad (\text{for all } j \in J)$$

we have

$$\pi_\sigma \pi_{UR}$$

$$= \pi_{G_n} \cdots \pi_{G_{k+1}} \pi_{G_k} \pi_{G_{k-1}} \cdots \pi_{G_1} \pi_{UR} \quad (\text{definition of } \pi_\sigma)$$

$$= \pi_{H_n} \cdots \pi_{H_{k+1}} \pi_{H_k} \pi_{H_{k-1}} \cdots \pi_{H_1} \pi_{UR} \quad (\text{L.7.4})$$

$$= \pi_{H_k} \pi_{H_n} \cdots \pi_{H_{k+1}} \pi_{H_{k-1}} \cdots \pi_{H_1} \pi_{UR} \quad (\text{like the } D_j, \text{ the } H_j \text{ are pairwise commutable})$$

$$= \pi_{H_k} \pi_{H_n} \cdots \pi_{H_{k+1}} \pi_{G_{k-1}} \cdots \pi_{G_1} \pi_{UR} \quad (\text{L.7.4})$$

$$= \pi_{G_k} \pi_{H_n} \cdots \pi_{H_{k+1}} \pi_{G_{k-1}} \cdots \pi_{G_1} \pi_{UR} \quad (\text{L.7.3})$$

Now, for all $\varphi \in \mathcal{H}$,

$$\pi_\sigma \pi_{UR} \varphi \in G_k$$

Since this applies to all k , we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_\sigma \pi_{UR} \varphi &\in \bigcap_k G_k \\ &= M_\sigma \end{aligned}$$

Thus

$$\pi_\sigma \pi_{UR} = \pi_{M_\sigma} \pi_\sigma \pi_{UR}$$

$$= \pi_{M_\sigma} \pi_{G_n} \cdots \pi_{G_1} \pi_{UR} \quad (\text{definition of } \pi_\sigma)$$

$$= \pi_{M_\sigma} \pi_{UR}$$

The latter holds because of $M_\sigma < G_k$ for all k .

QED

L.7.6 Let I be the identity operator on \mathcal{H} . Then:

$$I = \sum_{\sigma \in \mathcal{W}} \pi_\sigma$$

Proof: The proof is by complete induction on n .

Case $n = 1$

We then have $J = \{1\}$. The set \mathcal{W} contains exactly the two elements σ_1 and σ_0 , where $\sigma_1(1) := 1$ and $\sigma_0(1) := 0$. (The case $\sigma(1) = \emptyset$ cannot occur, because there is no $j \ll 1$ with $\sigma(j) \neq 1$.) With $A := A_1$, we now have

$$\pi_{\sigma_1} = \pi_{A_1; \sigma_1(1)} = \pi_A$$

$$\pi_{\sigma_0} = \pi_{A_1; \sigma_0(1)} = \pi_{A^\perp}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\sigma \in \mathcal{W}} \pi_\sigma &= \pi_{\sigma_1} + \pi_{\sigma_0} \\ &= \pi_A + \pi_{A^\perp} \\ &= I \end{aligned}$$

QED ($n = 1$)

Case $n > 1$ (induction step)

Let \mathcal{W}' be formed in the same way as \mathcal{W} , but with the index set

$$J' := \{1, \dots, n-1\}$$

instead of J . For all $\tau \in \{0, 1, \emptyset\}$ and $\sigma' \in \mathcal{W}'$, let (σ', τ) denote the map $\sigma : J \rightarrow \{0, 1, \emptyset\}$ for which the following holds:

$$\sigma|_{J'} = \sigma'$$

and

$$\sigma(n) = \tau$$

Now let

$$\mathcal{W}^+ := \{ \sigma' \in \mathcal{W}' \mid \forall_{j \ll n} \sigma'(j) = 1 \}$$

$$\mathcal{W}^- := \mathcal{W}' \setminus \mathcal{W}^+$$

Based on the definition of \mathcal{W} , it can be easily shown that

$$\mathcal{W} = \{ (\sigma', \tau) \mid (\sigma' \in \mathcal{W}^+ \text{ and } \tau \in \{0, 1\}) \text{ or } (\sigma' \in \mathcal{W}^- \text{ and } \tau = \emptyset) \}$$

Because of

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_{(\sigma', \emptyset)} &= \pi_{\mathcal{H}} \pi_{\sigma'} && \text{(definition of } \pi_\sigma) \\ &= \pi_{\sigma'} \end{aligned}$$

and (with $A := A_n$)

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_{(\sigma',1)} + \pi_{(\sigma',0)} &= \pi_A \pi_{\sigma'} + \pi_{A^\perp} \pi_{\sigma'} && \text{(definition of } \pi_{\sigma'}) \\ &= \pi_{\sigma'} \end{aligned}$$

we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\sigma \in \mathcal{W}} \pi_{\sigma} &= \sum_{\sigma' \in \mathcal{W}^-} \pi_{(\sigma',\emptyset)} + \sum_{\sigma' \in \mathcal{W}^+} (\pi_{(\sigma',1)} + \pi_{(\sigma',0)}) \\ &= \sum_{\sigma' \in \mathcal{W}^-} \pi_{\sigma'} + \sum_{\sigma' \in \mathcal{W}^+} \pi_{\sigma'} \\ &= \sum_{\sigma' \in \mathcal{W}} \pi_{\sigma'} \\ &= I \quad \text{(according to the induction hypothesis)} \end{aligned}$$

QED ($n > 1$)
QED

L.7.7 $UR < M^\wedge$

Proof: It is:

$$\pi_{UR} = \sum_{\sigma \in \mathcal{W}} \pi_{\sigma} \pi_{UR} \quad \text{(L.7.6)}$$

$$= \sum_{\sigma \in \mathcal{W}} \pi_{M_{\sigma}} \pi_{UR} \quad \text{(L.7.5)}$$

Since the M_{σ} are pairwise orthogonal (L.7.1), we obtain

$$UR < \bigoplus_{\sigma \in \mathcal{W}} M_{\sigma}$$

$$= M^\wedge \quad \text{(definition of } M^\wedge)$$

QED

L.7.8 For every $k \in J$,

$$B_{k;\tau} < A_{k;\tau} < C_{k;\tau} \quad \text{(for } \tau \in \{0,1,\emptyset\})$$

Proof: For every $\sigma \in \mathcal{W}$ with $\sigma(k) = \tau$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} M_{\sigma} &= \bigcap_{k \in J} A_{k;\sigma(k)} \\ &< A_{k;\sigma(k)} \\ &= A_{k;\tau} \end{aligned}$$

Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} B_{k;\tau} &= \bigoplus \{ M_{\sigma} \mid \sigma \in \mathcal{W} \wedge \sigma(k) = \tau \} && \text{(definition of } B_{k;\tau}) \\ &< A_{k;\tau} \end{aligned}$$

In the case of $\tau \in \{0,1\}$, due to the definitions of $C_{k;\tau}$ and $B_{k;\tau}$,

$$\begin{aligned} (C_{k;\tau})^\perp &= [(M^\wedge)^\perp \oplus B_{k;\tau} \oplus B_{k;\emptyset}]^\perp \\ &= M^\wedge \cap (B_{k;\tau})^\perp \cap (B_{k;\emptyset})^\perp && \text{(L.7.2)} \\ &= \bigoplus \{ M_{\sigma} \mid \sigma \in \mathcal{W} \wedge \sigma(k) \neq \tau \wedge \sigma(k) \neq \emptyset \} \\ &= \bigoplus \{ M_{\sigma} \mid \sigma \in \mathcal{W} \wedge \sigma(k) = 1-\tau \} \\ &= B_{k;1-\tau} && \text{(definition of } B_{k;\tau}) \\ &< A_{k;1-\tau} && \text{(first inequality of L.7.8)} \\ &= (A_{k;\tau})^\perp && \text{(definition of } A_{k;\tau}) \end{aligned}$$

From this we obtain $A_{k;\tau} < C_{k;\tau}$. In the case of $\tau = \emptyset$, we have $A_{k;\tau} = \mathcal{H}$ and $C_{k;\tau} = \mathcal{H}$, and obviously $A_{k;\tau} < C_{k;\tau}$. **QED**

L.7.9 For every $\sigma \in \mathcal{W}$,

$$\bigcap_{k \in J} B_{k;\sigma(k)} = M_\sigma$$

Proof: It is

$$\begin{aligned} \bigcap_{k \in J} B_{k;\sigma(k)} &= \bigcap_{k \in J} \oplus \{ M_{\sigma'} \mid \sigma' \in \mathcal{W} \wedge \sigma'(k) = \sigma(k) \} && \text{(definition of } B_{k;\tau} \text{)} \\ &= \oplus \{ M_{\sigma'} \mid \sigma' \in \mathcal{W} \wedge \forall_k [\sigma'(k) = \sigma(k)] \} && \text{(L.7.1)} \\ &= \oplus \{ M_{\sigma'} \mid \sigma' = \sigma \} \\ &= M_\sigma \end{aligned}$$

QED

L.7.10 For $\sigma, \sigma' \in \mathcal{W}$, if

$$\forall_{k \in J} [\sigma'(k) = \sigma(k) \text{ or } \sigma'(k) = \emptyset]$$

then $\sigma' = \sigma$.

Proof: Let the premise of the lemma be given, and suppose that $\sigma' \neq \sigma$. Then let

$$v := \min \{ k \in J \mid \sigma'(k) \neq \sigma(k) \}$$

From $\sigma'(v) \neq \sigma(v)$, it follows that $\sigma'(v) = \emptyset$. According to the definition of \mathcal{W} , there exists some $j \ll v$ with $\sigma'(j) \neq 1$. Because of $j < v$ and v is minimal, we have $\sigma(j) \neq 1$, and due to the definition of \mathcal{W} , $\sigma(v) = \emptyset$, i.e., $\sigma(v) = \sigma'(v)$. This is a contradiction. **QED**

L.7.11 For every $\sigma \in \mathcal{W}$,

$$M^\wedge \cap \bigcap_{k \in J} C_{k;\sigma(k)} = M_\sigma$$

Proof: It is

$$\begin{aligned} M^\wedge \cap \bigcap_{k \in J} C_{k;\sigma(k)} &= M^\wedge \cap \bigcap_{k \in J} [B_{k;\sigma(k)} \oplus B_{k;\emptyset} \oplus (M^\wedge)^\perp] && \text{(definition of } C_{k;\tau} \text{)} \\ &= M^\wedge \cap \bigcap_{k \in J} [B_{k;\sigma(k)} \oplus B_{k;\emptyset}] \\ &= \oplus \{ M_{\sigma'} \mid \sigma' \in \mathcal{W} \wedge \forall_k [\sigma'(k) = \sigma(k) \vee \sigma'(k) = \emptyset] \} && \text{(L.7.1 and definition of } B_{k;\tau} \text{)} \\ &= \oplus \{ M_{\sigma'} \mid \sigma' \in \mathcal{W} \wedge \sigma' = \sigma \} && \text{(L.7.10)} \\ &= M_\sigma \end{aligned}$$

QED

L.7.12 For every $\sigma \in \mathcal{W}$,

$$\bigcap_{k \in J} C_{k;\sigma(k)} < \bigcap_{k \in J} B_{k;\sigma(k)} \oplus (M^\wedge)^\perp$$

Proof: It is

$$\begin{aligned} \bigcap_{k \in J} C_{k;\sigma(k)} &= [M^\wedge \cap \bigcap_{k \in J} C_{k;\sigma(k)}] \oplus [(M^\wedge)^\perp \cap \bigcap_{k \in J} C_{k;\sigma(k)}] && \text{(L.7.2)} \\ &< M_\sigma \oplus (M^\wedge)^\perp && \text{(L.7.11)} \\ &= \bigcap_{k \in J} B_{k;\sigma(k)} \oplus (M^\wedge)^\perp && \text{(L.7.9)} \end{aligned}$$

QED

Applying L.7.2, L.7.7, L.7.8, L.7.9, L.7.11, and L.7.12 to the case of $\sigma = \sigma_1$ with $\sigma_1(k) = 1$ for all $k \in J$, we obtain (using the definitions $B_k := B_{k,1}$ and $C_k := C_{k,1}$) the following *nesting property*:

Theorem T.7.1 Let

$$(E_1, t_1), \dots, (E_n, t_n) \in \mathcal{E}$$

be a t -accessible sequence of events, and for brevity let

$$A_k := U_{-t_k} E_k \quad (\text{for all } k \in \{1, \dots, n\})$$

Then there exist an $M^\wedge < \mathcal{H}$ and, for all $k \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, subspaces $B_k < \mathcal{H}$ and $C_k < \mathcal{H}$ with:

- (a) all B_k , C_k , and M^\wedge are commutable (L.7.2)
- (b) $B_k < A_k < C_k$ (for all k) (by L.7.8 for $\tau = 1$)
- (c) $UR < M^\wedge$ (L.7.7)
- (d) $\bigcap_k B_k = \bigcap_k A_k$ (by L.7.9 for σ_1 and the definition of M_σ)
- (e) $M^\wedge \cap \bigcap_k C_k = \bigcap_k A_k$ (by L.7.11 for σ_1 and the definition of M_σ)
- (f) $\bigcap_k C_k < \bigcap_k B_k \oplus (M^\wedge)^\perp$ (L.7.12)

3. Formal representation of macroscopic experiments

Here we consider an experiment that can be evaluated by a macroscopic subject at a point in time t . The experiment must then be described within the framework of a t -accessible sequence of events

$$(E_1, t_1), \dots, (E_n, t_n)$$

with a dependency relation « on the index set

$$J := \{1, \dots, n\}$$

The index set J consists of two subranges

$$K' := \{1, \dots, q\}$$

$$K'' := \{q+1, \dots, n\}$$

such that

$$\mathcal{E}' := \{ (E_j, t_j) \mid j \in K' \}$$

describes the conditions of the experiment (with the exception of the initial condition) and

$$\mathcal{E}'' := \{ (E_j, t_j) \mid j \in K'' \}$$

denotes the set of all possible experimental results. The document relationship between any element of the t -accessible sequence and its document depends on all preceding experimental conditions. In addition, the document relationships between the experimental results and their documents should be independent of all other possible results and their documents. The dependency relation must therefore satisfy:

$$(+)\ j \ll k \Leftrightarrow j < k \wedge j \in K' \quad (\text{for all } j, k \in J)$$

Thus, the t -accessible sequence considered here is a “standard context” in the sense of the following definition:

Definition D.7.2 A “standard context” is a t -accessible sequence of events whose index set $J := \{1, \dots, n\}$ is divided into two subranges $K' = \{1, \dots, q\}$ and $K'' = \{q+1, \dots, n\}$ such that condition (+) applies to the dependency relation \ll . The elements of the sequence specified by K' are the “conditions”, while those specified by K'' are the “events of interest” of the context.

L.7.13 Let there be a standard context with a division of the index set J into $J = K' \cup K''$. Then, if L'' is a subset of K'' , restricting the events of interest of this context to the subset

$$\{ (E_j, t_j) \mid j \in L'' \}$$

(with a suitable renumbering of the elements of this set) again yields a standard context.

Proof: The assertion is easy to prove, since in the definition of t -accessibility, for the sequences B_1, \dots, B_n that are to satisfy conditions (i) to (iii), we can choose $B_j := \mathcal{H}$ for all $j \notin J_K$ and thus, due to (+), for every $j \in K'' \setminus L''$. **QED**

The experimental results are divided into R alternatives, each with S_r possible outcomes. We therefore define the following index range for the possible results of the experiment:

$$D := \{ (r, s) \mid r \in \{1, \dots, R\} \wedge s \in \{1, \dots, S_r\} \}$$

Each pair $(r, s) \in D$ corresponds to exactly one element of the sequence

$$(E_{q+1}, t_{q+1}), \dots, (E_n, t_n)$$

So let

$$k : D \rightarrow K''$$

be the bijective mapping that describes this: For each $(r, s) \in D$, let $(E_{k(r,s)}, t_{k(r,s)})$ be the event that corresponds to (r, s) . For brevity, we let:

$$E_{rs} := E_{k(r,s)}$$

$$t_{rs} := t_{k(r,s)}$$

Thus,

$$\{ (E_{rs}, t_{rs}) \mid (r, s) \in D \}$$

is equal to the set \mathcal{E}'' of all possible experimental results.

In the following, we use indices r and s in the sense that the index r runs through the set $\{1, \dots, R\}$ and the index s (for a given r) runs through $\{1, \dots, S_r\}$.

Note: The document relationships underlying the standard context considered here are based on the assumption that the initial condition $(UR, 0)$ is given. We assume here that UR has finite dimension, i.e., $\dim UR < \infty$. This assumption does not constitute a significant restriction. We can assume that, at the initial time $t = 0$, matter was confined to a large but finite part of space and that the total energy of the universe was (and thus all momenta were) confined to a finite range as well. The assumption $\dim UR < \infty$ ensures that the numerical expressions appearing in the following calculations will always be well defined and finite.

For brevity, we let:

$$A_j := U_{-t_j} E_j \quad (\text{for } j \in J)$$

$$A_{rs} := U_{-t_{rs}} E_{rs} \quad (\text{for } (r, s) \in D)$$

Then, for all $(r,s) \in D$,

$$A_{rs} = A_{k(r,s)}$$

where k is the bijective mapping from D to K introduced above.

As before, we can identify the event (E_j, t_j) with the possible fact $\langle E_j, t_j \rangle$ and, because of $\langle E_j, t_j \rangle = \langle A_j \rangle$, we can refer to it briefly as “the event” $\langle A_j \rangle$. Similarly, $\langle A_{rs} \rangle$ stands for the event (E_{rs}, t_{rs}) .

4. Certain possible facts and their properties

Let

$$G := \langle UR \rangle \wedge \forall_{j \in K} \langle A_j \rangle$$

$$N := \forall_r \exists_s \langle A_{rs} \rangle$$

$$M := \forall_r \forall_{s \neq s'} \neg(\langle A_{rs} \rangle \wedge \langle A_{rs'} \rangle)$$

$$Q := N \wedge M$$

G combines all the conditions of the experiment into one possible fact. G is called the “basic condition” of the experiment under consideration. N describes that at least one possible outcome is realized for each alternative. Only if N has occurred, has the experiment been successfully completed. M specifies that two different possible outcomes for one alternative cannot be realized simultaneously. Q describes that, for each alternative, exactly one of the possible outcomes is realized (see L.7.14 below).

We now assume that (for a fixed r) any two different $\langle A_{rs} \rangle$ mutually exclude each other under the basic condition G . We thus make the assumption

$$(EX1) \quad \forall_r \forall_{s \neq s'} \neg \diamond(G \wedge \langle A_{rs} \rangle \wedge \langle A_{rs'} \rangle)$$

This is a self-evident requirement for any experiment.

L.7.14 It is

$$Q = \forall_r \exists_s^1 \langle A_{rs} \rangle$$

Proof: For all $\omega \in \Omega$,

$$\omega \in Q$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \omega \in N \wedge \omega \in M$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \omega \in \forall_r \exists_s \langle A_{rs} \rangle \wedge \omega \in \forall_r \forall_{s \neq s'} \neg(\langle A_{rs} \rangle \wedge \langle A_{rs'} \rangle)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \forall_r \exists_s (\omega \in \langle A_{rs} \rangle) \wedge \forall_r \forall_{s \neq s'} \neg(\omega \in \langle A_{rs} \rangle \wedge \omega \in \langle A_{rs'} \rangle)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \forall_r \exists_s [(\omega \in \langle A_{rs} \rangle) \wedge \forall_{s \neq s'} \neg(\omega \in \langle A_{rs'} \rangle)]$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \omega \in \forall_r \exists_s [\langle A_{rs} \rangle \wedge \forall_{s \neq s'} (\neg \langle A_{rs'} \rangle)]$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \omega \in \forall_r \exists_s^1 \langle A_{rs} \rangle$$

QED

We define the set of all possible outcome constellations as

$$\mathfrak{B} := \{ \beta : \{1, \dots, R\} \rightarrow \mathbb{N} \mid \forall_r \beta(r) \in \{1, \dots, S_r\} \}$$

Each $\beta \in \mathfrak{B}$ assigns exactly one of the possible outcomes to each alternative.

For every outcome constellation $\beta \in \mathfrak{B}$, let

$$N_\beta := \forall_r \langle A_{r,\beta(r)} \rangle$$

N_β indicates that for each alternative, the outcome specified by β is realized.

L.7.15 It is

$$N = \exists \beta \in \mathfrak{B} N_\beta$$

Proof: It is

$$N = \exists \beta \in \mathfrak{B} N_\beta$$

$$\Leftrightarrow (\forall_r \exists_s \langle A_{rs} \rangle) = \exists \beta \in \mathfrak{B} \forall_r \langle A_{r,\beta(r)} \rangle$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \forall_\omega [\omega \in \forall_r \exists_s \langle A_{rs} \rangle \Leftrightarrow \omega \in \exists \beta \in \mathfrak{B} \forall_r \langle A_{r,\beta(r)} \rangle]$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \forall_\omega [\forall_r \exists_s (\omega \in \langle A_{rs} \rangle) \Leftrightarrow \exists \beta \in \mathfrak{B} \forall_r (\omega \in \langle A_{r,\beta(r)} \rangle)]$$

For fixed $\omega \in \Omega$, let $M_{r,s} := (\omega \in \langle A_{rs} \rangle)$ for all r and s . Then, in particular:

$$M_{r,\beta(r)} \Leftrightarrow \omega \in \langle A_{r,\beta(r)} \rangle$$

So we have to show that:

$$\forall_r \exists_s M_{r,s} \Leftrightarrow \exists \beta \in \mathfrak{B} \forall_r M_{r,\beta(r)}$$

For “ \Rightarrow ”: Let $\forall_r \exists_s M_{r,s}$ be given. If $\beta \in \mathfrak{B}$ is now defined by

$$\beta(r) := \min \{ s \mid M_{r,s} \} \quad (\text{for each } r)$$

we get

$$\forall_r M_{r,\beta(r)}$$

For “ \Leftarrow ”: Let $\beta \in \mathfrak{B}$ with $\forall_r M_{r,\beta(r)}$ be given. Then for every r there is an s , namely $s := \beta(r)$, with $M_{r,s}$. **QED**

For every outcome constellation $\beta \in \mathfrak{B}$, let

$$Q_\beta := N_\beta \wedge M$$

The possible fact Q_β indicates that for each alternative, only the outcome specified by β is realized and no other (cf. L.7.16). The Q_β are pairwise disjoint (cf. L.7.17), and we have:

$$Q = \exists \beta \in \mathfrak{B} Q_\beta$$

Thus, Q is the disjoint union of all Q_β .

L.7.16 It is

$$Q_\beta = \forall_r [\langle A_{r,\beta(r)} \rangle \wedge \forall_{s \neq \beta(r)} \neg \langle A_{rs} \rangle]$$

Proof: Let $\omega \in Q_\beta$. Then:

$$\omega \in N_\beta \wedge \omega \in M$$

$$\omega \in \forall_r \langle A_{r,\beta(r)} \rangle \wedge \omega \in \forall_r \forall_{s \neq \beta(r)} \neg (\langle A_{rs} \rangle \wedge \langle A_{rs'} \rangle)$$

$$\omega \in \forall_r [\langle A_{r,\beta(r)} \rangle \wedge \forall_{s \neq \beta(r)} \neg (\langle A_{rs} \rangle \wedge \langle A_{rs'} \rangle)]$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \forall_r [(\omega \in \langle A_r, \beta(r) \rangle) \wedge \forall_{s \neq s'} \omega \notin (\langle A_{rs} \rangle \wedge \langle A_{rs'} \rangle)] \\
 & \forall_r [(\omega \in \langle A_r, \beta(r) \rangle) \wedge \forall_{s \neq \beta(r)} \omega \notin (\langle A_{rs} \rangle \wedge \langle A_r, \beta(r) \rangle)] \\
 & \hspace{10em} \text{(by setting } s' := \beta(r) \text{ specifically)} \\
 & \forall_r [(\omega \in \langle A_r, \beta(r) \rangle) \wedge \forall_{s \neq \beta(r)} (\omega \notin \langle A_{rs} \rangle)] \\
 & \omega \in \forall_r [\langle A_r, \beta(r) \rangle \wedge \forall_{s \neq \beta(r)} \neg \langle A_{rs} \rangle] \qquad \text{QED (“\(\subset\)”)}
 \end{aligned}$$

Now assume

$$\omega \in \forall_r [\langle A_r, \beta(r) \rangle \wedge \forall_{s \neq \beta(r)} \neg \langle A_{rs} \rangle]$$

which is equivalent to

$$\forall_r [(\omega \in \langle A_r, \beta(r) \rangle) \wedge \forall_{s \neq \beta(r)} (\omega \notin \langle A_{rs} \rangle)]$$

We then have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \omega & \in \forall_r \langle A_r, \beta(r) \rangle \\
 & = N_\beta
 \end{aligned}$$

It remains to prove that $\omega \in M$. So let r and $s \neq s'$ be given. We then have to show:

$$\omega \notin (\langle A_{rs} \rangle \wedge \langle A_{rs'} \rangle)$$

Since s and s' cannot both be equal to $\beta(r)$, we have

$$s \neq \beta(r) \vee s' \neq \beta(r)$$

Without loss of generality, let $s \neq \beta(r)$ be true. Then $\omega \notin \langle A_{rs} \rangle$ follows, and thus the assertion.

QED (“\(\supset\)”)
QED

L.7.17 The Q_β are pairwise disjoint.

Proof: Let $\beta, \beta' \in \mathfrak{B}$ with $\beta \neq \beta'$. Then there exists an r such that $\beta(r) \neq \beta'(r)$. With $s := \beta(r)$ and $s' := \beta'(r)$, we get

$$s \neq s'$$

From the assumption

$$\omega \in Q_\beta \cap Q_{\beta'}$$

it would follow that

$$\omega \in N_\beta \wedge N_{\beta'} \wedge M$$

and from this we get:

$$\omega \in \langle A_r, \beta(r) \rangle \qquad \text{(definition of } N_\beta)$$

$$= \langle A_{rs} \rangle$$

$$\omega \in \langle A_r, \beta'(r) \rangle \qquad \text{(definition of } N_{\beta'})$$

$$= \langle A_{rs'} \rangle$$

$$\omega \notin (\langle A_{rs} \rangle \wedge \langle A_{rs'} \rangle) \qquad \text{(definition of } M)$$

This results in a contradiction.

QED

L.7.18 Q is the disjoint union of all $N_\beta \wedge Q$.

Proof: It is

$$\begin{aligned} N_\beta \wedge Q &= N_\beta \wedge N \wedge M && \text{(definition of } Q) \\ &= N_\beta \wedge M && \text{(since } N_\beta \subset N) \\ &= Q_\beta && \text{(definition of } Q_\beta) \end{aligned}$$

and Q is the disjoint union of all Q_β .

QED

L.7.19 Condition (EX1) is equivalent to the inclusion

$$G \subset M$$

Proof: For “ \Rightarrow ”: Let (EX1) hold and let $\omega \in G$. For r and $s \neq s'$, it follows from (EX1) that

$$\neg \diamond (G \wedge \langle A_{rs} \rangle \wedge \langle A_{rs'} \rangle)$$

and thus

$$G \wedge \langle A_{rs} \rangle \wedge \langle A_{rs'} \rangle = \emptyset$$

Because of $\omega \in G$, it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \omega &\notin (\langle A_{rs} \rangle \wedge \langle A_{rs'} \rangle) \\ \omega &\in \neg(\langle A_{rs} \rangle \wedge \langle A_{rs'} \rangle) \end{aligned}$$

So we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \forall_r \forall_{s \neq s'} \omega &\in \neg(\langle A_{rs} \rangle \wedge \langle A_{rs'} \rangle) \\ \omega &\in \forall_r \forall_{s \neq s'} \neg(\langle A_{rs} \rangle \wedge \langle A_{rs'} \rangle) \\ &= M \end{aligned}$$

QED (“ \Rightarrow ”)

For “ \Leftarrow ”: Let $G \subset M$ and let r and $s \neq s'$ be given. It must then be shown that:

$$G \wedge \langle A_{rs} \rangle \wedge \langle A_{rs'} \rangle = \emptyset$$

Because of $(\neg F \wedge F) = \emptyset$ for all $F \in \mathcal{A}$, we get:

$$\begin{aligned} \neg(\langle A_{rs} \rangle \wedge \langle A_{rs'} \rangle) \wedge \langle A_{rs} \rangle \wedge \langle A_{rs'} \rangle &= \emptyset \\ [\forall_r \forall_{s \neq s'} \neg(\langle A_{rs} \rangle \wedge \langle A_{rs'} \rangle)] \wedge \langle A_{rs} \rangle \wedge \langle A_{rs'} \rangle &= \emptyset \\ M \wedge \langle A_{rs} \rangle \wedge \langle A_{rs'} \rangle &= \emptyset && \text{(definition of } M) \\ G \wedge \langle A_{rs} \rangle \wedge \langle A_{rs'} \rangle &= \emptyset && \text{(since } G \subset M) \end{aligned}$$

QED (“ \Leftarrow ”)

QED

5. Some statements about outcome constellations

In this section, we shall prove several lemmas, some of which (e.g., L.7.22 to L.7.24) are rather “technical” and may be difficult to understand. They serve as a preparation for calculating the probability measure for the experiment in Section 6. Some expressions will be used here that have been introduced in the proof of the nesting property (see Section 2).

For each outcome constellation $\beta \in \mathfrak{B}$, let σ_β be the mapping from J to $\{0,1,\emptyset\}$ for which the following holds:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_\beta(j) &= 1 && \text{for all } j \in K' \\ \sigma_\beta(k(r,s)) &= 1 && \text{for all } (r,s) \in D \text{ with } s = \beta(r) \\ \sigma_\beta(k(r,s)) &= 0 && \text{for all } (r,s) \in D \text{ with } s \neq \beta(r) \end{aligned}$$

Thus, σ_β is the assignment that assigns the value 1 to all conditions of the experiment and, for each alternative, to the possible outcome specified by β . All other possible outcomes are assigned the value 0.

For the following, we assume that the set \mathcal{W} and the expressions $A_{j;\tau}$, $B_{j;\tau}$, and $C_{j;\tau}$ (for all $j \in J$ and $\tau \in \{0,1,\emptyset\}$), as well as M_σ (for every $\sigma \in \mathcal{W}$) and M^\wedge are defined in the same way as in the proof of the nesting property in Section 2. Furthermore, let $B_j := B_{j;1}$ and $C_j := C_{j;1}$ (for all $j \in J$) as well as $B_{rs} := B_{k(r,s)}$ and $C_{rs} := C_{k(r,s)}$ (for all $(r,s) \in D$).

The following statements then hold for all $j \in J$ and $(r,s) \in D$:

$$B_{j;\tau} < A_{j;\tau} < C_{j;\tau} \quad (\text{for } \tau \in \{0,1,\emptyset\}) \quad (\text{L.7.8})$$

$$B_j < A_j < C_j \quad (\text{with } \tau = 1)$$

$$B_{rs} < A_{rs} < C_{rs} \quad (\text{definition of } A_{rs}, B_{rs}, \text{ and } C_{rs})$$

$$UR < M^\wedge \quad (\text{L.7.7})$$

$$C_{j;\tau} = B_{j;\tau} \oplus B_{j;\emptyset} \oplus (M^\wedge)^\perp \quad (\text{for } \tau \in \{0,1\}) \quad (\text{definition of } C_{j;\tau})$$

$$C_j = B_j \oplus B_{j;\emptyset} \oplus (M^\wedge)^\perp \quad (\text{with } \tau = 1)$$

The M_σ are pairwise orthogonal and all $B_{j;\tau}$, $C_{j;\tau}$, B_j , C_j , B_{rs} , C_{rs} and M^\wedge are commutable with each other (because of L.7.1, L.7.2 and the definitions).

L.7.20 For all $\beta \in \mathfrak{B}$,
 $\sigma_\beta \in \mathcal{W}$

Proof: For every $j \in J$, $\sigma_\beta(j) \neq \emptyset$, and for all $i \ll j$, we have $i \in K'$ and thus $\sigma_\beta(i) = 1$. **QED**

For every $\beta \in \mathfrak{B}$, let

$$\mathcal{W}_\beta := \{ \sigma \in \mathcal{W} \mid \forall_{j \in K'} \sigma(j) = 1 \wedge \forall_r \sigma(k(r,\beta(r))) = 1 \}$$

be the set of assignments σ in \mathcal{W} that assign the value 1 to every condition of the experiment and, for each alternative, *at least* to the outcome indicated by β . For each subset $\mathfrak{B}' \subset \mathfrak{B}$, let

$$\mathcal{W}_{\mathfrak{B}'} := \cup \{ \mathcal{W}_\beta \mid \beta \in \mathfrak{B}' \}$$

L.7.21 For all $\beta \in \mathfrak{B}$,
 $\sigma_\beta \in \mathcal{W}_\beta$

Proof: Due to the definition of σ_β , we have

$$\sigma_\beta(j) = 1 \quad (\text{for all } j \in K')$$

and for all r

$$\sigma_\beta(k(r,\beta(r))) = 1$$

QED

L.7.22 For all $\mathfrak{B}' \subset \mathfrak{B}$,

$$\bigoplus_{\beta \in \mathfrak{B}'} (\bigcap_{j \in K'} B_j \cap \bigcap_r B_{r,\beta(r)}) = \bigoplus_{\sigma \in \mathcal{W}_{\mathfrak{B}'}} M_\sigma$$

Proof: Due to the orthogonality of all M_σ and the definition of B_j and $B_{r,\beta(r)}$, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} & \bigoplus_{\beta \in \mathfrak{B}'} (\bigcap_{j \in K'} B_j \cap \bigcap_r B_{r,\beta(r)}) \\ &= \bigoplus \{ M_\sigma \mid \sigma \in \mathcal{W} \text{ and } \exists \beta \in \mathfrak{B}' [\forall j \in K' \sigma(j) = 1 \wedge \forall_r \sigma(k(r,\beta(r))) = 1] \} \\ &= \bigoplus \{ M_\sigma \mid \exists \beta \in \mathfrak{B}' [\sigma \in \mathcal{W}_\beta] \} \\ &= \bigoplus_{\sigma \in \mathcal{W}_{\mathfrak{B}'}} M_\sigma \end{aligned}$$

QED

L.7.23 Let $I \subset J$ be closed in the sense that

$$\forall k \in I \forall j \ll k (j \in I)$$

Then:

$$\bigcap_{i \in I} B_i \oplus (M^\wedge)^\perp = \bigcap_{i \in I} C_i$$

Proof: For “<”:

$$\begin{aligned} \bigcap_{i \in I} B_i \oplus (M^\wedge)^\perp &< \bigcap_{i \in I} (B_i \oplus B_{i;\emptyset} \oplus (M^\wedge)^\perp) \\ &= \bigcap_{i \in I} C_i \end{aligned}$$

QED (“<”)

For “>”:

$$\begin{aligned} & \bigcap_{i \in I} C_i \\ &= \bigcap_{i \in I} (B_i \oplus B_{i;\emptyset} \oplus (M^\wedge)^\perp) \\ &= \bigoplus \{ M_\sigma \mid \sigma \in \mathcal{W} \wedge \forall_{i \in I} (\sigma(i) = 1 \vee \sigma(i) = \emptyset) \} \oplus (M^\wedge)^\perp \end{aligned}$$

For all $\sigma \in \mathcal{W}$, from the condition

$$\forall_{i \in I} (\sigma(i) = 1 \vee \sigma(i) = \emptyset)$$

it follows that

$$\forall_{i \in I} (\sigma(i) = 1)$$

since otherwise, with

$$v := \min \{ i \in I \mid \sigma(i) \neq 1 \}$$

we would have $\sigma(v) = \emptyset$, and there would be some $j \ll v$ with $\sigma(j) \neq 1$. Because I is closed, it would follow that $j \in I$, contradicting the minimality of v .

Therefore:

$$\begin{aligned} & \bigcap_{i \in I} C_i \\ &= \bigoplus \{ M_\sigma \mid \sigma \in \mathcal{W} \wedge \forall_{i \in I} (\sigma(i) = 1) \} \oplus (M^\wedge)^\perp \\ &= \bigcap_{i \in I} B_i \oplus (M^\wedge)^\perp \end{aligned}$$

QED (“>”)

QED

L.7.24 For all $\mathfrak{B}' \subset \mathfrak{B}$,

$$\bigoplus_{\beta \in \mathfrak{B}'} (\bigcap_{j \in K'} C_j \cap \bigcap_r C_{r,\beta(r)}) = (\bigoplus_{\sigma \in \mathcal{W}_{\mathfrak{B}'}} M_\sigma) \oplus (M^\wedge)^\perp$$

Proof: It is

$$\bigoplus_{\beta \in \mathfrak{B}'} (\bigcap_{j \in K'} C_j \cap \bigcap_r C_{r,\beta(r)})$$

$$= \bigoplus_{\beta \in \mathfrak{B}'} [(\bigcap_{j \in K'} B_j \cap \bigcap_r B_{r, \beta(r)}) \oplus (M^\wedge)^\perp] \quad (\text{L.7.23})$$

$$= \bigoplus_{\beta \in \mathfrak{B}'} (\bigcap_{j \in K'} B_j \cap \bigcap_r B_{r, \beta(r)}) \oplus (M^\wedge)^\perp$$

$$= (\bigoplus_{\sigma \in \mathcal{W}_{\mathfrak{B}'}} M_\sigma) \oplus (M^\wedge)^\perp \quad (\text{L.7.22})$$

QED

L.7.25 The following holds:

$$\sigma \in \mathcal{W}_{\mathfrak{B}} \wedge \sigma \notin \{ \sigma_\beta \mid \beta \in \mathfrak{B} \} \Rightarrow \pi_{M_\sigma} \pi_{UR} = 0$$

Proof: Let $\sigma \in \mathcal{W}_{\mathfrak{B}}$ and $\sigma \notin \{ \sigma_\beta \mid \beta \in \mathfrak{B} \}$. Then there exists some $\beta \in \mathfrak{B}$ with $\sigma \in \mathcal{W}_\beta$. That implies:

$$\forall_{j \in K'} \sigma(j) = 1 \text{ and } \forall_r \sigma(k(r, \beta(r))) = 1$$

Since $\sigma \in \mathcal{W}$ and $\sigma \neq \sigma_\beta$, there exists an r and $s' \neq s := \beta(r)$ with $\sigma(k(r, s')) = 1$. Thus we have:

$$\exists_r \exists_{s' \neq s} [\sigma(k(r, s)) = 1 \wedge \sigma(k(r, s')) = 1]$$

It follows that:

$$\begin{aligned} M_\sigma &= \bigcap_{j \in J} A_j; \sigma(j) \\ &< \bigcap_{j \in K'} A_j \cap A_{rs} \cap A_{rs'} \end{aligned}$$

From the assumption (EX1) made above, we get:

$$\langle UR \rangle \wedge \forall_{j \in K'} \langle A_j \rangle \wedge \langle A_{rs} \rangle \wedge \langle A_{rs'} \rangle = \emptyset$$

Then, because of L.5.26, there are commutable subspaces $D, D_j, D_{rs},$ and $D_{rs'} < \mathcal{H}$ with

$$UR < D$$

$$A_j < D_j \quad (\text{for all } j \in K')$$

$$A_{rs} < D_{rs}$$

$$A_{rs'} < D_{rs'}$$

and

$$D \cap \bigcap_j D_j \cap D_{rs} \cap D_{rs'} = 0$$

Now

$$M_\sigma < \bigcap_j A_j \cap A_{rs} \cap A_{rs'}$$

$$< \bigcap_j D_j \cap D_{rs} \cap D_{rs'} < D^\perp < UR^\perp$$

and thus

$$M_\sigma \perp UR$$

$$\pi_{M_\sigma} \pi_{UR} = 0$$

QED

L.7.26 For all $\mathfrak{B}' \subset \mathfrak{B}$,

$$\mathcal{W}_{\mathfrak{B}'} \cap \{ \sigma_\beta \mid \beta \in \mathfrak{B} \} = \{ \sigma_\beta \mid \beta \in \mathfrak{B}' \}$$

Proof: For “ \subset ”: Let $\sigma \in \mathcal{W}_{\mathfrak{B}'}$ and $\beta \in \mathfrak{B}$ with $\sigma = \sigma_\beta$. Then there is a $\beta' \in \mathfrak{B}'$ with $\sigma_\beta \in \mathcal{W}_{\beta'}$.

It follows that:

$$\forall_r \sigma_\beta(k(r, \beta'(r))) = 1$$

Since σ_β satisfies

$$\forall_r \forall_s [\sigma_\beta(k(r,s)) = 1 \Leftrightarrow s = \beta(r)]$$

by inserting $\beta'(r)$ for s , we get for all r

$$\beta'(r) = \beta(r)$$

and thus $\beta = \beta'$ as well as

$$\sigma = \sigma_{\beta'}$$

$$\in \{ \sigma_\beta \mid \beta \in \mathfrak{B}' \}$$

QED (“ \subset ”)

For “ \supset ”: The statement is trivial, since $\mathfrak{B}' \subset \mathfrak{B}$ and $\sigma_\beta \in \mathcal{W}_\beta$ always hold.

QED (“ \supset ”)

QED

6. From the outer measure μ to the probability measure for the experiment

L.7.27 For every $\mathfrak{B}' \subset \mathfrak{B}$,

$$\mu(G \wedge \exists \beta \in \mathfrak{B}' N_\beta) = \sum_{\sigma \in \mathcal{W}_{\mathfrak{B}'}} \text{tr } \pi_{M_\sigma} \pi_{UR}$$

Proof: For “ \leq ”:

$$\mu(G \wedge \exists \beta \in \mathfrak{B}' N_\beta)$$

$$= \mu(\langle UR \rangle \wedge \forall_{j \in K} \langle A_j \rangle \wedge \exists \beta \in \mathfrak{B}' \forall_r \langle A_{r, \beta(r)} \rangle) \quad (\text{definition of } G \text{ and } N_\beta)$$

$$\leq \mu(\langle UR \rangle \wedge \forall_{j \in K} \langle C_j \rangle \wedge \exists \beta \in \mathfrak{B}' \forall_r \langle C_{r, \beta(r)} \rangle) \quad (\text{L.7.8, MON, and monotonicity of } \mu)$$

$$= \mu(\langle UR \rangle \wedge \exists \beta \in \mathfrak{B}' [\forall_{j \in K} \langle C_j \rangle \wedge \forall_r \langle C_{r, \beta(r)} \rangle])$$

$$= \text{tr } \pi_{\oplus_{\beta \in \mathfrak{B}'} [\cap_{j \in K} C_j \cap \cap_r C_{r, \beta(r)}]} \pi_{UR} \quad (\text{T.5.4})$$

$$= \text{tr } \pi_{(\oplus_{\sigma \in \mathcal{W}_{\mathfrak{B}'}} M_\sigma) \oplus (M^\wedge)^\perp} \pi_{UR} \quad (\text{L.7.24})$$

$$= \text{tr } \pi_{(\oplus_{\sigma \in \mathcal{W}_{\mathfrak{B}'}} M_\sigma)} \pi_{UR} \quad (\text{since } UR < M^\wedge)$$

$$= \sum_{\sigma \in \mathcal{W}_{\mathfrak{B}'}} \text{tr } \pi_{M_\sigma} \pi_{UR} \quad (\text{since the } M_\sigma \text{ are orthogonal}) \quad \mathbf{QED} \text{ (“}\leq\text{”)}$$

For “ \geq ”:

$$\mu(G \wedge \exists \beta \in \mathfrak{B}' N_\beta)$$

$$= \mu(\langle UR \rangle \wedge \forall_{j \in K} \langle A_j \rangle \wedge \exists \beta \in \mathfrak{B}' \forall_r \langle A_{r, \beta(r)} \rangle) \quad (\text{definition of } G \text{ and } N_\beta)$$

$$\geq \mu(\langle UR \rangle \wedge \forall_{j \in K} \langle B_j \rangle \wedge \exists \beta \in \mathfrak{B}' \forall_r \langle B_{r, \beta(r)} \rangle) \quad (\text{L.7.8, MON, and monotonicity of } \mu)$$

$$= \mu(\langle UR \rangle \wedge \exists \beta \in \mathfrak{B}' [\forall_{j \in K} \langle B_j \rangle \wedge \forall_r \langle B_{r, \beta(r)} \rangle])$$

$$= \text{tr } \pi_{\oplus_{\beta \in \mathfrak{B}'} [\cap_{j \in K} B_j \cap \cap_r B_{r, \beta(r)}]} \pi_{UR} \quad (\text{T.5.4})$$

$$= \text{tr } \pi_{(\oplus_{\sigma \in \mathcal{W}_{\mathfrak{B}'}} M_\sigma)} \pi_{UR} \quad (\text{L.7.22})$$

$$= \sum_{\sigma \in \mathcal{W}_{\mathfrak{B}'}} \text{tr } \pi_{M_\sigma} \pi_{UR} \quad (\text{since the } M_\sigma \text{ are orthogonal}) \quad \mathbf{QED} \text{ (“}\geq\text{”)}$$

QED

L.7.28 For every $\mathfrak{B}' \subset \mathfrak{B}$,

$$\mu(G \wedge \exists \beta \in \mathfrak{B}' N_\beta) = \sum_{\beta \in \mathfrak{B}'} \text{tr } \pi_{M_{\sigma_\beta}} \pi_{UR}$$

Proof: Due to L.7.27,

$$\mu(G \wedge \exists \beta \in \mathfrak{B}' N_\beta) = \sum_{\sigma \in \mathcal{W}_{\mathfrak{B}'}} \text{tr } \pi_{M_\sigma} \pi_{UR}$$

For every $\sigma \in \mathcal{W}_{\mathfrak{B}'}$ we have either

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma &\in \mathcal{W}_{\mathfrak{B}'} \cap \{ \sigma_\beta \mid \beta \in \mathfrak{B} \} \\ &= \{ \sigma_\beta \mid \beta \in \mathfrak{B}' \} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{L.7.26})$$

or

$$\sigma \in \mathcal{W}_{\mathfrak{B}'} \text{ and } \sigma \notin \{ \sigma_\beta \mid \beta \in \mathfrak{B} \}$$

In the latter case,

$$\text{tr } \pi_{M_\sigma} \pi_{UR} = 0 \quad (\text{L.7.25})$$

Therefore,

$$\mu(G \wedge \exists \beta \in \mathfrak{B}' N_\beta) = \sum_{\beta \in \mathfrak{B}'} \text{tr } \pi_{M_{\sigma_\beta}} \pi_{UR}$$

QED

Using L.7.28, we now define a conditional outer measure on the algebra of all possible results of the experiment and show that this outer measure has the properties of a probability measure in the sense of Kolmogorov.

Let

$$q_\beta := \text{tr } \pi_{M_{\sigma_\beta}} \pi_{UR} \quad (\text{for all } \beta \in \mathfrak{B})$$

$$\bar{q} := \sum_{\beta \in \mathfrak{B}} q_\beta$$

$$p_\beta := q_\beta / \bar{q} \quad (\text{for all } \beta \in \mathfrak{B})$$

Then obviously: $\sum_{\beta \in \mathfrak{B}} p_\beta = 1$

L.7.29 Using the definition of q_β , L.7.28 can be written as:

$$\mu(G \wedge \exists \beta \in \mathfrak{B}' N_\beta) = \sum_{\beta \in \mathfrak{B}'} q_\beta \quad (\text{for all } \mathfrak{B}' \subset \mathfrak{B})$$

L.7.30 With $\mathfrak{B}' = \mathfrak{B}$, we obtain from L.7.29 (due to L.7.15):

$$\mu(G \wedge N) = \bar{q}$$

L.7.31 It is:

$$\mu(\exists \beta \in \mathfrak{B}' N_\beta \mid G \wedge N) = \sum_{\beta \in \mathfrak{B}'} p_\beta \quad (\text{for all } \mathfrak{B}' \subset \mathfrak{B})$$

The condition $G \wedge N$ appearing here specifies that all conditions of the experiment are met and that at least one outcome has been obtained for each alternative, thus successfully completing the experiment.

Proof: It is

$$\begin{aligned} &\mu(\exists \beta \in \mathfrak{B}' N_\beta \mid G \wedge N) \\ &= \mu(G \wedge N \wedge \exists \beta \in \mathfrak{B}' N_\beta) / \mu(G \wedge N) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \mu(G \wedge \exists \beta \in \mathfrak{B}' N_\beta) / \mu(G \wedge N) && \text{(since } N_\beta \subset N \text{)} \\
 &= \Sigma_{\beta \in \mathfrak{B}'} q_\beta / \bar{q} && \text{(L.7.29 and L.7.30)} \\
 &= \Sigma_{\beta \in \mathfrak{B}'} p_\beta
 \end{aligned}$$

QED

We define

$$\mathcal{A}_e := \mathcal{A}(\{ \langle A_{rs} \rangle \mid (r,s) \in D \})$$

to be the subalgebra of \mathcal{A} generated by the set of all possible results of the experiment. Specifically, the possible facts M, N, Q , as well as N_β and Q_β are elements of \mathcal{A}_e .

On \mathcal{A}_e we define

$$\mu_e(A) := \mu(A \mid G \wedge N) \quad (\text{for all } A \in \mathcal{A}_e)$$

μ_e is the restriction of the conditional outer measure $\mu(\mid G \wedge N)$ to the subalgebra \mathcal{A}_e and thus itself is an outer measure. It turns out that μ_e is even a Kolmogorov probability measure (see T.7.2 below).

Theorem T.7.2 μ_e is a probability measure on \mathcal{A}_e .

Proof: In particular, the additivity of μ_e must be proven. The possible facts

$$Q_\beta = \forall_r [\langle A_{r,\beta(r)} \rangle \wedge \forall_{s \neq \beta(r)} \neg \langle A_{rs} \rangle] \quad (\text{cf. L.7.16})$$

(insofar as they are not empty) are atomic elements of \mathcal{A}_e . Each $A \in \mathcal{A}_e$ is a union of atomic elements of the form

$$\forall_{(r,s) \in D'} \langle A_{rs} \rangle \wedge \forall_{(r,s) \notin D'} \neg \langle A_{rs} \rangle$$

with a set $D' \subset D$.

Because of $Q = \exists \beta \in \mathfrak{B} Q_\beta$, we can always write $A \wedge Q$ as

$$A \wedge Q = \exists \beta \in \mathfrak{B}' Q_\beta$$

with a suitable $\mathfrak{B}' \subset \mathfrak{B}$. Every empty Q_β can be omitted, i.e., without loss of generality, Q_β is non-empty for all $\beta \in \mathfrak{B}'$.

Now let $A, B \in \mathcal{A}_e$ be disjoint elements. Then there exist $\mathfrak{B}' \subset \mathfrak{B}$ and $\mathfrak{B}'' \subset \mathfrak{B}$ such that

$$A \wedge Q = \exists \beta \in \mathfrak{B}' Q_\beta$$

$$B \wedge Q = \exists \beta \in \mathfrak{B}'' Q_\beta$$

as well as

$$\mathfrak{B}' \cap \mathfrak{B}'' = \emptyset.$$

Due to (EX1), $G \subset M$ (cf. L.7.19) and thus $(G \wedge N) = (G \wedge Q)$. Therefore, for all $A' \in \mathcal{A}_e$,

$$(*) \mu_e(A') = \mu_e(A' \wedge Q)$$

It now follows that:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mu_e(A \vee B) &= \mu_e((A \wedge Q) \vee (B \wedge Q)) && \text{(according to (*))} \\
 &= \mu_e(\exists \beta \in \mathfrak{B}' Q_\beta \vee \exists \beta \in \mathfrak{B}'' Q_\beta)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \mu_e(\exists \beta \in \mathfrak{B}' \cup \mathfrak{B}'' Q_\beta) \\
 &= \mu_e(\exists \beta \in \mathfrak{B}' \cup \mathfrak{B}'' N_\beta) && \text{(according to (*), since } Q_\beta = N_\beta \wedge Q) \\
 &= \sum_{\beta \in \mathfrak{B}' \cup \mathfrak{B}''} p_\beta && \text{(L.7.31)} \\
 &= \sum_{\beta \in \mathfrak{B}'} p_\beta + \sum_{\beta \in \mathfrak{B}''} p_\beta
 \end{aligned}$$

Similarly,

$$\mu_e(A) = \sum_{\beta \in \mathfrak{B}'} p_\beta$$

and

$$\mu_e(B) = \sum_{\beta \in \mathfrak{B}''} p_\beta$$

From this we get

$$\mu_e(A \vee B) = \mu_e(A) + \mu_e(B)$$

and thus the additivity of μ_e .

QED

According to T.7.2, μ_e is a Kolmogorov probability measure. Since the weak law of large numbers applies here, $\mu_e(A)$ also plays the role of the “expected frequency”. We therefore do not need to distinguish between the improbability $\mu_e(A)$ and the expected frequency $P_e(A)$ and can assume the equality $P_e = \mu_e$ (on the algebra \mathcal{A}_e). So we obtain:

Theorem T.7.3 With

$$P_e(A) := \mu(A \mid G \wedge N) \quad (\text{for all } A \in \mathcal{A}_e)$$

P_e is defined as an additive probability measure in the sense of Kolmogorov on the algebra of all possible experimental results.

B8. Measurements on quantum systems

The aim of this chapter is to show that the realistic quantum theory considered here says the same about measurements on quantum systems as the Copenhagen formalism. The chapter consists of the following subsections:

1. Quantum experiments: prerequisites and definitions
2. Reduction and commutability of experimental results
3. The probability measure on the algebra of possible experimental results
4. Some more definitions
5. Calculation of outcome probabilities using quantum states
6. The quantum state after measurement

1. Quantum experiments: prerequisites and definitions

This section describes the formal representation of quantum experiments.

A quantum experiment is a special macroscopic experiment in which the experimental results are interpreted as “measurement results”. In this sense (see Chapter B7), let $(E_1, t_1), \dots, (E_n, t_n)$ be a t -accessible sequence of events with the index set $J := \{1, \dots, n\}$ and the dependency relation \ll . Let J be divided into the subranges:

$$\begin{aligned} K' &:= \{1, \dots, q\} && \text{(conditions of the experiment)} \\ K'' &:= \{q+1, \dots, n\} && \text{(possible experimental results)} \end{aligned}$$

and assume the following condition:

$$(+)\ j \ll k \Leftrightarrow j < k \wedge j \in K' \quad (\text{for all } j, k \in J)$$

The sequence of events under consideration thus forms a standard context.

The experimental results are divided into R alternatives $\mathcal{A}_1, \dots, \mathcal{A}_R$ with S_r possible outcomes for the r -th alternative. Thus, the index range for the possible results is

$$D := \{ (r, s) \mid r \in \{1, \dots, R\} \wedge s \in \{1, \dots, S_r\} \}$$

Let

$$k : D \rightarrow K''$$

be the bijective mapping that identifies the index ranges D and K'' with each other. Each pair $(r, s) \in D$ thus corresponds to exactly one element of the sequence $(E_{q+1}, t_{q+1}), \dots, (E_n, t_n)$.

We define the following abbreviations:

$$E_{rs} := E_{k(r,s)} \quad (\text{for } (r,s) \in D)$$

$$t_{rs} := t_{k(r,s)} \quad (\text{for } (r,s) \in D)$$

$$A_j := U_{-t_j} E_j \quad (\text{for } j \in K')$$

$$A_{rs} := U_{-t_{rs}} E_{rs} \quad (\text{for } (r,s) \in D)$$

Because of

$$\langle A_j \rangle = \langle E_j, t_j \rangle \quad (\text{by SE, for all } j \in K')$$

the expression $\langle A_j \rangle$ denotes the possible fact that the event (E_j, t_j) occurs. Similarly, $\langle A_{rs} \rangle$ corresponds to the event (E_{rs}, t_{rs}) .

In a quantum experiment, measurements are performed on one or more quantum systems. Since multiple quantum systems can always be viewed as a single overall system, it suffices to consider the case of *one single* system. Such a quantum system corresponds to a subsystem of \mathcal{H} , the Hilbert space of the universe. So, in the following, we consider one specific subsystem Q , which is the object of the quantum experiment under consideration. Q^- denotes the associated “rest of the world”, and we have

$$\mathcal{H} = \mathcal{H}_Q \otimes \mathcal{H}_{Q^-}$$

Each property of the subsystem Q corresponds in a canonical way to a property of the universe. In this sense, for each subspace A' of \mathcal{H}_Q ,

$$\alpha_Q(A') := A' \otimes \mathcal{H}_{Q^-}$$

is the corresponding subspace of the Hilbert space of the universe.

The observation of an alternative corresponds to the measurement of an observable. Let the observables associated with the alternatives $\mathcal{A}_1, \dots, \mathcal{A}_R$ be $\mathcal{X}_1, \dots, \mathcal{X}_R$. The observable \mathcal{X}_r can take exactly S_r different values. Therefore, \mathcal{X}_r is an operator with a finite spectrum and its spectral representation is

$$\mathcal{X}_r = \sum_s \lambda_{rs} \pi_{F_{rs}}$$

Here, λ_{rs} are the pairwise distinct (real) eigenvalues of \mathcal{X}_r and F_{rs} are the pairwise orthogonal eigenspaces, which satisfy the equation

$$\bigoplus_s F_{rs} = \mathcal{H}_Q$$

Let τ_r be the point in time at which the measurement of \mathcal{X}_r takes place. These points in time are arranged in ascending order, i.e., we have

$$\tau_1 \leq \dots \leq \tau_R$$

The order in which the measurements of the observables take place is thus determined.

For all $(r,s) \in D$, let

$$X_{rs} := \alpha_Q(F_{rs})$$

Thus, the occurrence of the event (X_{rs}, τ_r) is equivalent to the fact that the observable \mathcal{X}_r has the value λ_{rs} at time τ_r .

Between the event (X_{rs}, τ_r) , which describes the fact that the observable \mathcal{X}_r has the value λ_{rs} at time τ_r , and the corresponding measurement result (E_{rs}, t_{rs}) , there must be a “measurement relationship” (under the given experimental conditions). Based on this measurement relationship, the observation of the event (E_{rs}, t_{rs}) can be interpreted as a “measurement” of the value λ_{rs} for the observable \mathcal{X}_r at time τ_r .

Note: τ_r denotes the time at which the observable \mathcal{X}_r is measured on Q. In contrast, t_{rs} is the time at which the measurement result (E_{rs}, t_{rs}) is available and can be read out (in case that the value obtained from the measurement is λ_{rs}). We can therefore assume:

$$\tau_r \leq t_{rs} \quad (\text{for all } (r,s) \in D)$$

In principle, a measurement relationship has the same form as a document relationship. However, we do not assume measurement relationships to be independent of the outcomes of subsequent measurements. Like a document relationship, a measurement relationship in general exists only under certain conditions. In the case of the experiment considered here, we let

$$L := \pi_{A_q} \dots \pi_{A_1} \pi_{UR}$$

as well as

$$B_{rs} := U_{-\tau_r} X_{rs} \quad (\text{for } (r,s) \in D)$$

and then assume (for every $(r,s) \in D$) the existence of a measurement relationship between (X_{rs}, τ_r) and (E_{rs}, t_{rs}) if the following holds:

$$(MR1) \quad \pi_{B_{rs}} L = \pi_{A_{rs}} L$$

This equation describes the existence of the measurement relationship under all experimental conditions, including the initial condition. The expression $\langle A_{rs} \rangle$ denotes the possible fact that the event (E_{rs}, t_{rs}) occurs. Similarly, $\langle B_{rs} \rangle$ describes the event (X_{rs}, τ_r) . If the measurement relationship (MR1) holds, then $\langle A_{rs} \rangle$ corresponds to the possible fact that the value λ_{rs} is measured on the observable \mathcal{X}_r at time τ_r .

For all $r \in \{0, \dots, R\}$, we define

$$\mathfrak{B}_r := \{ \beta : \{1, \dots, r\} \rightarrow \mathbb{N} \mid \forall_{r' \leq r} \beta(r') \in \{1, \dots, S_{r'}\} \}$$

to be the set of all possible outcome constellations for the observables $\mathcal{X}_1, \dots, \mathcal{X}_r$. An element $\beta \in \mathfrak{B}_r$ specifies which outcomes are realized in the first r measurements. For all $r \in \{0, \dots, R\}$ and $\beta \in \mathfrak{B}_r$, let

$$L_{\beta, r} := \pi_{A_{r, \beta(r)}} \dots \pi_{A_{1, \beta(1)}} L$$

We expect the measurement relationships for the r -th observable to be independent of the outcomes of previous measurements. For the relationship between (X_{rs}, τ_r) and (E_{rs}, t_{rs}) , the following must therefore apply to any outcome constellation $\beta \in \mathfrak{B}_{r-1}$:

$$(MR) \quad \pi_{B_{rs}} L_{\beta, r-1} = \pi_{A_{rs}} L_{\beta, r-1}$$

Equation (MR) holds for all $r \in \{1, \dots, R\}$ (for all measured observables), for all $s \in \{1, \dots, S_r\}$ (for every possible value of these observables) and for all $\beta \in \mathfrak{B}_{r-1}$ (i.e., for all outcome constellations of the observables \mathcal{X}_1 to \mathcal{X}_{r-1}).

As before, we define the possible facts

$$G := \langle UR \rangle \wedge \forall_{j \in K'} \langle A_j \rangle$$

$$N := \forall_r \exists_s \langle A_{rs} \rangle$$

G states that all conditions of the experiment are met, and N states that at least one possible outcome is realized for each of the alternatives.

In addition to G and N, the expressions \mathfrak{B} and \bar{q} as well as N_β , σ_β , q_β , p_β , and W_β (for each outcome constellation $\beta \in \mathfrak{B}$) and $W_{\mathfrak{B}'}$ (for every subset $\mathfrak{B}' \subset \mathfrak{B}$) are defined in the same way as in Chapter B7, Sections 4 to 6. We also assume that the set \mathcal{W} and the expressions $A_{j;\tau}$ (for $\tau \in \{0,1,\emptyset\}$ and $j \in J$) as well as M_σ and M^\wedge (for $\sigma \in \mathcal{W}$) are defined as in Chapter B7, Section 2.

2. Reduction and commutability of experimental results

In this section we show that the expression

$$\pi_{A_n} \cdots \pi_{A_{q+1}} \pi_{A_q} \cdots \pi_{A_1} \pi_{UR}$$

is independent of the order in which the experimental results A_{q+1}, \dots, A_n are listed, and that this also applies if one restricts oneself to a subset of the experimental results and/or replaces some of the A_j (for $j > q$) by $(A_j)^\perp$ (see L.8.5, L.8.6, and L.8.7 below).

According to definition D.7.2, a standard context is a t -accessible sequence of events $(E_1, t_1), \dots, (E_n, t_n)$, whose index set J is divided into two subranges K' and K'' such that for the dependency relation the following applies:

$$(+) \quad j \ll k \Leftrightarrow j < k \wedge j \in K' \quad (\text{for all } j, k \in J)$$

According to definition D.7.1, the t -accessibility of events means that for all $k \in J$ and for every sequence $B_1, \dots, B_n < \mathcal{H}$ that satisfies conditions (i) to (iii) of D.7.1, the document relationship (DR) holds.

If, in the definition of a standard context, conditions (i) and (ii) are replaced by

$$(i_D) \quad B_j = D_j \quad (\text{for all } j \in J_k)$$

$$(ii_D) \quad B_j \in \{D_j, \mathcal{H}\} \quad (\text{for all } j \in J \setminus J_k \setminus \{k\})$$

we speak of a “D-context”. The third condition

$$(iii) \quad B_k = \mathcal{H}$$

remains unchanged here.

L.8.1 Every standard context is a D-context.

Proof: We consider the standard context introduced in the previous section with all notations defined there. It must now be shown that for every $k \in J$ and for all sequences $B_1, \dots, B_n < \mathcal{H}$ which satisfy conditions (i_D) , (ii_D) , and (iii) , the document relationship (DR) holds. So, let $k \in J$ and let B_1, \dots, B_n be such a sequence. With q being the number of conditions of the context, we let $p := \min\{q, k-1\}$. Since condition $(+)$ applies, we have $J_k = \{1, \dots, p\}$ and thus for all $j \leq p$:

$$B_j = D_j \quad (\text{because of } (i_D))$$

For $j > p$, we have $B_j \in \{D_j, \mathcal{H}\}$ and consequently $B_j \in \{A_j, D_j, \mathcal{H}\}$. The sequence

$$A_1, \dots, A_p, B_{p+1}, \dots, B_n$$

therefore satisfies conditions (i) to (iii), and for the standard context assumed here, we have the document relationship

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_{A_k} \pi_{B_n} \dots \pi_{B_{p+1}} \pi_{A_p} \dots \pi_{A_1} \pi_{UR} \\ = \pi_{D_k} \pi_{B_n} \dots \pi_{B_{p+1}} \pi_{A_p} \dots \pi_{A_1} \pi_{UR} \end{aligned}$$

By setting $\sigma(j) := 1$ for all $j \in J$, we obtain by L.7.4:

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_{A_p} \dots \pi_{A_1} \pi_{UR} &= \pi_{D_p} \dots \pi_{D_1} \pi_{UR} \\ &= \pi_{B_p} \dots \pi_{B_1} \pi_{UR} \end{aligned}$$

and consequently

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_{A_k} \pi_{B_n} \dots \pi_{B_{p+1}} \pi_{B_p} \dots \pi_{B_1} \pi_{UR} \\ = \pi_{D_k} \pi_{B_n} \dots \pi_{B_{p+1}} \pi_{B_p} \dots \pi_{B_1} \pi_{UR} \end{aligned}$$

This is the relationship (DR) to be proven. **QED**

L.8.2 Using notations from L.7.3, the following statement holds for every D-context: For all $k \in J$, $\sigma \in \mathcal{W}'$, and every sequence $B_1, \dots, B_n < \mathcal{H}$ that satisfies the conditions

- (i_D') $B_j = H_j$ (for all $j \in J_k$)
- (ii_D') $B_j \in \{H_j, \mathcal{H}\}$ (for all $j \in J \setminus J_k \setminus \{k\}$)
- (iii') $B_k = \mathcal{H}$

the following equation holds:

$$(DR') \pi_{G_k} \pi_{B_n} \dots \pi_{B_1} \pi_{UR} = \pi_{H_k} \pi_{B_n} \dots \pi_{B_1} \pi_{UR}$$

Proof: The proof of this statement can be carried out in exactly the same way as the proof of L.7.3. (Simply replace A_j with D_j , G_j with H_j , and G_v with H_v throughout.) **QED**

L.8.3 Using notations from L.7.4, the following applies to every D-context: For every $\sigma \in \mathcal{W}$ and $k \in J \cup \{0\}$,

$$\pi_{G_k} \dots \pi_{G_1} \pi_{UR} = \pi_{H_k} \dots \pi_{H_1} \pi_{UR}$$

Proof: The proof is carried out by complete induction on the index k . The case $k = 0$ is trivial. Now let $k \in J$. Then:

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_{G_k} \pi_{G_{k-1}} \dots \pi_{G_1} \pi_{UR} \\ = \pi_{G_k} \pi_{H_{k-1}} \dots \pi_{H_1} \pi_{UR} &\quad (\text{by the induction hypothesis}) \\ = \pi_{H_k} \pi_{H_{k-1}} \dots \pi_{H_1} \pi_{UR} &\quad (\text{using L.8.2, with } B_j := H_j \text{ for } j < k \\ &\quad \text{and } B_j := \mathcal{H} \text{ for } j \geq k) \end{aligned} \quad \text{QED}$$

L.8.4 Using notations from L.7.5, the following applies to every D-context: For all $\sigma \in \mathcal{W}$,

$$\pi_{\sigma} \pi_{UR} = \pi_{M_{\sigma}} \pi_{UR}$$

Proof: Let $\sigma \in \mathcal{W}$. Using the abbreviations

$$G_j := A_{j;\sigma(j)} \quad (\text{for all } j \in J)$$

$$H_j := D_{j;\sigma(j)} \quad (\text{for all } j \in J)$$

we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \pi_\sigma \pi_{UR} \\ &= \pi_{G_n} \cdots \pi_{G_{k+1}} \pi_{G_k} \pi_{G_{k-1}} \cdots \pi_{G_1} \pi_{UR} && (\text{definition of } \pi_\sigma) \\ &= \pi_{H_n} \cdots \pi_{H_{k+1}} \pi_{H_k} \pi_{H_{k-1}} \cdots \pi_{H_1} \pi_{UR} && (\text{L.8.3}) \\ &= \pi_{H_k} \pi_{H_n} \cdots \pi_{H_{k+1}} \pi_{H_{k-1}} \cdots \pi_{H_1} \pi_{UR} && (\text{just like the } D_j, \text{ the } H_j \\ & && \text{are pairwise commutable}) \\ &= \pi_{G_k} \pi_{H_n} \cdots \pi_{H_{k+1}} \pi_{H_{k-1}} \cdots \pi_{H_1} \pi_{UR} && (\text{L.8.2}) \end{aligned}$$

The proof can now be continued in the same way as the proof of L.7.5. **QED**

L.8.5 Let there be a D-context with the sequence of events $(E_1, t_1), \dots, (E_n, t_n)$, the dependency relation \ll , and the division of the index set $J := \{1, \dots, n\}$ into the subranges

$$K' := \{1, \dots, q\} \quad (\text{conditions})$$

and

$$K'' := \{q+1, \dots, n\} \quad (\text{events of interest})$$

Furthermore, let

$$\sigma : K'' \rightarrow K''$$

be a bijection. The mapping σ describes a permutation of the events of interest. If we now replace the above sequence of events by the sequence

$$(E_1, t_1), \dots, (E_q, t_q), (E_{\sigma(q+1)}, t_{\sigma(q+1)}), \dots, (E_{\sigma(n)}, t_{\sigma(n)})$$

we again obtain a D-context.

Proof: Since we are starting from a D-context, the following condition applies:

$$(+)\ j \ll k \Leftrightarrow j < k \wedge j \in K' \quad (\text{for all } j, k \in J)$$

The validity of this condition does not change when the elements of K'' are permuted. Now, let (F_j, t) be documents of (E_j, t_j) as well as

$$A_j := U_{-t_j} E_j$$

and

$$D_j := U_{-t} F_j$$

such that for all $k \in J$ and for every sequence B_1, \dots, B_n that satisfies conditions (i_D) , (ii_D) , and (iii) , the document relationship

$$(DR) \ \pi_{A_k} \pi_{B_n} \cdots \pi_{B_1} \pi_{UR} = \pi_{D_k} \pi_{B_n} \cdots \pi_{B_1} \pi_{UR}$$

holds. Based on the assumptions (i_D) , (ii_D) , and (iii) , we have for all $j \in J$:

$$B_j \in \{D_j, \mathcal{H}\}$$

Consequently, all B_j are commutable, and the validity of the document relationship remains unchanged when the events of interest are permuted. For a given $k \in J$, conditions (i_D) , (ii_D) , and (iii) also remain unchanged by such a permutation. **QED**

L.8.6 For every standard context based on a given sequence of events $(E_1, t_1), \dots, (E_n, t_n)$ with $A_j := U_{-t_j} E_j$ and $K' := \{1, \dots, q\}$, and for every subsequence B_1, \dots, B_m of A_{q+1}, \dots, A_n (i.e., for a subset of the events of interest), with the abbreviation

$$L := \pi_{A_q} \dots \pi_{A_1} \pi_{UR}$$

as defined above, the expression

$$\pi_{B_m} \dots \pi_{B_1} L$$

is independent of the order in which the factors π_{B_k} occur.

Proof: According to L.7.13, if we omit all events of interest in the context except B_1, \dots, B_m , we obtain a standard context again. According to L.8.1, this is also a D-context. In the following, the expressions π_σ , M_σ , \mathcal{W} , and J are used as if they were defined for this D-context.

Due to L.8.4, the equation

$$(*) \pi_\sigma \pi_{UR} = \pi_{M_\sigma} \pi_{UR}$$

holds for every assignment $\sigma \in \mathcal{W}$. If $\sigma(j) := 1$ for all $j \in J$, then with

$$A := \bigcap_{k \in \{1, \dots, m\}} B_k \cap \bigcap_{j \in \{1, \dots, q\}} A_j$$

we obtain the equation:

$$(**) \pi_{B_m} \dots \pi_{B_1} L = \pi_A \pi_{UR}$$

According to L.8.5, permuting the events of interest in the D-context under consideration yields another D-context. For it, equation (*) also applies. Since the expression A does not depend on the order of the B_k , (**) still applies after permuting the events of interest. From this, the assertion of the lemma immediately follows. **QED**

L.8.7 The statement of L.8.6 still applies if some of the B_k are replaced by $(B_k)^\perp$.

Proof: The proof of L.8.6 can be adopted here almost word for word. One only has to choose a different $\sigma \in \mathcal{W}$: For each $k \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ where B_k has been replaced by $(B_k)^\perp$, the assignment σ must have the value 0 instead of 1 at the corresponding position. **QED**

3. The probability measure on the algebra of possible experimental results

In this section we show that, under the conditions of a quantum experiment, a Kolmogorov probability measure is obtained on the algebra of possible experimental results, so that no distinction needs to be made between the (im-) probability and the “expected frequency” on that algebra.

L.8.8 From (MR) it follows for all $(r, s) \in D$ and $\beta \in \mathfrak{B}_{r-1}$ that

$$(MR') \pi_{B_{rs}} L' = \pi_{A_{rs}} L'$$

where L' is formed in the same way as $L_{\beta, r-1}$, but using only a subsequence of the factors $\pi_{A_{k, \beta(k)}}$ that appear in the definition of $L_{\beta, r-1}$.

Proof: Omitting one of the factors $\pi_{A_{k,\beta(k)}}$ corresponds to replacing $A_{k,\beta(k)}$ with \mathcal{H} . So let $\beta \in \mathfrak{B}_{r-1}$ and let a sequence G_k of subspaces of \mathcal{H} be given such that

$$G_k \in \{A_{k,\beta(k)}, \mathcal{H}\} \quad (\text{for } k \in \{1, \dots, r-1\})$$

For

$$L' := \pi_{G_{r-1}} \dots \pi_{G_1} L$$

the relationship (MR') must then be proven.

Let N be the number of indices $k \in \{1, \dots, r-1\}$ with $G_k \neq A_{k,\beta(k)}$. The proof is carried out by complete induction on N . For $N = 0$, there is nothing to prove, since in this case (MR') transforms into (MR). Let us now assume that $N > 0$ and that (MR') is true for all $N' < N$ (induction hypothesis).

Let m be the smallest index $k \in \{1, \dots, r-1\}$ with $G_k \neq A_{k,\beta(k)}$. Then $G_m = \mathcal{H}$. Because of

$$\mathcal{H}_Q = \bigoplus_{s'} F_{ms'}$$

we have

$$\mathcal{H} = \bigoplus_{s'} B_{ms'}$$

Furthermore, for fixed m , the $B_{ms'}$ (like the $F_{ms'}$) are pairwise orthogonal. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} L' &= \pi_{G_{r-1}} \dots \pi_{G_1} L \\ &= \prod_{k=r-1..1} \pi_{G_k} L \\ &= \prod_{k=r-1..m+1} \pi_{G_k} \pi_{G_m} \prod_{k=m-1..1} \pi_{G_k} L \\ &= \prod_{k=r-1..m+1} \pi_{G_k} \pi_{\mathcal{H}} \prod_{k=m-1..1} \pi_{A_{k,\beta(k)}} L \\ &= \prod_{k=r-1..m+1} \pi_{G_k} \pi_{\bigoplus_{s'} B_{ms'}} \prod_{k=m-1..1} \pi_{A_{k,\beta(k)}} L \\ &= \sum_{s'} \prod_{k=r-1..m+1} \pi_{G_k} \pi_{B_{ms'}} \prod_{k=m-1..1} \pi_{A_{k,\beta(k)}} L \\ &= \sum_{s'} \prod_{k=r-1..m+1} \pi_{G_k} \pi_{A_{ms'}} \prod_{k=m-1..1} \pi_{A_{k,\beta(k)}} L \end{aligned}$$

The latter follows directly from (MR), applied to m instead of r .

For every $s' \in \{1, \dots, S_m\}$ let $\beta_{s'} \in \mathfrak{B}_{r-1}$ be defined by

$$\begin{aligned} \beta_{s'}(k) &:= \beta(k) \quad (\text{for } k \in \{1, \dots, r-1\} \setminus \{m\}) \\ \beta_{s'}(m) &:= s' \end{aligned}$$

By applying the induction hypothesis to $\beta_{s'}$ for each s' , we obtain the equations

$$\begin{aligned} (\text{MR}'_{s'}) \pi_{B_{rs'}} \prod_{k=r-1..m+1} \pi_{G_k} \pi_{A_{ms'}} \prod_{k=m-1..1} \pi_{A_{k,\beta(k)}} L \\ = \pi_{A_{rs'}} \prod_{k=r-1..m+1} \pi_{G_k} \pi_{A_{ms'}} \prod_{k=m-1..1} \pi_{A_{k,\beta(k)}} L \end{aligned}$$

since the sequence

$$G_{r-1}, \dots, G_{m+1}, A_{ms'}, A_{m-1,\beta(m-1)}, \dots, A_{1,\beta(1)}$$

differs from the sequence

$$A_{r-1,\beta_{s'}(r-1)}, \dots, A_{1,\beta_{s'}(1)}$$

at only $N-1$ positions. By summing over s' , we obtain the equation to be proven, i.e.,

$$\pi_{B_{rs}} L' = \pi_{A_{rs}} L'$$

from the equations (MR'_s) together with the above representation of L' as a sum. **QED**

L.8.9 For all $\psi \in \mathcal{H}$ with $|\psi| = 1$ and $A < \mathcal{H}$,

$$\pi_{[\psi]} \pi_A \psi = |\pi_A \psi|^2 \psi$$

Proof: It is

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_{[\psi]} \pi_A \psi &= \psi \psi^* \pi_A \pi_A \psi \\ &= \psi (\pi_A \psi)^* \pi_A \psi \\ &= \psi |\pi_A \psi|^2 \end{aligned}$$

QED

L.8.10 For all $\psi \in \mathcal{H}$ and $A_1, \dots, A_m < \mathcal{H}$,

$$\psi + \sum_{k \in \{1, \dots, m\}} \pi_{A_k} \psi = 0 \Rightarrow \psi = 0$$

Proof: Let $\psi \in \mathcal{H}$ and $\psi \neq 0$. We can assume, without loss of generality, that $|\psi| = 1$. Then:

$$\begin{aligned} \psi + \sum_k \pi_{A_k} \psi &= 0 \\ \Rightarrow \pi_{[\psi]} [\psi + \sum_k \pi_{A_k} \psi] &= 0 \\ \Rightarrow \psi + \sum_k \pi_{[\psi]} \pi_{A_k} \psi &= 0 \\ \Rightarrow \psi + \sum_k |\pi_{A_k} \psi|^2 \psi &= 0 \quad (\text{L.8.9}) \\ \Rightarrow [1 + \sum_k |\pi_{A_k} \psi|^2] \psi &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

contradicting $\psi \neq 0$. **QED**

L.8.11 The measurement relationships (MR) imply:

$$(EX1) \quad \forall_r \forall_{s \neq s'} \neg \diamond (G \wedge \langle A_{rs} \rangle \wedge \langle A_{rs'} \rangle)$$

Condition (EX1) states that, under the assumption G , a simultaneous realization of more than one outcome for the same alternative is impossible.

Proof: From (MR), the relationship (MR') follows according to L.8.8. Now let $r \in \{1, \dots, R\}$ as well as $s, s' \in \{1, \dots, S_r\}$ with $s \neq s'$. Because of

$$\mathcal{H} = \bigoplus_{k \in \{1, \dots, S_r\}} B_{rk}$$

and since the B_{rk} are pairwise orthogonal, the following holds for every $\varphi \in \mathcal{H}$:

$$\begin{aligned} \psi &:= \pi_{A_{rs}} \pi_{A_{rs'}} L \varphi \\ &= \pi_{A_{rs}} \pi_{A_{rs'}} \pi_{\bigoplus_k B_{rk}} L \varphi \\ &= \sum_k \pi_{A_{rs}} \pi_{A_{rs'}} \pi_{B_{rk}} L \varphi \\ &= \sum_k \pi_{A_{rs}} \pi_{A_{rs'}} \pi_{A_{rk}} L \varphi \quad (\text{according to (MR')}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \pi_{A_{rs}} \pi_{A_{rs}'} \pi_{A_{rs}}^L \varphi \\
 &\quad + \pi_{A_{rs}} \pi_{A_{rs}'} \pi_{A_{rs}'}^L \varphi \\
 &\quad + \sum_{k \notin \{s, s'\}} \pi_{A_{rs}} \pi_{A_{rs}'} \pi_{A_{rk}}^L \varphi \\
 &= \pi_{A_{rs}} \pi_{A_{rs}} \pi_{A_{rs}'}^L \varphi \\
 &\quad + \pi_{A_{rs}} \pi_{A_{rs}'} \pi_{A_{rs}'}^L \varphi \\
 &\quad + \sum_{k \notin \{s, s'\}} \pi_{A_{rk}} \pi_{A_{rs}} \pi_{A_{rs}'}^L \varphi \quad (\text{L.8.6}) \\
 &= \psi + \psi + \left(\sum_{k \notin \{s, s'\}} \pi_{A_{rk}} \psi \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

From this it follows that

$$\psi + \left(\sum_{k \notin \{s, s'\}} \pi_{A_{rk}} \psi \right) = 0$$

and by L.8.10

$$\psi = 0$$

Since this holds for every $\varphi \in \mathcal{H}$, we have

$$\pi_{A_{rs}} \pi_{A_{rs}'}^L = 0$$

With

$$A := A_{rs} \cap A_{rs}' \cap \bigcap_j A_j$$

we get (as in the proof of L.8.6):

$$\begin{aligned}
 \pi_A \pi_{UR} &= \pi_{A_{rs}} \pi_{A_{rs}'} \pi_{A_q} \dots \pi_{A_1} \pi_{UR} \\
 &= \pi_{A_{rs}} \pi_{A_{rs}'}^L \\
 &= 0
 \end{aligned}$$

and thus

$$A < UR^\perp$$

We consider the standard context in which $\langle A_{rs} \rangle$ and $\langle A_{rs}' \rangle$ are the only events of interest (cf. L.7.13). Using the definitions from Chapter B7, Section 2, we obtain commutable subspaces C_j , C_{rs} , and C_{rs}' as well as M^\wedge of \mathcal{H} with (cf. L.7.2, L.7.7 and L.7.8)

$$\begin{aligned}
 A_j &< C_j && \text{(for all } j \in \{1, \dots, q\}) \\
 A_{rs} &< C_{rs} \\
 A_{rs}' &< C_{rs}' \\
 UR &< M^\wedge
 \end{aligned}$$

Based on L.7.12 and L.7.9, we obtain with $\sigma(i) := 1$ (for all i) and

$$C := C_{rs} \cap C_{rs}' \cap \bigcap_j C_j$$

the relationship

$$\begin{aligned}
 C &< A \oplus (M^\wedge)^\perp && \text{(because of } M_\sigma = A) \\
 &< UR^\perp \oplus UR^\perp \\
 &= UR^\perp
 \end{aligned}$$

and thus

$$UR < C^\perp$$

Since

$$C^\perp \cap C_{rs} \cap C_{rs'} \cap \bigcap_j C_j = \mathbf{o}$$

we obtain, using MON and SEC,

$$\begin{aligned} G \wedge \langle A_{rs} \rangle \wedge \langle A_{rs'} \rangle &= \langle UR \rangle \wedge \forall_j \langle A_j \rangle \wedge \langle A_{rs} \rangle \wedge \langle A_{rs'} \rangle \\ &\subset \langle C^\perp \rangle \wedge \forall_j \langle C_j \rangle \wedge \langle C_{rs} \rangle \wedge \langle C_{rs'} \rangle \\ &= \emptyset \end{aligned}$$

and hence the assertion. **QED**

L.8.12 The measurement relationships (MR) imply:

$$(EX2) \quad \forall_r \neg \diamond (G \wedge \forall_s \langle (A_{rs})^\perp \rangle)$$

(EX2) states that for every alternative, under the assumption G , it is impossible that the “physical opposite” to each of its possible outcomes is realized.

Proof: From (MR), the relationship (MR') follows according to L.8.8. Let $r \in \{1, \dots, R\}$ and $S := S_r$. Because of

$$\mathcal{H} = \bigoplus_{s \in \{1, \dots, S\}} B_{rs}$$

and since the B_{rs} are pairwise orthogonal, the following holds for every $\varphi \in \mathcal{H}$:

$$\begin{aligned} \psi &:= \pi_{(A_{r1})^\perp} \dots \pi_{(A_{rS})^\perp} L \varphi \\ &= \pi_{(A_{r1})^\perp} \dots \pi_{(A_{rS})^\perp} \pi_{\bigoplus_s B_{rs}} L \varphi \\ &= \sum_s \pi_{(A_{r1})^\perp} \dots \pi_{(A_{rS})^\perp} \pi_{B_{rs}} L \varphi \\ &= \sum_s \pi_{(A_{r1})^\perp} \dots \pi_{(A_{rS})^\perp} \pi_{A_{rs}} L \varphi && \text{(according to (MR'))} \\ &= \sum_s \pi_{(A_{r1})^\perp} \dots \pi_{(A_{rs})^\perp} \pi_{A_{rs}} \pi_{(A_{r,s+1})^\perp} \dots \pi_{(A_{rS})^\perp} L \varphi && \text{(L.8.7)} \\ &= \mathbf{o} \end{aligned}$$

Since this applies to every $\varphi \in \mathcal{H}$, we have

$$\pi_{(A_{r1})^\perp} \dots \pi_{(A_{rS})^\perp} L = \mathbf{o}$$

With

$$A := \bigcap_s (A_{rs})^\perp \cap \bigcap_j A_j$$

we get (as in the proof of L.8.7)

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_A \pi_{UR} &= \pi_{(A_{r1})^\perp} \dots \pi_{(A_{rS})^\perp} \pi_{A_q} \dots \pi_{A_1} \pi_{UR} \\ &= \pi_{(A_{r1})^\perp} \dots \pi_{(A_{rS})^\perp} L \\ &= \mathbf{o} \end{aligned}$$

and thus

$$A < UR^\perp$$

We consider the standard context in which the $\langle A_{rs} \rangle$ (with $s \in \{1, \dots, S\}$) are the only events of interest (cf. L.7.13). Using the definitions from Chapter B7, Section 2, we obtain commutable subspaces C_j and $C_{rs;0}$ as well as M^\wedge of \mathcal{H} with (cf. L.7.2, L.7.7 and L.7.8)

$$A_j < C_j \quad (\text{for all } j \in \{1, \dots, q\})$$

$$(A_{rs})^\perp < C_{rs;0} \quad (\text{for all } s \in \{1, \dots, S\})$$

$$UR < M^\wedge$$

Based on L.7.12 and L.7.9, with

$$C := \bigcap_s C_{rs;0} \cap \bigcap_j C_j$$

we obtain the relationship

$$C < A \oplus (M^\wedge)^\perp \quad (\text{because of } M_\sigma = A)$$

$$< UR^\perp \oplus UR^\perp$$

$$= UR^\perp$$

and thus

$$UR < C^\perp$$

Since

$$C^\perp \cap \bigcap_s C_{rs;0} \cap \bigcap_j C_j = \emptyset$$

we obtain, using MON and SEC,

$$\begin{aligned} G \wedge \bigvee_s \langle (A_{rs})^\perp \rangle &= \langle UR \rangle \wedge \bigvee_j \langle A_j \rangle \wedge \bigvee_s \langle (A_{rs})^\perp \rangle \\ &\subset \langle C^\perp \rangle \wedge \bigvee_j \langle C_j \rangle \wedge \bigvee_s \langle C_{rs;0} \rangle \\ &= \emptyset \end{aligned}$$

and hence the assertion. **QED**

According to L.8.11, condition (EX1) applies. Thus, all statements from Chapter B7 can be used in the following. In this sense, we define

$$\mathcal{A}_e := \mathcal{A}(\{ \langle A_{rs} \rangle \mid (r,s) \in D \})$$

to be the algebra of all possible experimental results. \mathcal{A}_e is a subalgebra of \mathcal{A} .

Moreover, we define the outer measure

$$\mu_e(A) := \mu(A \mid G \wedge N) \quad (\text{for } A \in \mathcal{A}_e)$$

According to T.7.2, μ_e is a Kolmogorov probability measure. According to T.7.3, μ_e is identical to the “expected frequency” P_e , i.e., we have $P_e = \mu_e$ on the algebra \mathcal{A}_e .

4. Some more definitions

In order to show that the (conditional) probability of a particular measurement outcome occurring for one of the alternatives can be calculated using the equations known from the formalism of quantum theory on the basis of the corresponding (conditional) quantum state, some more definitions are required.

Let

$$\mathcal{W}_1 := \{ \sigma \in \mathcal{W} \mid \forall j \in K' \sigma(j) = 1 \}$$

be the set of assignments σ in \mathcal{W} that assign the value 1 to every condition of the experiment.

Based on the definitions of \mathcal{W} and \mathcal{W}_1 as well as condition (+), we obtain the identity

$$\mathcal{W}_1 = \{ \sigma : \{1, \dots, n\} \rightarrow \{0, 1\} \mid \forall j \in K' \sigma(j) = 1 \}$$

Because of $\mathcal{W}_1 \subset \mathcal{W}$, the following applies to all $\sigma \in \mathcal{W}_1$:

$$\pi_\sigma = \pi_{A_n; \sigma(n)} \cdots \pi_{A_1; \sigma(1)} \quad (\text{definition in Chapter B7, Section 2})$$

$$M_\sigma = \bigcap_{k \in J} A_{k; \sigma(k)} \quad (\text{definition in Chapter B7, Section 2})$$

$$\pi_\sigma \pi_{UR} = \pi_{M_\sigma} \pi_{UR} \quad (\text{L.7.5})$$

For all $\beta \in \mathfrak{B}$, we have $\sigma_\beta \in \mathcal{W}_1$ and

$$\sigma_\beta(k(r, s)) = 1 \quad \text{for all } (r, s) \in D \text{ with } s = \beta(r)$$

$$\sigma_\beta(k(r, s)) = 0 \quad \text{for all } (r, s) \in D \text{ with } s \neq \beta(r)$$

For all $r \in \{0, \dots, R\}$ and $\beta \in \mathfrak{B}_r$ let

$$\mathcal{G}_{\beta, r} := ((UR, 0), (E_1, t_1), \dots, (E_q, t_q), (E_1, \beta(1), t_{1, \beta(1)}), \dots, (E_r, \beta(r), t_{r, \beta(r)}))$$

$$Y_{\beta, r} := \langle A_{1, \beta(1)} \rangle \wedge \dots \wedge \langle A_{r, \beta(r)} \rangle$$

$\mathcal{G}_{\beta, r}$ represents, as a sequence of events, the outcomes of the first r measurements as specified by β , as well as the conditions of the experiment. On the other hand, $Y_{\beta, r}$ describes only the outcomes of the first r measurements, but as a possible fact.

For the following, choose some fixed element $\underline{r} \in \{0, \dots, R\}$ as well as $\underline{\beta} \in \mathfrak{B}_{\underline{r}}$. On this basis, let

$$\underline{D} := \{ (r, s) \in D \mid r \leq \underline{r} \}$$

$$\underline{J} := K' \cup \{ k(r, s) \mid (r, s) \in \underline{D} \}$$

\underline{D} and \underline{J} are the restrictions of the index ranges D and J to the first \underline{r} alternatives.

Analogous to σ_β , but restricted to the first \underline{r} alternatives, let

$$\underline{\sigma} : \underline{J} \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$$

be defined by:

$$\underline{\sigma}(j) := 1 \quad \text{for all } j \in K'$$

$$\underline{\sigma}(k(r, s)) := 1 \quad \text{for } (r, s) \in \underline{D} \text{ with } s = \underline{\beta}(r)$$

$$\underline{\sigma}(k(r, s)) := 0 \quad \text{for } (r, s) \in \underline{D} \text{ with } s \neq \underline{\beta}(r)$$

Moreover, let

$$\pi_{\underline{\sigma}} := \prod_{j \in \underline{J}} \pi_{A_j; \underline{\sigma}(j)}$$

where the product is formed in descending order of the elements of $\underline{J} \subset J$. Then $\pi_{\underline{\sigma}}$ is the analogue of π_{σ_β} , restricted to the first \underline{r} alternatives.

Furthermore, let:

$$\underline{\mathcal{W}} := \{ \sigma \in \mathcal{W}_1 \mid \sigma|_{\underline{J}} = \underline{\sigma} \}$$

$$\underline{\mathcal{B}} := \{ \beta \in \mathcal{B} \mid \beta|_{\{1, \dots, \underline{r}\}} = \underline{\beta} \}$$

$\underline{\mathcal{W}}$ is the set of assignments in \mathcal{W}_1 that coincide with $\underline{\sigma}$ for the first \underline{r} alternatives. Similarly, $\underline{\mathcal{B}}$ is the set of outcome constellations in \mathcal{B} that coincide with $\underline{\beta}$ for the first \underline{r} alternatives.

5. Calculation of outcome probabilities using quantum states

In this section, it will be shown that the (conditional) probability of a specific measurement outcome for one of the alternatives can be calculated on the basis of the corresponding (conditional) quantum state using the equations known from the formalism of quantum theory. Here, the condition of the quantum state must correspond to the condition of the probability to be calculated. This condition includes the prerequisites of the experiment as well as the outcomes of the preceding alternatives.

L.8.13 It is

$$\sum_{\sigma \in \underline{\mathcal{W}}} \pi_{\sigma} = \pi_{\underline{\sigma}}$$

Proof: First, consider the case where \underline{J} is an initial part of J , i.e., let $\underline{J} := \{1, \dots, \underline{n}\}$ with some $\underline{n} \in \mathbb{N}$. Now let

$$\mathcal{W}_+ := \{ \sigma' \mid \sigma' : J \setminus \underline{J} \rightarrow \{0, 1\} \}$$

be the set of all assignments on $J \setminus \underline{J}$. We then have

$$\underline{\mathcal{W}} = \{ \underline{\sigma} \cup \sigma' \mid \sigma' \in \mathcal{W}_+ \}$$

where $\underline{\sigma} \cup \sigma'$ denotes the assignment that coincides with $\underline{\sigma}$ on \underline{J} and with σ' on $J \setminus \underline{J}$.

For all j ,

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_{A_j;1} + \pi_{A_j;0} &= \pi_{A_j} + \pi_{(A_j)^\perp} \\ &= I_{\mathcal{H}} \end{aligned}$$

It follows that:

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_{\underline{\sigma}} &= \prod_{j=\underline{n}..1} \pi_{A_j; \underline{\sigma}(j)} \\ &= \prod_{j=\underline{n}.. \underline{n}+1} (\pi_{A_j;1} + \pi_{A_j;0}) \prod_{j=\underline{n}..1} \pi_{A_j; \underline{\sigma}(j)} \\ &= \sum_{\sigma' \in \mathcal{W}_+} \prod_{j=\underline{n}.. \underline{n}+1} \pi_{A_j; \sigma'(j)} \prod_{j=\underline{n}..1} \pi_{A_j; \underline{\sigma}(j)} \\ &= \sum_{\sigma \in \underline{\mathcal{W}}} \prod_{j=\underline{n}..1} \pi_{A_j; \sigma(j)} \\ &= \sum_{\sigma \in \underline{\mathcal{W}}} \pi_{\sigma} \end{aligned}$$

The general case can be proven in an analogous way by writing the products that occur here in the appropriate order. **QED**

The following lemma L.8.14 is purely technical. Its sole purpose is to prove the subsequent lemma L.8.15 by means of complete induction.

L.8.14 Let G_{rs} be subspaces of \mathcal{H} with

$$\forall (r,s) \in \underline{D} [s = \underline{\beta}(r) \Rightarrow G_{rs} = A_{rs} \text{ and } s \neq \underline{\beta}(r) \Rightarrow G_{rs} \in \{(A_{rs})^\perp, \mathcal{H}\}]$$

Then the following holds:

$$[\prod_{(r,s) \in \underline{D}} \pi_{G_{rs}}] L = L_{\underline{\beta}, \underline{r}}$$

Note: The order of the factors in the specified product is irrelevant due to L.8.7.

Proof: The proof is carried out by complete induction on

$$N := \# \{ (r,s) \in \underline{D} \mid s \neq \underline{\beta}(r) \wedge G_{rs} \neq \mathcal{H} \}$$

For $N = 0$, the assertion is trivial due to the definition of $L_{\underline{\beta}, \underline{r}}$. Now let $N > 0$. In this case, we

can choose an element $(r,s) \in \underline{D}$ with $s \neq \underline{\beta}(r)$ and $G_{rs} \neq \mathcal{H}$. It follows that $G_{rs} = (A_{rs})^\perp$. With $s' := \underline{\beta}(r)$, we have $G_{rs'} = A_{rs'}$ and $s \neq s'$. From (MR), as in the proof of L.8.11, we obtain the equation

$$\pi_{A_{rs}} \pi_{A_{rs'}} L = 0$$

Since the order of the factors in the product specified above does not matter, with

$$M := \prod_{(r,s) \in \underline{D} \setminus \{(r,s), (r,s')\}} \pi_{G_{rs}}$$

we get:

$$\begin{aligned} [\prod_{(r,s) \in \underline{D}} \pi_{G_{rs}}] L &= M \pi_{(A_{rs})^\perp} \pi_{A_{rs'}} L \\ &= M \pi_{\mathcal{H}} \pi_{A_{rs'}} L - M \pi_{A_{rs}} \pi_{A_{rs'}} L \\ &= M \pi_{\mathcal{H}} \pi_{A_{rs'}} L \\ &= L_{\underline{\beta}, \underline{r}} \end{aligned}$$

The last equation holds due to the induction hypothesis, since the product

$$M \pi_{\mathcal{H}} \pi_{A_{rs'}} L$$

has one less factor that is different from $\pi_{\mathcal{H}}$.

QED

L.8.15 It is

$$\pi_{\underline{\sigma}} \pi_{UR} = L_{\underline{\beta}, \underline{r}}$$

Proof: The statement is a special case of L.8.14. It can be obtained by setting for all $(r,s) \in \underline{D}$ with $s \neq \underline{\beta}(r)$:

$$G_{rs} := (A_{rs})^\perp$$

QED

L.8.16 It is

$$\text{tr } L_{\underline{\beta}, \underline{r}} (L_{\underline{\beta}, \underline{r}})^* = \text{tr } L_{\underline{\beta}, \underline{r}}$$

Proof: With

$$A := \bigcap_{r \leq \underline{r}} A_{r, \underline{\beta}(r)} \cap \bigcap_{j \in K'} \pi_{A_j}$$

we have:

$$\begin{aligned} L_{\underline{\beta}, \underline{r}} &= \pi_{A_{\underline{r}, \underline{\beta}(\underline{r})}} \cdots \pi_{A_{1, \underline{\beta}(1)}} \pi_{A_q} \cdots \pi_{A_1} \pi_{UR} \\ &= \pi_A \pi_{UR} \quad (\text{as in the proof of L.8.6}) \end{aligned}$$

It follows that:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{tr } L_{\underline{\beta}, \underline{r}} (L_{\underline{\beta}, \underline{r}})^* &= \text{tr } \pi_A \pi_{UR} \pi_{UR} \pi_A \\ &= \text{tr } \pi_A \pi_{UR} \\ &= \text{tr } L_{\underline{\beta}, \underline{r}} \end{aligned}$$

QED

L.8.17 It is

$$(Y_{\underline{\beta}, \underline{r}} \wedge N) = \exists \beta \in \underline{\mathfrak{B}} N_\beta$$

Proof: We have:

$$\begin{aligned} \omega \in (Y_{\underline{\beta}, \underline{r}} \wedge N) &\Leftrightarrow (\omega \in Y_{\underline{\beta}, \underline{r}}) \wedge (\omega \in N) \\ &\Leftrightarrow \forall_{r \leq \underline{r}} (\omega \in \langle A_{r, \underline{\beta}(r)} \rangle) \wedge \forall_r \exists_s (\omega \in \langle A_{rs} \rangle) \\ &\Leftrightarrow \exists \beta \in \underline{\mathfrak{B}} \forall_r (\omega \in \langle A_{r, \beta(r)} \rangle) \\ &\Leftrightarrow \exists \beta \in \underline{\mathfrak{B}} \omega \in (\forall_r \langle A_{r, \beta(r)} \rangle) \\ &\Leftrightarrow \exists \beta \in \underline{\mathfrak{B}} \omega \in N_\beta \\ &\Leftrightarrow \omega \in \exists \beta \in \underline{\mathfrak{B}} N_\beta \end{aligned}$$

QED

L.8.18 It is

$$\underline{\mathcal{W}} \cap \{ \sigma_\beta \mid \beta \in \underline{\mathfrak{B}} \} = \{ \sigma_\beta \mid \beta \in \underline{\mathfrak{B}} \}$$

Proof: Based on the definition of $\underline{\mathfrak{B}}$, it suffices to show for any $\beta \in \underline{\mathfrak{B}}$ that

$$\sigma_\beta \in \underline{\mathcal{W}} \Leftrightarrow \beta|_{\{1, \dots, \underline{r}\}} = \underline{\beta}$$

Because of the definition of σ_β , we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \forall_{j \in K'} \sigma_\beta(j) = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \forall_{(r,s) \in D} [s = \beta(r) \Rightarrow \sigma_\beta(k(r,s)) = 1] \\ \text{and} \quad \forall_{(r,s) \in D} [s \neq \beta(r) \Rightarrow \sigma_\beta(k(r,s)) = 0] \end{aligned}$$

Based on the definition of $\underline{\mathcal{W}}$ and $\underline{\sigma}$,

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_\beta \in \underline{\mathcal{W}} &\Leftrightarrow (\sigma_\beta)|_{\underline{J}} = \underline{\sigma} \\ &\Leftrightarrow \forall_{(r,s) \in \underline{D}} [s = \underline{\beta}(r) \Rightarrow \sigma_\beta(k(r,s)) = 1] \text{ and} \\ &\quad \forall_{(r,s) \in \underline{D}} [s \neq \underline{\beta}(r) \Rightarrow \sigma_\beta(k(r,s)) = 0] \end{aligned}$$

Because of $\underline{D} \subset D$ and $\forall_{(r,s) \in \underline{D}} (r \leq \underline{r})$, it follows from $\beta|_{\{1, \dots, \underline{r}\}} = \underline{\beta}$ that $\sigma_\beta \in \underline{\mathcal{W}}$.

Conversely, if $\sigma_\beta \in \underline{\mathcal{W}}$, then for all $r \leq \underline{r}$:

$$\begin{aligned} s = \underline{\beta}(r) &\Leftrightarrow \sigma_\beta(k(r,s)) = 1 \\ &\Leftrightarrow s = \beta(r) \end{aligned}$$

and thus $\underline{\beta}(r) = \beta(r)$. Consequently, $\beta|_{\{1, \dots, \underline{r}\}} = \underline{\beta}$.

QED

L.8.19 For all $\sigma \in \mathcal{W}_1$ with

$$\sigma \notin \{ \sigma_\beta \mid \beta \in \mathfrak{B} \}$$

the following holds:

$$\pi_{M_\sigma} \pi_{UR} = 0$$

Proof: Due to L.7.25, the claim only needs to be proven for $\sigma \in \mathcal{W}_1$ with $\sigma \notin \mathcal{W}_{\mathfrak{B}}$.

Since $\sigma \in \mathcal{W}_1 \subset \mathcal{W}$, we have $\sigma(k) \in \{0,1\}$ for all $k \in K$.

Because of $\sigma \notin \mathcal{W}_{\mathfrak{B}}$ and the definition of \mathcal{W}_β , there is an index r with

$$\sigma(k(r,s)) = 0 \quad (\text{for all } s)$$

For this r ,

$$M_\sigma < \bigcap_{j \in K'} A_j \cap \bigcap_s (A_{rs})^\perp$$

Because of L.8.12 (EX2),

$$G \wedge \bigvee_s \langle (A_{rs})^\perp \rangle = \emptyset$$

$$\langle UR \rangle \wedge \bigvee_{j \in K'} \langle A_j \rangle \wedge \bigvee_s \langle (A_{rs})^\perp \rangle = \emptyset$$

According to L.5.26, there are commutable D, D_j , and $D_{rs} < \mathcal{H}$ with

$$UR < D$$

$$A_j < D_j \quad (\text{for } j \in K')$$

$$(A_{rs})^\perp < D_{rs} \quad (\text{for all } s)$$

and

$$D \cap \bigcap_j D_j \cap \bigcap_s D_{rs} = 0$$

Now we have:

$$\bigcap_j D_j \cap \bigcap_s D_{rs} < D^\perp$$

$$M_\sigma < \bigcap_{j \in K'} A_j \cap \bigcap_s (A_{rs})^\perp$$

$$< \bigcap_{j \in K'} D_j \cap \bigcap_s D_{rs}$$

$$< D^\perp$$

$$< UR^\perp$$

It follows that

$$\pi_{M_\sigma} \pi_{UR} = 0$$

QED

L.8.20 It is

$$\sigma \in \underline{\mathcal{W}} \wedge \sigma \notin \{ \sigma_\beta \mid \beta \in \mathfrak{B} \} \Rightarrow \pi_\sigma \pi_{UR} = 0$$

Proof: Let the assignment σ satisfy the premises of this lemma. Because of $\underline{W} \subset W_1$ and L.8.19, we have

$$\pi_{M_\sigma} \pi_{UR} = 0$$

According to L.7.5,

$$\pi_\sigma \pi_{UR} = \pi_{M_\sigma} \pi_{UR}$$

This proves the assertion. **QED**

L.8.21 It is

$$\text{tr } L_{\underline{\beta}, \underline{r}} (L_{\underline{\beta}, \underline{r}})^* = \sum_{\beta \in \underline{\mathfrak{B}}} q_\beta$$

Proof: We have:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{tr } L_{\underline{\beta}, \underline{r}} (L_{\underline{\beta}, \underline{r}})^* &= \text{tr } L_{\underline{\beta}, \underline{r}} && \text{(L.8.16)} \\ &= \text{tr } \pi_\sigma \pi_{UR} && \text{(L.8.15)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \sum_{\sigma \in \underline{W}} \text{tr } \pi_\sigma \pi_{UR} && \text{(L.8.13)} \\ &= \sum_{\sigma \in \underline{W} \cap \{\sigma_\beta \mid \beta \in \underline{\mathfrak{B}}\}} \text{tr } \pi_\sigma \pi_{UR} && \text{(L.8.20)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \sum_{\beta \in \underline{\mathfrak{B}}} \text{tr } \pi_{\sigma_\beta} \pi_{UR} && \text{(L.8.18)} \\ &= \sum_{\beta \in \underline{\mathfrak{B}}} q_\beta && \text{(definition of } q_\beta) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \sum_{\beta \in \underline{\mathfrak{B}}} q_\beta && \text{(definition of } q_\beta) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \sum_{\beta \in \underline{\mathfrak{B}}} q_\beta && \text{(definition of } q_\beta) \end{aligned}$$

L.8.22 As a corollary to L.8.21,

$$\bar{q} = \text{tr } LL^*$$

Proof: We consider the case $\underline{r} = 0$. Then $\underline{\beta} = \emptyset$, $\underline{\mathfrak{B}} = \mathfrak{B}$, and $L_{\underline{\beta}, \underline{r}} = L$. Now,

$$\bar{q} = \sum_{\beta \in \mathfrak{B}} q_\beta \quad \text{(definition of } \bar{q})$$

$$= \sum_{\beta \in \underline{\mathfrak{B}}} q_\beta \quad \text{(since } \underline{\mathfrak{B}} = \mathfrak{B})$$

$$= \text{tr } L_{\underline{\beta}, \underline{r}} (L_{\underline{\beta}, \underline{r}})^* \quad \text{(L.8.21)}$$

$$= \text{tr } LL^* \quad \text{(since } L_{\underline{\beta}, \underline{r}} = L)$$

QED

L.8.23 It is

$$P_e(Y_{\underline{\beta}, \underline{r}}) = \text{tr } L_{\underline{\beta}, \underline{r}} (L_{\underline{\beta}, \underline{r}})^* / \text{tr } LL^*$$

Proof: Because of $Y_{\underline{\beta}, \underline{r}} \in \mathcal{A}_e$,

$$\begin{aligned} P_e(Y_{\underline{\beta}, \underline{r}}) &= \mu_e(Y_{\underline{\beta}, \underline{r}}) && \text{(since } \mu_e \text{ is concentrated on } N) \\ &= \mu_e(Y_{\underline{\beta}, \underline{r}} \wedge N) && \text{(L.8.17)} \\ &= \mu_e(\exists \beta \in \underline{\mathfrak{B}} N_\beta) && \text{(L.7.31)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \sum_{\beta \in \underline{\mathfrak{B}}} p_\beta && \text{(definition of } p_\beta) \\ &= \sum_{\beta \in \underline{\mathfrak{B}}} q_\beta / \bar{q} && \text{(definition of } p_\beta) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \sum_{\beta \in \underline{\mathfrak{B}}} q_\beta / \bar{q} && \text{(definition of } p_\beta) \\ &= \text{tr } L_{\underline{\beta}, \underline{r}} (L_{\underline{\beta}, \underline{r}})^* / \bar{q} && \text{(L.8.21)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \text{tr } L_{\underline{\beta}, \underline{r}} (L_{\underline{\beta}, \underline{r}})^* / \text{tr } LL^* && \text{(L.8.22)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \text{tr } L_{\underline{\beta}, \underline{r}} (L_{\underline{\beta}, \underline{r}})^* / \text{tr } LL^* && \text{(L.8.22)} \end{aligned}$$

QED

For operators L on \mathcal{H}_Q and M on \mathcal{H}_{Q^-} , the tensor product is defined by:

$$(L \otimes M)(\varphi_1 \otimes \varphi_2) := L\varphi_1 \otimes M\varphi_2 \quad (\text{for all } \varphi_1 \in \mathcal{H}_Q \text{ and } \varphi_2 \in \mathcal{H}_{Q^-})$$

and for an operator L on \mathcal{H} we have

$$\alpha_Q(L) = L \otimes I_{Q^-}$$

where I_{Q^-} is the identity operator on \mathcal{H}_{Q^-} .

L.8.24 For every subspace $A < \mathcal{H}_Q$,

$$\alpha_Q(\pi_A) = \pi_{\alpha_Q(A)}$$

Proof: This can easily be proven using well-known properties of the tensor product. **QED**

L.8.25 Let Q be a subsystem of \mathcal{H} and W an operator on \mathcal{H} . Moreover, let C' be a subspace of \mathcal{H}_Q and $C := \alpha_Q(C')$. Then:

$$\text{tr}_Q[\pi_C W \pi_C] = \pi_{C'} \text{tr}_Q[W] \pi_{C'}$$

Proof: Using the matrix notation introduced in Chapter B0, we can represent W as

$$W = (W_{kl})_{kl}$$

With I_{Q^-} being the identity operator on \mathcal{H}_{Q^-} , we get

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_C &= \pi_{\alpha_Q(C')} \\ &= \alpha_Q(\pi_{C'}) \quad (\text{L.8.24}) \\ &= \pi_{C'} \otimes I_{Q^-} \end{aligned}$$

Thus we have

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_C W \pi_C &= (\pi_{C'} \otimes I_{Q^-}) (W_{kl})_{kl} (\pi_{C'} \otimes I_{Q^-}) \\ &= (\pi_{C'} W_{kl} \pi_{C'})_{kl} \end{aligned}$$

and consequently,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{tr}_Q[\pi_C W \pi_C] &= \sum_k (\pi_{C'} W_{kk} \pi_{C'}) \\ &= \pi_{C'} (\sum_k W_{kk}) \pi_{C'} \\ &= \pi_{C'} \text{tr}_Q[W] \pi_{C'} \end{aligned}$$

QED

L.8.26 For every operator W on \mathcal{H} and every subspace $F < \mathcal{H}_Q$, the following equation holds with $C := \alpha_Q(F)$:

$$\text{tr} \pi_C W = \text{tr} \pi_F \text{tr}_Q[W]$$

Proof: Applying the matrix representation used in the proof of L.8.25

$$W = (W_{kl})_{kl}$$

we obtain (for every operator W):

$$\begin{aligned} (*) \text{tr} W &= \text{tr} (W_{kl})_{kl} \\ &= \sum_k \text{tr} W_{kk} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \text{tr} \sum_k W_{kk} \\ &= \text{tr} \text{tr}_Q[W] \end{aligned}$$

As in the proof of L.8.25, it can be shown that:

$$\text{tr}_Q[\pi_C W] = \pi_F \text{tr}_Q[W]$$

By applying (*) to $[\pi_C W]$, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{tr} \pi_C W &= \text{tr} \text{tr}_Q[\pi_C W] \\ &= \text{tr} \pi_F \text{tr}_Q[W] \end{aligned}$$

QED

Theorem T.8.1 For all $(r,s) \in D$ and $\beta \in \mathfrak{B}_{r-1}$,

$$(PR) P_e(\langle A_{rs} \rangle | Y_{\beta,r-1}) = \text{tr} \pi_{F_{rs}} W_{Q;\tau_r | \mathcal{G}_{\beta,r-1}}$$

Proof: Let $(r,s) \in D$ and $\beta \in \mathfrak{B}_{r-1}$. Let $\beta' \in \mathfrak{B}_r$ be defined by

$$\beta' |_{\{1,\dots,r-1\}} = \beta$$

and

$$\beta'(r) = s$$

Then with

$$L' := L_{\beta,r-1}$$

and

$$L'' := L_{\beta',r}$$

we obtain from L.8.23:

$$\begin{aligned} P_e(Y_{\beta,r-1}) &= \text{tr} L'(L')^* / \text{tr} LL^* \\ P_e(Y_{\beta',r}) &= \text{tr} L''(L'')^* / \text{tr} LL^* \end{aligned}$$

Based on the definitions given above, we get:

$$\begin{aligned} L'' &= \pi_{A_{rs}} L' \\ Y_{\beta',r} &= \langle A_{rs} \rangle \wedge Y_{\beta,r-1} \end{aligned}$$

With

$$W' := L'(L')^* / \text{tr} L'(L')^*$$

and

$$(W')_{\tau_r} := U_{\tau_r} W' U_{-\tau_r}$$

due to the definition of the conditional quantum state, we have:

$$W_{Q;\tau_r | \mathcal{G}_{\beta,r-1}} = \text{tr}_Q[(W')_{\tau_r}]$$

It follows that:

$$\begin{aligned} &P_e(\langle A_{rs} \rangle | Y_{\beta,r-1}) \\ &= P_e(\langle A_{rs} \rangle \wedge Y_{\beta,r-1}) / P_e(Y_{\beta,r-1}) \\ &= P_e(Y_{\beta',r}) / P_e(Y_{\beta,r-1}) \\ &= \text{tr} L''(L'')^* / \text{tr} L'(L')^* \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \text{tr } \pi_{A_{rs}} L'(L)^* \pi_{A_{rs}} / \text{tr } L'(L)^* \\
 &= \text{tr } \pi_{A_{rs}} W' \pi_{A_{rs}} \\
 &= \text{tr } \pi_{A_{rs}} W' \\
 &= \text{tr } \pi_{B_{rs}} W' && \text{(according to (MR))} \\
 &= \text{tr } U_{-\tau_r} \pi_{X_{rs}} U_{\tau_r} W' && \text{(since } B_{rs} = U_{-\tau_r} X_{rs}) \\
 &= \text{tr } \pi_{X_{rs}} U_{\tau_r} W' U_{-\tau_r} \\
 &= \text{tr } \pi_{X_{rs}} (W')_{\tau_r} \\
 &= \text{tr } \pi_{F_{rs}} \text{tr}_Q[(W')_{\tau_r}] && \text{(by L.8.26, since } X_{rs} = \alpha_Q(F_{rs})) \\
 &= \text{tr } \pi_{F_{rs}} W_{Q;\tau_r} | \mathcal{G}_{\beta,r-1} && \text{(definition of the quantum state)} \quad \mathbf{QED}
 \end{aligned}$$

The following relationships exist between the expressions used here and those appearing in Part A, Section 19:

$$\begin{aligned}
 A &= F_{rs} \\
 \tau &= \tau_r \\
 M_A &= (E_{rs}, t_{rs})
 \end{aligned}$$

As noted above, $\langle A_{rs} \rangle$ corresponds to the possible fact that (E_{rs}, t_{rs}) occurs. Therefore, M_A also stands for $\langle A_{rs} \rangle$.

Moreover, we have

$$M_1 \wedge \dots \wedge M_{r-1} = Y_{\beta,r-1}$$

$$\mathcal{B}_{r-1} = \mathcal{G}_{\beta,r-1}$$

and consequently

$$\begin{aligned}
 W_{r-1} &:= W_{Q;\tau} | \mathcal{B}_{r-1} \\
 &= W_{Q;\tau_r} | \mathcal{G}_{\beta,r-1}
 \end{aligned}$$

Substituting the corresponding expressions into Theorem T.8.1, we obtain:

Theorem T.8.2

$$P_e(M_A | M_1 \wedge \dots \wedge M_{r-1}) = \text{tr}(\pi_A W_{r-1})$$

6. The quantum state after measurement

In this section we show that the quantum state after measurement can be calculated using the equation known from the formalism of quantum theory.

Let $(r,s) \in D$ and $\beta \in \mathfrak{B}_{r-1}$. Let $\beta' \in \mathfrak{B}_r$ be defined by

$$\beta' |_{\{1,\dots,r-1\}} = \beta$$

and

$$\beta'(r) = s$$

Furthermore, let:

$$\underline{W}' := W_{Q;\tau_r|\mathcal{G}_{\beta,r-1}}$$

$$\underline{W}'' := W_{Q;\tau_r|\mathcal{G}_{\beta',r}}$$

Theorem T.8.3 With $F := F_{rs}$ the following equation holds:

$$(ST) \quad \underline{W}'' = \pi_F \underline{W}' \pi_F / \text{tr}(\pi_F \underline{W}' \pi_F)$$

Proof: Let

$$L' := L_{\beta,r-1}$$

$$L'' := L_{\beta',r}$$

$$W' := L'(L')^* / \text{tr} L'(L')^*$$

$$W'' := L''(L'')^* / \text{tr} L''(L'')^*$$

$$(W')_{\tau_r} := U_{\tau_r} W' U_{-\tau_r}$$

$$(W'')_{\tau_r} := U_{\tau_r} W'' U_{-\tau_r}$$

Based on the definitions given above, we have

$$\underline{W}' = \text{tr}_Q[(W')_{\tau_r}]$$

$$\underline{W}'' = \text{tr}_Q[(W'')_{\tau_r}]$$

and

$$L'' = \pi_{A_{rs}} L'$$

$$= \pi_{B_{rs}} L' \quad (\text{according to (MR)})$$

It follows that

$$W'' = \pi_{B_{rs}} W' \pi_{B_{rs}} / \text{tr}(\pi_{B_{rs}} W' \pi_{B_{rs}})$$

and because of $B_{rs} = U_{-\tau_r} X_{rs}$ we obtain:

$$(W'')_{\tau_r} = \pi_{X_{rs}} (W')_{\tau_r} \pi_{X_{rs}} / \text{tr}(\pi_{X_{rs}} (W')_{\tau_r} \pi_{X_{rs}})$$

As in the proof of L.8.26, it can be shown for every operator W that:

$$\text{tr} W = \text{tr} \text{tr}_Q[W]$$

It follows that:

$$\underline{W}'' = \text{tr}_Q[(W'')_{\tau_r}]$$

$$= \text{tr}_Q[\pi_{X_{rs}} (W')_{\tau_r} \pi_{X_{rs}}] / \text{tr} \text{tr}_Q[\pi_{X_{rs}} (W')_{\tau_r} \pi_{X_{rs}}]$$

$$= \pi_F \text{tr}_Q[(W')_{\tau_r}] \pi_F / \text{tr}(\pi_F \text{tr}_Q[(W')_{\tau_r}] \pi_F) \quad (\text{by L.8.25, since } X_{rs} = \alpha_Q(F))$$

$$= \pi_F \underline{W}' \pi_F / \text{tr}(\pi_F \underline{W}' \pi_F)$$

QED

The following relationships exist between the expressions used here and those appearing in Part A, Section 19:

$$A = F$$

$$\mathcal{B}_{r-1} = \mathcal{G}_{\beta, r-1}$$

$$\mathcal{B}_r = \mathcal{G}_{\beta', r}$$

Thus, we have:

$$W_{r-1} = \underline{W}' \quad (\text{quantum state "before measurement"})$$

$$W_r = \underline{W}'' \quad (\text{quantum state "after measurement"})$$

Substituting the corresponding expressions into Theorem T.8.3, we obtain:

Theorem T.8.4

$$W_r = \pi_A W_{r-1} \pi_A / \text{tr} (\pi_A W_{r-1} \pi_A)$$

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